

AFCOS

D4.1 Course Syllabus

**Project: Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization
for Boosting the Twin Transition**

Acronym: AFCOS

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General introduction

The AFCOS training “THE STANDARDIZATION OF INNOVATIONS - UNDERSTANDING THE SIGNIFICANCE OF IMPLEMENTING STANDARDS. LEGISLATION. PROCESS OF STANDARDS DEVELOPMENT AND ADOPTION” is designed to develop knowledge and skills related to the standardization of new construction products. It combines theoretical training for students with practical modules for industry representatives. The course reflects the need for professionals to become familiar with the requirements of standardization and new construction products. The trainings are developed based on the roadmaps produced in WP3 and their results will be reflected in the Whitepaper produced within WP5.

Introduction to the training programme

The training programme “THE STANDARDIZATION OF INNOVATIONS - UNDERSTANDING THE SIGNIFICANCE OF IMPLEMENTING STANDARDS. LEGISLATION. PROCESS OF STANDARDS DEVELOPMENT AND ADOPTION” is developed to serve the needs of master students and industry representatives and more particularly to familiarize participants with the basic principles and stages of standardization, the importance and application of standards, legislation, and the process of developing and adopting standards. Therefore, the programme is developed into two courses – one for each target group, as follows:

Course name	Modules	Target group
#1 General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry	Module 1 Fundamentals of European technical legislation and standardization	Master students
	Module 2 Product responsibility and market surveillance	Master students
#2 Specific rules for standardization of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope	Module 3 Green & Digital Transition	Industry representatives
	Module 4 How to standardize innovative products “low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products” and “bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope”.	Industry representatives

Course Syllabus

Course 1 General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry

Module 1 Fundamentals of European technical legislation and standardization

Module description	Introduction to the basic concepts and principles of European technical legislation and standardization
Learning outcomes	Trainees will acquire knowledge about the role and importance of European technical legislation, the essence and significance of the main European regulatory acts, knowledge of the basic and specific requirements of the CPR, the basic concepts, functions and meaning of standards, the mechanism and meaning of the conditionally binding nature of standards, the role and importance of awareness of new construction products.
Module outline	The module consists of six topics. Each topic will have a duration of one lesson - 40 minutes. After the topics, there will be a practical application of the lessons learned from the module by solving cases, debates and serious games lasting 80 minutes.

Table 1: MASTER STUDENTS: Module 1: Fundamentals of European technical legislation and standardization (8 hours)

Topic	Duration	Lecturers	Training method	Form of training	Learning outcomes
Topic 1: Essence and importance of European technical legislation	1 class hour (40 min)	Bulgaria - TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. I. Tsenkolovska	Lecture, presentation, discussion	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	After mastering the material on the topic, learners will understand the essence of European technical legislation and will be able to apply its principles and be required to solve specific tasks in various areas of the economy.
Topic 2: Legislative acts of the European Union - regulations, directives, decisions, etc.	1 class hour (40 min)	Bulgaria - TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. I. Tsenkolovska	Lecture, presentation, discussion	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	After mastering the material on the topic, the learners will understand the importance of European legislative acts, will be able to assess which acts a given product is covered by and what requirements it must meet in order to be admitted to the European market.
Topic 3: Requirements of the Construction Products Regulation	1 class hour (40 min)	Bulgaria - TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. G. Stanchev	Lecture, presentation, discussion	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	After mastering the material on the topic, the trainees will understand the meaning of CPR, and will be able to apply its requirements when developing new construction products.
Topic 4: Basic concepts of standardization. Types of standards and standard deliverables, status and functions of standards	1 class hour (40 min)	Bulgaria - Bulgaria - TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. G. Stanchev	Lecture, presentation, discussion	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	After mastering the material on the topic, learners will know the conceptual framework in the field of standardization, the principles, functions and importance of standards.

Topic	Duration	Lecturers	Training method	Form of training	Learning outcomes
Topic 5: Mechanism for "conditional obligation" of standards	1 class hour (40 min)	Bulgaria - Bulgaria - TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. G. Stanchev	Lecture, presentation, discussion	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	After mastering the material on the topic, learners will understand the mechanism for conditional binding of standards and will be able to apply it when concluding and executing contracts and implementing regulatory documents where standards are cited.
Topic 6: Awareness of new products	1 class hour (40 min)	Bulgaria - TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. G. Stanchev , Assoc. Prof. B. Ilieva, Assoc. Prof. I. Tsenkolovska	Lecture, presentation, discussion	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	After mastering the material on the topic, learners will be able to analyze and apply the legislative requirements for new construction products and will be able to make informed decisions.
Practical application to case studies on the topics	2 class hour (80 min)	Bulgaria - TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. G. Stanchev Assoc. Prof. B. Ilieva, Assoc. Prof. I. Tsenkolovska	Exercise, explanation, practical work and case solving, brainstorming	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	Acquiring practical knowledge and skills by solving specific causes

Module 2 Product responsibility and market surveillance

Module description	Introduction to the basic concepts and principles of product responsibility and market surveillance.
Learning outcomes	Learners will gain knowledge of the basic concepts and requirements for conformity assessment, the principles of CE marking and products that require CE marking, the requirements for the preparation of technical product documentation and declaration of conformity. Knowledge of the legal requirements for product liability and consumer protection and market surveillance.
Module outline	The module consists of six topics. Each topic will have a duration of one lesson - 40 minutes. After the topics, there will be a practical application of the lessons learned from the module by solving cases, debates and serious games lasting 80 minutes.

Table 2: MASTER STUDENTS: Module 2: Product responsibility and market surveillance (8 hours)

Topic	Duration	Lecturers	Training method	Form of training	Learning outcomes
Topic 1: Conformity assessment, concepts and criteria	1 class hour (40 min)	Bulgaria - TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. B. Ilieva	Lecture, presentation, discussion	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	After mastering the material on the topic, the learners will know the principles for assessing the compliance of products with the requirements of European legislative acts, the criteria for implementing product safety requirements and placing them on the market.

Topic	Duration	Lecturers	Training method	Form of training	Learning outcomes
Topic 2: Documentation of conformity assessment. Principles of CE marking	1 class hour (40 min)	Bulgaria - TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. G. Stanchev	Lecture, presentation, discussion	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	After mastering the material on the topic, the trainees will know the procedures for assessing conformity, the principles of CE marking. They will have the skills to prepare the necessary documentation in accordance with European legislative requirements. They will acquire skills to work with standards and specific technical literature.
Topic 3: Products for CE marking	1 class hour (40 min)	TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. B. Ilieva	Lecture, presentation, discussion	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	After mastering the material on the topic, the trainees will be familiar with the products for which CE marking is provided and will be able to determine the essential safety requirements of a given product.
Topic 4: Declaration of performance and Technical documentation	1 class hour (40 min)	Bulgaria - TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. G. Stanchev	Lecture, presentation, discussion	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	After mastering the material on the topic, the learners will be familiar with the main legislative requirements of the European Union that require a declaration of conformity, the content and form of the declaration of conformity. They will be able to make a connection between the declaration of conformity and the technical documentation. They will acquire skills in drawing up a declaration of conformity and skills in using other documents as a basis for the declaration of conformity.

Topic	Duration	Lecturers	Training method	Form of training	Learning outcomes
Topic 5: Product Liability and Consumer Protection	1 class hour (40 min)	TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. G. Stanchev	Lecture, presentation, discussion	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	After mastering the material on the topic, the trainees will understand the obligations of economic operators for product liability and consumer protection.
Topic 6: European market surveillance legislation	1 class hour (40 min)	Bulgaria - TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. G. Stanchev Assoc. Prof. B. Ilieva, Assoc. Prof. I. Tsenkolovska	Lecture, presentation, discussion	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	After mastering the material on the topic, the trainees will learn and apply the principles of market surveillance. They will be introduced to the functions and work of the regulatory authorities for market surveillance.
Practical application to case studies on the topics	2 class hour (80 min)	Bulgaria - TU-Sofia: Assoc. Prof. G. Stanchev Assoc. Prof. B. Ilieva, Assoc. Prof. I. Tsenkolovska	Exercise, explanation, practical work and case solving, brainstorming	Bulgaria TU – Sofia, Classroom learning	Acquiring practical knowledge and skills by solving specific causes

Course 2 Specific rules for standardization of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope

Module 3 Green & Digital transition

Module description	Introduction to the sustainability concept and how this is applied to buildings and the importance of European taxonomy.
Learning outcomes	Learners will understand the importance of carbon footprint, circular economy, different way for assessing green buildings (BREEAM; LEED and GREEN HOMES), the ESG and their impact on large companies, the importance of European taxonomy and the impact on green financing. The learners will gain knowledge of the basic concepts of sustainability and ways to improve it through innovative materials and solutions in buildings.
Module outline	The module consists of five topics. Each topic will have a duration of one lesson - 40 minutes, except topic 1. For each topic there will be case studies, which will help learners to have a better understanding.

Table 3: INDUSTRY REPRESENTATIVES: Module 3: Green & Digital Transition (6 hours)

Topic	Duration	Lecturers	Training method	Form of training	Learning outcomes
Topic 1: Carbon footprint (LCA calculation)	2 class hours (80 min)	RoGBC Assoc. prof. Tania Rus	Lecture, presentations, comparison of two solutions, discussion	RoGBC Online	To understand the role carbon footprint and of EPDs, and can apply some basic calculations and analyze two solutions

Topic	Duration	Lecturers	Training method	Form of training	Learning outcomes
Topic 2: Circular economy	1 class hour (40 min)	RoGBC Assist.prof. Hora'iu Albu	Lecture, presentations, discussion	RoGBC Online	To be able to apply the circular economy principle in the building sector and to analyze the pros and cons of building materials reuse.
Topic 3: Green buildings certifications	1 class hour (40 min)	RoGBC Elena Rastei	Lecture, presentations, discussion	RoGBC Online	Understanding the difference between energy efficient buildings and green ones. Apply BREEAM, LEED, WELL concepts for a specific building.
Topic 4: ESG	1 class hour (40 min)	RoGBC Dr. Dorin Beu	Lecture, presentations, discussion	RoGBC Online	Understanding the principle of Do no Harm and European Taxonomy. Analyze the pros and cons of a specific company.
Topic 5: Green financing	1 class hour (40 min)	RoGBC Dr. Dorin Beu	Lecture, presentations, discussion	RoGBC Online	Understand the role and benefits for banks, investors and end-users. Apply the concept for house/apartment.

Module 4 How to standardize innovative products “low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products” and “bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope

Module description	Introduction to the European standardization concepts and principles of product responsibility and market surveillance.
Learning outcomes	Learners will focus on two types of products as case studies and concentrate on the standardization barriers and what are the options for obtaining the

	CE label through different standardization options. A major outcome will be to understand European market access - understanding EAD, ETA, hEN and the need for harmonized standards, costs and preparation timelines. CWA simulation: standards development for market access. Another outcome will be Eco-design regulation (Regulation (EU) 2024/1781) and the Digital product passport acc. to Construction Products Regulation (CPR)
Module outline	The module consists of five topics. Each topic will have a duration of one lesson - 40 minutes, except topic 4. After each topic, there will be a discussion about practical application of the lessons.

Table 4: INDUSTRY REPRESENTATIVES: Module 4: How to standardize innovative products “low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products” and “bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope” (6 hours)

Topic	Duration	Lecturers	Training method	Form of training	Expected results
Topic 1: Technological features of innovative building products - low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope.	1 class hour (40 min)	RoGBC Dr. Dorin Beu	Lecture, presentations, discussion	RoGBC Online	Understanding issues related to cement and thermal insulations. Solutions for cement decarbonization and bio-based thermal insulation solutions. Results of an AFCOS survey regarding the main problems of these two kinds of construction products.
Topic 2: Next-generation	1 class hour (40 min)	RoGBC Theodor Conțolencu	Lecture, presentations,	RoGBC	Barriers for innovative products with a focus on standardization. Possible solutions

Topic	Duration	Lecturers	Training method	Form of training	Expected results
construction products: filling knowledge gaps for construction products' producers, construction companies and designers			discussion	Online	for overrun these barriers. Proposed actions.
Topic 3: Understanding new standards: preparing construction stakeholders (product manufacturers, designers, building control and assessment bodies) for evolving building products requirements. Understanding standards and the role of national standardization bodies	1 class hour (40 min)	RoGBC Dr. Dorin Beu	Lecture, presentations, discussion	RoGBC Online	Understanding the EU standardization process: identification of needs, preparation and plannings, development of draft standard, consultation and consensus, approval and adoption, publication and distribution, implementation and compliance, monitoring and review. Alignment between European and International Standardization

Topic	Duration	Lecturers	Training method	Form of training	Expected results
Topic 4: Navigating European market access - understanding EAD, ETA, hEN and the need for harmonized standards, costs and preparation timelines. CWA simulation: standards development for market access.	2 class hours (80 min)	RoGBC Dr. Dorin Beu	Lecture, presentations, discussion	RoGBC Online	Other deliverables of CEN and CENELEC – beside EN: Harmonized European Standard (hEN), Technical Specification (TS), Technical Report (TR), Harmonization Document (HD), CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA), CEN and/or CENELEC Guides. EN timeline. CE label. Differences between CWA and EN. Development of a CWA. The European Technical Assessment (ETA) and the European Assessment Document (EAD). Comparison between EN, CWA and ETA/EAD
Topic 5: Eco-design regulation (Regulation (EU) 2024/1781) and the Digital product passport acc. to Construction Products Regulation (CPR)	1 class hour (40 min)	RoGBC Dr. Dorin Beu	Lecture, presentations, discussion	RoGBC Online	EcoDesign: Scope, application and Extended information obligations. Digital Product Passport – DPP and obligation for manufacturers, importers and distributors. What changed with the Construction Products Regulation - CPR update? Overview of the new CPR timeframe

Annexes

The training materials in the format of PPT presentations are attached as Annexes.

Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

AFCOS

Topic 1: Essence and importance of European technical legislation

Module 1 “Fundamentals of European technical legislation and standardization”
Course “General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry”

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ESSENCE AND MEANING

The European Union (EU) is a unique phenomenon on a global scale. It creates a common economic space between countries with different levels of law, economy, and different moral norms of public life.

The main goal of the EU is, while taking into account these differences, to build a single market mechanism in the member states and to use appropriate means and activities.

For this purpose, a product manufactured in any member state must meet the same European technical requirements.

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ESSENCE AND MEANING

The functioning of the EU is based on a unique legal system that exists in parallel with the legal systems of the member states and with the international law.

The EU legal system is divided into two subsystems – primary law and secondary law.

EU primary law encompasses the treaties that govern the successive formation of the current EU and the relationships between member states.

An essential legislative object is the establishment creation of an economic space without borders for the free movement of products, services, people and capital.

ESSENCE AND MEANING

Secondary EU law is conventionally called European Technical Legislation (ETL).

Unlike classical international organizations and like the legislature of a state, the EU, through the activities of its institutions, creates laws to which not only member states, but also their individuals and legal entities are subject within the spheres of activity transferred to the EU.

Although the terms “law” and “legislation” are deliberately avoided in the treaties, the Court of Justice of the EU does not hesitate to use formulations such as “legislative system of the treaty” or “EU legislature”.

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ESSENCE AND MEANING

The legal acts that the EU institutions adopt on the basis of the Treaties (primary law) and serving to implement them, constitute the sources of the ETC (secondary law).

The contracts provide the possibility of adopting various legal acts:

- acts which have direct effect on the territory of the Member States;

- framework rules, that set out only the objective to be achieved and give the Member States the choice of form and means.

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ESSENCE AND MEANING

The Court of Justice of the EU has clarified the principle of harmonisation on which technical legislation is based.

It states:

“Any product which circulates on the market of one country must also circulate freely on the markets of the other Member States.”

In order to satisfy this principle, it is necessary to build a structured and extensive system, which is formed by the two subsystems - of the ETL and of the European standardization.

Their goal is to resolve all issues of harmonization/unification of norms and requirements for products and services in a particular country in such a way that they can freely appear on the markets of other countries.

ESSENCE AND MEANING

In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to analyze in detail all the circumstances affecting the functioning of the market and to smooth out the differences in the regulations of different countries.

The EU Commission is obliged, when preparing proposals for the harmonisation of national legislation in the fields of health, safety, environmental protection and consumer protection, to use the highest level of protection as a basis.

Particularly important is the harmonization of legal provisions and standardized prescriptions that relate to the regulated area of public interest.

ESSENCE AND MEANING

Directions of the public interest regulated area:

- protection of health and life of humans and animals and protection of plants;
- protection of the working environment and health and labour safety;
- protection of the environment;
- protection of public order and security and preservation of public morals;
- protection of national monuments and values of artistic, historical and archaeological value;
- protection of intellectual property and competition.

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ESSENCE AND MEANING

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As a result of these two areas of impact of the technical legislation, the preconditions for a real opening of borders between the parties, the establishment and functioning of the Single European Market (SEM) are created.

By merging their national markets, the Member States create a single area in which goods, services, people and capital move freely across national borders.

Uniform conditions of competition and uniform rules are established for individuals and legal entities from different Member States.

THE EUROPEAN SINGLE MARKET

The single market, launched in 1993, guarantees the free movement of:

- Goods
- Services
- Capital
- People

- Current members:
- EU countries
 - Agreement on the European Economic Area (EEA)
Iceland Liechtenstein Norway
 - Bilateral agreements
Switzerland

Sources: European Commission and European Parliament

Σημερινά μέλη:

- Χώρας της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης
- Συμφωνία για τον Ευρωπαϊκό Οικονομικό Χώρο (ΕΕΧ)
Ισλανδία Λιχτενστάιν Νορβηγία
- Διμερείς συμφωνίες
Ελβετία

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ESSENCE AND MEANING

The concept of “technical legislation” is specific to the EU law.

“Technical legislation” refers to the development of “technical legislative acts”, so-called because their legal rules are predominantly technical in nature.

There are two varieties:

legislative acts governing objects or fields in typically technical sectors such as mechanical engineering, electrical engineering/electrical equipment, communications, fire protection, measurement and measuring instruments, etc. ;

legislative acts acts which, in their separate parts, lay down technical provisions to ensure safety at work, the use of products as intended, or requirements for technical parameters of products and services, registration, production and control arrangements.

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ESSENCE AND MEANING

EU technical legislative acts are primarily intended for products and services and aim to:

- to eliminate differences in specific technical norms where those differences are so great in the various Member States that they become technical barriers;

- In order to ensure that such forms effectively have the effect of imposing customs duties and restrictions on trade between Member States, they must be reasonably harmonised, which is facilitated by European legislation.

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ESSENCE AND MEANING

FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES

Although separated into an autonomous legal order, the EEA is neither alien nor external to the national laws of the Member States. It penetrates into the internal law of each of them and is integrated into it without, however, losing its identity.

The relationship between the two legal systems is defined by:

- the direct applicability of the ETL;
- the direct effect of a large number of its provisions;
- the primacy of the ETL over national law.

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FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES

Direct applicability of the ETL

- The principle of direct applicability of the ETL means that its provisions automatically acquire the status of positive law in the national legal systems of the Member States and become an integral part of them.

Direct effect of a large number of provisions

- The possibility for citizens and legal entities under the jurisdiction of a Member State to derive rights directly from the rules of the ETL is known as the direct effect of this right.

FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES

Priority of the ETL over national legislation

- By integrating directly into national law, the ETL may encounter rules that conflict with it. In the event of such a conflict, the question arises: which of the two legal systems should give way to the other (which of the two systems will prevail over the other)?
- The Court of Justice of the EU has formulated the principle of the primacy of the ETL over national law and declared it to be “vital” for the very existence of integration.

Предимството се извежда от:

- “transfer” of sovereignty from the Member States to the EU in accordance with the Treaties, which has the effect of definitive restriction in the relevant area of their rights;
- the binding nature of EU law;
- the unity of the EU legal order, i.e. its uniform application throughout the EU.

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The principle of the primacy of the ETL over national law requires that this primacy be ensured equally and efficiently, directly and immediately throughout the territory of the EU.

The national authorities have an obligation to do so.

The Court of Justice may declare an ETL incompatible with national law, but it cannot annul the national legislation.

For the competent national authorities, the primacy means a prohibition on applying a national provision incompatible with EU law and, if necessary, to take the required action to ensure the full operation of the ETL.

FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES

FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES

States are obliged to compensate natural and legal persons for the damage caused to them as a result of a breach of the ETL by public authorities.

The purpose of the ETL is the technical harmonisation of national legislation and standardisation in order to regulate the essential legislative subject-matter of European law - the establishment and functioning of the Single European Market with the free movement of goods, services, persons and capital.

Sources:

1. Сандалски Бр., М. Вичева, Г. Дюкенджиев, И. Николова, Г. Станчев, Б. Илиева, М. Митова, И. Буров, Б. Георгиев – Техническа конкурентноспособност на промишлените продукти в Европейския съюз, изд. “Изток-Запад”, ISBN 619152888-4.

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

AFCOS

Topic 2: Legislative acts of the European Union - regulations, directives, decisions, etc.

Module 1 “Fundamentals of European technical legislation and standardization”
Course “General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry”

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LEGISLATIVE ACTS OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

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European technical legislation (ETL) covers the technical legislative acts and documents.

These acts may be adopted by the institutions of the EU within the scope of competences conferred on them and in accordance with the procedure set out in the Treaty.

Each of the acts is defined by indicating its specific features. This makes it possible to determine the exact legal nature of each specific act.

Technical legislative acts are: regulations, directives, decisions, etc. They shall be published in the Official Journal of the EU.

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REGULATIONS

REGULATIONS

A regulation is the most characteristic expression of the EU's legislative power. It has a direct impact on the national legal systems of the Member States.

It is mandatory in its entirety and directly applicable in all Member States.

The Regulation defines generally and objectively the hypotheses to which it is applicable and the legal consequences for the categories of persons considered in the abstract and as a whole.

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REGULATIONS

A regulation has general application, unlike the decisions addressed to individuals.

The Regulation is mandatory in its entirety. The mandatory character distinguishes it from recommendations and opinions which are not obligatory.

The obligation of all its elements contrasts and distinguishes it from directives, which are binding only with regard to the result to be achieved.

The fact that a regulation is mandatory in its entirety means that the Member States cannot apply it only partially or selectively, change the conditions for its application or divert some of its provisions.

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REGULATIONS

The Regulation is directly applicable in all Member States. This means two things:

First, acts of this kind have immediate effect in the sense that, from the moment of their entry into force, they bring all their effects into national law without the need for a national act for that purpose.

Second, its direct effect means that it has a straight impact. Its very essence is the creation of rights for the benefit of the individuals under the jurisdiction of the Member States.

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REGULATIONS

The direct effect of the regulation gives rise not only to rights but also to obligations which individuals can bring before the national courts.

The meaning and place of the regulation in the EU legal system corresponds to that of laws in national legal systems.

A regulation is an instrument through which regulatory sovereignty is transferred from the Member States to the EU.

Regulations themselves also have a hierarchy.

There are those that are based directly on the provisions of the Treaties and are intended to secure their application. On the basis of these, another regulation subsequently provides the complete and detailed regulation of the relevant matter.

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DIRECTIVES

DIRECTIVES

A directive is the most common type of EU legislative act.

Its purpose is to:

take into account national traditions and legal structures;

to avoid contradictions and conflicts in the harmonisation of technical market conditions in the Member States.

Directives oblige the Member States to which they are addressed with regard to the result to be achieved by them, leaving to national authorities the choice of the forms and means to be used for that result.

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DIRECTIVES

Unlike a Regulation, a Directive is the appropriate legal instrument for issues where Member States have retained national competence and the EU is only concerned with coordinating or harmonising national rules.

In principle, and unlike the Regulation, the Directive is not of general application, but rather binds the Member States to which it is explicitly addressed: one, several or all together.

It creates an obligation only for an outcome to be achieved in the national law.

DIRECTIVES

The choice of the forms and means of achieving the result is left to the competent national authorities of the State addressed.

They decide, in accordance with their national law, whether a directive should be implemented by a legislative, regulatory or administrative provision and who is to be responsible for enforcing those provisions on their territory.

Following the definition of a directive, it should not itself have direct effect. The regulatory effect of directives on individuals requires the action of the national authorities to implement their content into national law.

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DIRECTIVES

Under certain conditions, directives are not deprived of the possibility of directly providing rights in the legal sphere of individuals before national courts.

The direct effect of directives, when they have one, is limited. Private individuals may refer to a directive before their national courts only against their State where it has not implemented the directive addressed to it in a timely and correct manner.

In that sense, the direct effect of the directive is a kind of penalty for Member States which have not taken appropriate measures to comply with their obligations under the directive.

DIRECTIVES

At the same time, citizens can benefit from the rights they would have had if the Directive had been implemented in the national law in a timely manner.

Thus, direct effect becomes a mechanism through which citizens indirectly control the fulfilment of the obligations arising from the ETL.

The Court of Justice of the EU monitors the implementation of directives into national law and has developed a system of requirements for this process to ensure that Member States adequately fulfil such an obligation.

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DECISIONS

DECISIONS

These acts are individual and may be addressed to the Member State as well as to private individuals and legal entities.

By definition, they have direct effect for their addressee in that they are the source of rights and/or obligations which the national courts are required to protect.

Moreover, where they create proprietary obligations, those acts have executory effect in the territory of the Member State.

Decisions may give rise to rights not only for their direct addressee but also for third parties.

DECISIONS

RECOMMENDATIONS AND OPINIONS

RECOMMENDATIONS AND OPINIONS

Recommendations and opinions have no binding force.

This means that they do not create rights and obligations for their addressees and are not legal acts, much less sources of law

However, this does not mean that resorting to them should be underestimated.

They are a particularly suitable instrument in areas where the EU has no legislative competence or where the adoption of a legally binding act requires the expiry of a transition period.

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RECOMMENDATIONS AND OPINIONS

Recommendations are issued on the initiative of the institutions and are an invitation to their addressees to adopt a certain behavior. In these cases, they may have indirect legal effect.

Opinions are usually given by the Commission at the request of private entities or Member States.

They contain a general assessment of certain facts relevant to the behavior of the person concerned.

UNPROVIDED FOR IN THE TREATIES

The Council of the EU or the Commission often use:

- **Resolutions;**
- Positions;**
- Conclusions;**
- Declarations;**
- Communications;**
- Etc.**

They are not provided for in the contracts.

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

Topic 3: Requirements of the Construction Products Regulation

Module 1 “Fundamentals of European technical legislation and standardization”
Course “General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry”

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

- The new Regulation (EU) 2024/3110 sets out harmonized rules for the marketing of construction products and repeals Regulation (EU) No 305/2011.
- The new regulation is a part of the EU's efforts to ensure the safety, quality and sustainability of construction products.
- The new regulation updates the rules for construction products offered in the ESM.
- With Regulation (EU) 2024/3110, the European Union aims to address the weaknesses of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 by modernizing the regulatory framework and adapting it to the new requirements of sustainable development and digitalization.

**Construction
Products
Regulation**

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

IMPORTANT DEADLINES

Transitional periods and deadlines in the new Construction Products Regulation (EU) 2024/3110

- **Date of entry into force:**
 - The regulation enters into force on the 20th day following its publication in the Official Journal of the EU, which means January 8th, 2025.
- **Application of the provisions:**
 - The regulation applies from 8 January 2026, with the exception of specific articles that enter into force earlier.
 - Article 92 (related to sanctions) shall apply from 8 January 2027.
- **Transitional regulations for economic operators:**
 - The requirements and obligations for economic operators apply one year after the adoption of the implementing act making a harmonized standard mandatory.
- **Within one year after the date of application of the requirements for a specific product family, the Commission will withdraw the old harmonized standards and assessment documents.**
- **Repeal of the old regulation:**
 - Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 is repealed from 8 January 2026, with the exception of certain provisions which remain in force until 8 January 2040.

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

IMPORTANT DEADLINES

Articles that enter into force before 8 January 2027.

According to Article 96 of the Regulation, most provisions enter into force from 8 January 2026, with the exception of the following, which apply from 7 January 2025:

- Articles 1-4
- Article 5, paragraphs 1-7
- Article 7, paragraph 1
- Articles 9 and 10
- Article 12, paragraph 1, first subparagraph
- Article 16, paragraph 3
- Article 37, paragraph 4
- Articles 63, 89 and 90
- Annexes I, II, III, IV, VII, IX, and X

Article 92 (related to sanctions) will apply from 8 January 2027.

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

OBJECTIVES OF THE NEW REGULATION

To contribute to the effective functioning of the ESM by ensuring the free movement of safe and sustainable construction products in the EU.

To contribute to achieving the goals of green and digital transition by preventing and reducing the impact of construction products on the environment and on human health and safety.

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

SCOPE OF THE NEW REGULATION

It applies to construction products, including second-hand products, and to the following articles: key parts of products and parts or materials intended to be used for products covered by the regulation, if the manufacturer of those parts or materials requests this.

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

Regulation (EU) 2024/3110 introduces a new mechanism to accelerate the adoption of new harmonized standards:

The Commission is assisted by *the Expert Group on Legislation Related to the Construction Products Regulation* when considering requests from Member States for harmonization at the EU level through harmonized technical specifications.

The methods and criteria for assessing the performance of a product in relation to its essential characteristics are set out in harmonized standards, which become mandatory based on implementing acts.

The Commission may adopt implementing acts to define the essential characteristics, the methods for their assessment and the technical details for one or more product families or for one or more product categories within a family if the standardization process is delayed. The Commission may adopt implementing acts to define common specifications which provide other means of achieving compliance with the requirements for products.

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

The assessment and verification of the performance of a product in relation to its essential characteristics, as defined in the harmonized technical specifications or in the European Assessment Documents, or of its conformity with the product requirements, shall be carried out in accordance with one or more of the *assessment and verification systems*.

When a product is covered by a harmonized technical specification, the manufacturer undergoes the applicable assessment and verification system and draws up a declaration of performance and conformity before that product is placed on the market.

The declaration must contain the performance of the product throughout its life cycle. The different groups of characteristics start to apply from:

- January 8, 2026 – for the initial set of features.
- January 9, 2030 – for additional features.
- January 9, 2032 – for the remaining features.

REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

REQUIREMENTS for “CE” marking:

The general principles established in Regulation (EC) No. 765/2008 apply to the “CE” marking.

The “CE” marking is only applied to products for which the manufacturer has drawn up a declaration of performance and conformity. The “CE” marking is applied to key parts.

By affixing the “CE” marking, the economic operator indicates that they have taken responsibility for the conformity of the product with the declared performance and the applicable requirements for the product.

The “CE” marking is the only marking that certifies the performance of the product in relation to the assessed essential characteristics, as well as the conformity of the product.

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

The obligations of economic operators apply only to products that are covered by a harmonized technical specification or to products that are “CE” marked on the basis of a European Technical Assessment.

When a manufacturer places a product on the market, he defines the product type. The manufacturer ensures that the performance of the product is assessed in relation to the mandatory essential characteristics and the essential characteristics intended to be declared.

The natural or legal person who manufactures a product using 3D printing shall fulfil the obligations applicable to manufacturers when placing the product on the market.

The manufacturer prepares a declaration of performance and conformity and applies the “CE” marking.

As a basis for the declaration of performance and conformity, the manufacturer draws up technical documentation.

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

REQUIREMENTS/conditions for placing on the market

A manufacturer established in the EU may appoint, by written mandate, any natural or legal person established in the EU as its sole authorized representative. A manufacturer not established in the EU appoints only one authorized representative. The preparation of the technical documentation is not part of the authorized representative's mandate.

Importers place on the market only products which are in conformity with the Regulation. Before placing a product on the market, the importer ensures that the conformity of the product with the applicable requirements and its performance related to the relevant essential characteristics have been demonstrated by the manufacturer.

When making products available on the market, distributors act with due diligence regarding the obligations under the Regulation.

REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

Products offered *for sale online or through other means of distance selling* are considered to be made available on the market if the offer is targeted at customers in the EU.

The methods and criteria for assessing the performance of products, including used products, in relation to their essential characteristics may be laid down in *European assessment documents*, provided that the products are not covered by:

- a harmonized standard made mandatory by an implementing act;
- an implementing act;
- a harmonized standard that must be ready within less than one year, in accordance with the standardization request.

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

The European Technical Assessment is issued by Technical Assessment Bodies at the request of a manufacturer on the basis of a European Assessment Document, the details of which are published in the Official Journal of the EU.

Without prejudice to the obligations of economic operators under the Regulation and the activities of market surveillance authorities under Regulation (EU) 2019/1020, *the Commission establishes a system allowing any natural or legal person to submit complaints or alerts regarding alleged non-compliance with this Regulation.*

Member States designate one or more of their market surveillance authorities that have the specific knowledge required to assess products from both a technical and legal perspective

Member States designate a single liaison office to act as a central point of contact with the Commission and the *single liaison* offices of other Member States.

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

The Commission establishes and maintains *an information and communication system for collecting, processing and storing information in a structured form* on matters relating to the interpretation or application of the rules set out in or pursuant to the Regulation, with a view to ensuring the harmonized application of those rules.

Member States assist economic operators by means of Product *Contact* Points for Construction. Member States designate and maintain at least one Product Contact Point for Construction on their territory.

Product Contact Points for Construction must be able to carry out their functions in a way that helps to avoid conflicts of interest, in particular in relation to the procedures for obtaining the “CE” marking.

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

The digital product passport for a product includes:

- the declaration of performance and conformity;
- general product information, instructions for use and safety information;
- technical documentation;
- Environmental sustainability label;
- uniform identification codes;
- etc.

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

The digital product passport:

- is linked to one or more data carriers;
- is accessible electronically;
- corresponds to the type of product and its unique identification code;
- is accessible free of charge to all economic operators, customers, users and authorities;
- provides different levels of access to the system for digital passports of construction products;
- etc.

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

The Commission adopts delegated acts to complement the Regulation by setting mandatory minimum requirements for the *environmental sustainability of construction products*.

When minimum performance criteria for the environmental sustainability of construction products are defined in relation to their essential characteristics covered by harmonized technical specifications in the context of public procurement, contracting authorities and contracting entities apply the mandatory minimum requirements for environmental sustainability to the procurement procedures.

The EU Ecolabel and other national or regional EN ISO 14024 Type I ecolabel schemes that are officially recognized in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 66/2010 may be used to demonstrate compliance with the minimum requirements for environmental sustainability.

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REQUIREMENTS OF THE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS REGULATION

Regulation (EU) 2024/3110 represents a significant step forward in the harmonization of rules for construction products in the EU through digitalization, sustainability and better market surveillance. It will:

It is expected that after its full implementation, the construction sector will become more environmentally friendly, transparent and competitive.

Facilitate the access of new technology and innovation.

Strengthen safety and environmental requirements.

Prevent market fragmentation through more effective standardization mechanisms.

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

Topic 4: Basic concepts of standardization. Types of standards and standard deliverables, status and functions of standards

Module 1 “Fundamentals of European technical legislation and standardization”
Course “General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry”

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BASIC CONCEPTS OF STANDARDIZATION

Standardization objectives:

The goals of standardization change with its development and have an economic and social focus with a predominantly technical content.

The non-technical objectives of standardization raise the standard of living of people. They now include objectives for non-technical aspects such as safety, health and environmental protection.

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BASIC CONCEPTS OF STANDARDIZATION

International and European standardization organizations formulate its principles

Voluntariness. Voluntary initiation of the work on the development and issuance of standardization documents, as well as the voluntary application of standards are required.

- *A standard is created only when it will be applied.*

Transparency. During the development of standards, it is essential that they are publicly discussed. The publication of information about their development and the free access of the stakeholders to meetings where the standards will be discussed and/or adopted is a criterion for the presence of transparency.

Equality. In the development, discussion, adoption and text of standards no significant advantages should be given to:

- **Specific products or their manufacturer;**
- **A defined group of persons with common commercial interests;**
- **Products of the industry of one or a group of countries.**

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BASIC CONCEPTS OF STANDARDIZATION

Basic concepts

The concepts in standardization change with scientific and technological progress and the requirements of international trade.

To create a common terminology fund worldwide, ISO/IEC published Guide 2.

The basic terms of standardization are given in EN 45020:2006 Standardization and related activities - General vocabulary (ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004).

Standardization is an activity aimed at achieving optimal order in a certain area by establishing prescriptions for general and repeated application in solving existing or anticipated tasks. It includes the development, adoption and application of standards.

The results of standardization are:
increasing the degree of conformity of products to their functional purpose;
removing barriers to trade;
facilitating scientific and technical cooperation;
and others.

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BASIC CONCEPTS OF STANDARDIZATION

Object of standardization – matter for standardization.

- The term is encompassed by the expression “product, process or service” (hereinafter referred to simply as “product”). It equally includes any material, element, equipment, system, their compatibility, protocol, procedure, function, method or activity.
- Standardization can be limited to certain aspects of an object or to its entirety.

Standardization area - a set of interconnected standardization objects.

- Areas of standardization include mechanical engineering, transport, agriculture, quantities and units, and many others

Recognized technical level - a technical prescription that is recognized by the majority of competent specialists as corresponding to the state of the art.

- A standard for an object is a “recognized technical level” at the time of its approval if it has been developed through consultation and consensus-building procedures with stakeholders.

BASIC CONCEPTS OF STANDARDIZATION

Consensus - general agreement characterized by the absence of strongly held objections on essential issues from the majority of interested parties.

- Consensus is achieved through a procedure that takes into account the opinions of all parties and reconciles divergent points of view, but it is not complete unanimity.

Majority – consensus, voting and acceptance of the vote of the majority of those who voted, as follows:

- *Simple majority – over 1/2 of the votes (over 50%);*
- *By qualified majority – with the following variations:*
 - over 2/3 votes (over 67%);
 - over 3/4 votes (over 75%).

Level of standardization - a form of participation in standardization activities taking into account a geographical, political or economic characteristic:

- International standardization;
- Regional standardization;
- National standardization;
- Administrative-territorial standardization.

BASIC CONCEPTS OF STANDARDIZATION

Standardization objectives – they are aligned with the definition of standardization, and the objectives may encompass one or several specific goals to achieve:

diversity and usability management;	compatibility and interchangeability;	health protection, safety assurance;	environmental protection, product protection;	achieving mutual understanding;	improving economic indicators;	trade facilitation, etc.
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The realization of some goals can occur simultaneously with the realization of other goals.

The subject of standardization can be any object in the fields of: mechanical engineering, transport, construction, food, agriculture, forestry, medicine, textiles, chemistry, trade, science, education, etc.

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BASIC CONCEPTS OF STANDARDIZATION

Standard – a regulatory document available to the public:

- *it is developed and adopted by consensus;*
- *it expresses the interests of all stakeholders in the object;*
- *it is approved by a recognized (authorized) body;*
- *it is intended for repeated and/or general application;*
- *it meets the achievements of science, technology and practice, including prescriptions that are at a recognized technical level.*
- *the copyright holders of the standards are the organizations that developed them.*

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BASIC CONCEPTS OF STANDARDIZATION

Standards are classified according to various characteristics:

1/ According to the level of standardization:

- **International standard;**
- **Regional standard;**
- **National standard;**
- **Administrative-territorial standard.**

2/ Types of standards according to the current state of the standard:

- **Current standard - the deadline for the standard to enter into force has expired and the standard is in effect.**
- **Preliminary standardization document - is adopted temporarily by the standardization body and is known to the public for the purpose of its implementation in order to gain the necessary experience for its subsequent adoption as a valid standard. A characteristic of preliminary standardization documents is that they are developed for new or rapidly developing areas without existing standards. You can also cover products or processes with standard effects, if this is necessary to address specific or newly emerging requirements. Such standardized documents are TR, TS, CWA, IWA, etc.**
- **Draft standard - a document that is proposed by a standardization body for discussion, voting and approval.**

BASIC CONCEPTS OF STANDARDIZATION

3/ Types of standards according to the object of standardization:

- **Basic standard** - it is of general purpose or contains general provisions for a specific area of standardization, and can be a standard with direct application or serve as the basis for other standards.
- **Terminological standard** - establishes terms along with their definitions, including explanatory notes, illustrations, examples, etc.
- **Product standard** - defines the requirements for one or a group of products to be fit for their intended purpose.
 - In it, in addition to the requirements for suitability for purpose, there may be included terminology, testing methods, packaging and labeling, requirements for the production process, method of supply, etc.
 - The product standard may specify all or only part of the necessary requirements, with varying requirements for dimensions, materials, technical delivery rules, etc.

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BASIC CONCEPTS OF STANDARDIZATION

The European system for technical regulation and standardization is as follows:

European standards are mandatory for adoption by EU member states and voluntary for implementation.

The mandatory product requirements related to the regulated area of public interest are formulated in a mandatory technical regulatory act.

When, in order to comply with the technical legal norms of the act, it is necessary to perform actions defined in standards, these standards are indicated in the act - a reference is made from the technical regulatory act to the standard through its "reference (indication)".

In this way, without having the status of mandatory, the referenced standards, by complying with the technical regulatory act, receive mandatory application.

Since standardization in the EU is voluntary, anyone complying with the regulatory act has the right to apply other standards than those referred to in the act. In that case, they must prove that their application leads to the same end result and ensures compliance with the mandatory requirements of the act.

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STANDARDS IMPLEMENTATION

GENERAL PROVISIONS

The implementation of standards depend on the structure and organization of standardization activities in the country.

The implementation formulated by international standardization experts are examined.

The implementation of the standard are a relationship between the actual state of the object before the application of the standard and the results after its application.

STANDARDS FUNCTIONS

The standards perform the following functions:

- Energy (saving energy, resources, time, etc.);
- For establishing order;
- Mediation;
- On safety;
- On determining quality;
- Reducing;
- On exchange;
- On health;
- On supplies;
- Organizational;
- Informative;
- On knowledge transfer;
- etc.

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STANDARDS FUNCTIONS

Energy function

This function shows that the implementation of standards always leads to savings /profit/ of resources, funds, energy in a general sense, as evident from the examples:

Production processes:

the one that provides the most rational savings of resources for materials, technical means and capacities is standardized.

Products:

Concepts, characteristics, requirements, products are standardized, leading to profits from saving time and resources for calculations, from documentation, technologies, rapid readjustment to new market requirements, etc.

Creating standards:

Intellectual energy is expended only by the team developing the standard, and the profit from saving intellectual and material energy is achieved by all users of the standard.

STANDARDS FUNCTIONS

Function for establishing order

This function is based on the fact that the application of each new standard introduces a new order. The standard is created to require a new way of selecting, arranging, and linking product indicators.

Two directions are distinguished, through which a new order in activities arises:

Order - by clarifying and standardizing new relationships between objects.

Order - by typifying and standardizing new indicators of the objects themselves.

Research shows that the two functions of standards are interconnected - first, the function of establishing order is activated and as a consequence of the application of the standard, the specified energy savings in the general sense are achieved, i.e. profit for the company.

STANDARDS FUNCTIONS

Mediating function

Standardized are:

- **identifiers of bank codes, banknotes, contracts, forms, electronic means, etc.;**
- **symbols and activities in mathematics, physics, documentation, etc.;**
- **information and communication in society;**
- **relationships between specialists in different sectors of the economy;**
- **a unified terminological language in a specific sector, etc.**

STANDARDS FUNCTIONS

Safety function

It is implemented through the application of harmonized European standards with Directives and Regulations.

Here, the main areas of their safety function are generally highlighted, including:

- indicators for safe use of products for their intended purpose;
- methods for producing safe products;
- methods for verifying the safety indicators of products;
- ways of describing these indicators in the instructions for users, which may be dangerous when using the product for purposes other than its intended purpose.

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STANDARDS FUNCTIONS

Quality determination function

It is implemented through the application of standards to achieve "market" quality of products, whereby:

The characteristics of the product are standardized by one or a group of standards, which in their entirety determine its quality.

Departmental, industry and company standards include safety features as a mandatory part of quality indicators.

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

Topic 5: Mechanism for “conditional obligation” of standards

Module 1 “Fundamentals of European technical legislation and standardization”
Course “General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry”

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MECHANISM FOR “MANDATORY” STANDARDS

Reference in a technical regulatory act

The links in the European system between technical legislation and voluntary standardization are realized through the “referencing” of standards. This is one of the ways in which the “*conditional mandatory status*” of standards can be determined.

There are other ways, which are considered once the first of these - a reference to standard(s) in regulatory instrument(s) - is more fully clarified.

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MECHANISM FOR “MANDATORY” STANDARDS

Reference in a technical regulatory act

Two types of reference to standards are distinguished:

- static (dated)
reference

- dynamic (undated)
reference

MECHANISM FOR “MANDATORY” STANDARDS

When a standard is *statically referenced*, the version corresponding to the year of its entry into force shall be given in its designation. Each subsequent revision of the standard to create a new version must then change its designation in the normative act - revision of the act.

Static reference is used only when it is necessary to apply specific prescriptions related to a particular version of the standard in the act.

MECHANISM FOR “MANDATORY” STANDARDS

Dynamic reference – the designation of the standard does not specify a version - a specific year. This method of referencing requires that the version of the standard currently in force is used.

This way is more flexible, as the revision of the standard and the creation of a new version does not also require a revision of the regulatory act.

MECHANISM FOR “MANDATORY” STANDARDS

The advantages of the European approach of "mandatory" standards should be emphasized.

By referring to standards in regulatory acts, the legislator is freed to seek technical solutions and include them in the acts.

On the one hand, this is very convenient for lawyers who do not have the necessary technical qualifications on the specific subject of the reference. The legal text is free from complex technical and/or detailed descriptions, and defines only generalized /and ambiguous / legal norms.

On the other hand, the standard for a specific object is developed and adopted by specific technical specialists.

MECHANISM FOR “MANDATORY” STANDARDS

MECHANISM FOR “MANDATORY” STANDARDS

Market mechanism of conditional "obligation"

The hidden binding nature of standards, due to the market mechanism, arises from their “exchange” and “diminishing” function as well as their function for “quality”.

Every competitive manufacturer is "obliged" to comply with the standards, as they are a link in the market mechanism.

The following areas of influence arise:

- *Compatibility;*
- *Standardized /typified/ objects;*
- *Contracts between partners;*
- *Proof of quality.*

MECHANISM FOR “MANDATORY” STANDARDS

Compatibility

When they do not manufacture products that meet the standardized requirements for them, they will not be compatible with other products from other manufacturers available on the market.

For example If a paper manufacturer does not comply with the voluntary EN ISO 5457 standard for formats, the paper will not be usable for office equipment, printers, copiers, etc. In this case, the paper manufacturer loses the opportunity to sell in the required quantities and is excluded from the market. For this reason, manufacturers comply with EN ISO 5457.

MECHANISM FOR “MANDATORY” STANDARDS

Standardized /typified/ objects

Standards that define the characteristics of highly typified products used across all sectors of technology acquire the status of implicit obligation. Such are the standards for the most widely used elements like screws, bolts, nuts, washers, bearings, etc.

These elements are manufactured by specialized companies, where the standards with the requirements for the elements are strictly followed. Users of these elements are required to seek the appropriate characteristics as specified in the standards.

MECHANISM FOR “MANDATORY” STANDARDS

Contracts between partners

In industry, they mutually use strictly defined standards – they actually acquire the status of mandatory for the partners.

Proof of quality

Achieving product competitiveness in the Single European Market and in the World Trade Organization (WTO) market requires proving quality.

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MECHANISM FOR “MANDATORY” STANDARDS

To prove quality, the manufacturer produces its products in compliance with the requirements set out in the relevant standards:

- For offering in the Single European Market – European standards;
- For offering in the WTO – global standards.

The compliance with standards is proven by Conformity Assessment Bodies through the following activities:

- Testing;

MECHANISM FOR “MANDATORY” STANDARDS

In order to assess quality, each Authority must first be accredited according to a specific standard from the EN ISO/IEC 17000 series of global standards.

To perform Testing, Inspection or Certification, the Authority applies methods that are standardized.

When the Authority carries out the assessment, it uses the product standard to verify the conformity of its actual characteristics with the requirements specified in the standard.

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

Topic 6: Awareness of new products

Module 1 “Fundamentals of European technical legislation and standardization”
Course “General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry”

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

01

In the modern world, the development of construction technologies plays a key role in sustainable development and reducing the ecological footprint.

02

Low-carbon cement and bio-based insulation materials stand out among the latest innovations in the sector.

03

They offer environmentally friendly alternatives to traditional building materials, reducing carbon emissions and improving the comfort and energy efficiency of buildings.

04

As technology advances and public awareness increases, sustainable building solutions will become increasingly accessible and widely used.

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

ECOPlanet
The Green Cement

Low-carbon cement – the future of sustainable construction

Cement is one of the most widely used construction materials, but its production is associated with large amounts of carbon emissions.

Traditional Portland cement is responsible for approximately 8% of global CO₂ emissions.

In order to reduce this footprint, new, greener options are coming to market.

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

Main advantages of low-carbon cement:

Reduced emissions – using alternative raw materials and low-carbon technologies can reduce the carbon footprint by up to 50%.

Improved mechanical properties – some variants of this cement even increase the strength and durability of concrete.

Use of industrial waste – some low-carbon cements include additives such as fly ash, slag and clay, which reduce the need for clinker – the main component leading to high emissions.

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

Some examples of low carbon cement:

LC3 (Limestone Calcined Clay Cement) – uses a combination of limestone and calcined clay, which reduces CO₂ emissions by up to 40%.

Geopolymer Cement – combines industrial waste with special alkaline activators.

Carbon Cure Technology – introduces carbon dioxide into the concrete mix, converting it into minerals and improving the strength of the material.

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

Bio-based insulations – sustainable and effective solutions

Insulation is a key factor in the energy efficiency of buildings.

While traditional materials such as Styrofoam and mineral wool have high carbon emissions and are often difficult to recycle, new bio-based insulation materials offer a more environmentally friendly alternative.

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

Some bio-based insulation types:

Hemp insulation – made from hemp fibers, it offers high durability, good thermal and sound insulation, and a low ecological footprint.

Sheep wool insulation – a natural and breathable alternative that has excellent thermoregulatory properties.

Cellulose insulation – made from recycled paper and cardboard, treated against pests and fire.

Cork insulation – cork is a renewable resource that offers high moisture resistance and excellent thermal insulation qualities.

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

NORMATIVE REQUIREMENTS AND STANDARDS. LOW-CARBON CEMENT:

EN 197-5 - regulates the use of cements with a low clinker factor.

EN ISO 14067 - standard for assessing the carbon footprint of building materials.

Main technical characteristics:

Compressive strength – must meet the requirements for structural stability.

Resistance to moisture and chemicals – suitable for specific conditions such as industrial and marine environments.

Compatibility with traditional additives and reinforcements – to be used in existing construction processes.

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

**NORMATIVE
REQUIREMENTS AND
STANDARDS.
BIO-BASED INSULATIONS:**

EN 13171+A1 - standard for
thermal insulation materials
based on wood fibers.

EN ISO 14040 and EN ISO
14044 - standards for life
cycle analysis and ecological
footprint.

Regulation (EC) No.
1907/2006 (REACH) - ensures
that materials do not contain
harmful chemicals.

Main technical
characteristics:

Thermal conductivity
coefficient – comparable to
traditional materials.

Vapor permeability –
facilitates the natural
"breathing" of buildings.

Fire resistance – some bio-
based insulations are treated
with flame retardants to
meet fire safety
requirements.

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

Financial and regulatory support

European green building programs – investors of buildings designed with many of the new materials receive subsidies through programs such as Horizon Europe and Green Deal.

Tax relief and incentives – in some countries, reduced taxes or subsidies are offered for using low-carbon building materials.

Sustainability certificates – using these materials can help buildings obtain HQE, BREEAM or DGNB certification (HQE, BREEAM, DGNB - green building certification standards).

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

Although low-carbon cement and bio-based insulation still face some challenges such as costs and adaptation to existing building codes, they are a key part of the future of sustainable construction.

As stricter regulations come in and environmental awareness increases, these innovative materials will become more common and affordable.

AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

Standardization as a catalyst or obstacle to innovation in building materials

Standardization plays a critical role in construction, ensuring quality, safety, and compatibility between different materials and technologies.

When it comes to innovative building materials, such as low-carbon cement and bio-based insulation, the question arises: Do existing standards help the rapid implementation of these products or slow them down?

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

Some solutions to facilitate the adoption of low-carbon cements:

Proof projects – bridges and buildings that use these materials in real-world conditions.

Adaptation of existing standards – for example, EN 197-5 now includes calcined clay.

Public policies and incentives – subsidies for certified ecological materials.

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

How to make standards more flexible for innovation?

Balance between safety and innovation:
Flexible standards that are updated
more quickly with new scientific
evidence.

International examples of adaptive
standards: Germany and Switzerland
have standards that encourage bio-
insulations through additional financial
incentives.

Standardization through digitalization:
BIM (Building Information Modeling)
and standardization - how software
simulations can accelerate the
certification process; Using digital twins
to predict the durability of materials.

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AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

Despite the challenges associated with the delayed standardization of new construction products, the growing pressure for sustainable construction and innovation is leading to positive changes.

More and more institutions and industry organizations are working to accelerate certification processes, create new testing methodologies, and adapt building codes.

This trend opens the door for faster implementation of environmentally friendly materials, which will contribute to more sustainable and efficient construction in the future.

AWARENESS OF NEW PRODUCTS

The recent adoption of the new Construction Products Regulation is another step in the right direction.

The introduction of more flexible certification criteria and the promotion of innovative solutions will facilitate the integration of low carbon technologies.

Although the construction sector is gradually adapting to the new legislation, we are moving together towards a greener and environmentally balanced future.

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

Topic 1: Conformity assessment, concepts and criteria

Module 2 “Product responsibility and market surveillance”

Course “General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry”

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT

Conformity assessment is a process, a set of activities, through which it is assessed and proven whether the requirements and prescriptions for the characteristics of a product, as defined by a regulatory document, have been met.

Conformity assessment is:

Voluntary – when the document is a voluntary standard for application;

Mandatory – when the document is a regulatory act or a standard harmonized with a directive or regulation.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT

First party in market relations

- ***The supplier /Manufacturer/*** of a regulated product may wish to undergo both voluntary and mandatory conformity assessment. The first assesses compliance with the requirements for the product's competitiveness characteristics, and the second assesses safety for its intended purpose.

Second party

- ***The users.***

Third party in market relations on the European Single Market (ESM)

- ***Assessment body/Person*** that assesses the conformity of the product and must be independent from the first and second parties on the market. In order to assess conformity, the Assessment body must have competence that is recognized by the first and second parties on the market.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT

The requirements for the competence of the Conformity Assessment Body depend on the type of assessment - voluntary or mandatory.

For voluntary conformity assessment, it is imperative that the assessment body be *accredited*.

For mandatory conformity assessment, the assessment body, in addition to being accredited, is required to be *notified*.

Market surveillance is a specific type of conformity assessment carried out by specialized Authorities. It plays a huge role in the correct implementation of ETL regulations.

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CONCEPTS OF CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT

Requirements – legally established criteria that a given object must meet.

Object of evaluation – a product, service, process, system or person being evaluated.

Conformity assessment body – an independent organization that performs assessment (e.g. certifying and accrediting bodies).

CONCEPTS OF CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT

Accreditation – a set of actions through which the Body's compliance with the requirements of specific harmonized European standards is assessed and it is recognized as having general technical competence to carry out testing, control or certification activities.

Testing – determining the characteristics of a product or process through measurement, analysis, and other methods.

Certification – official confirmation by a third party that a product, process or service meets certain requirements.

Control – verification of a product, process, or system to establish conformity.

CONCEPTS OF CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT

Notification - a set of actions at national and European level, through which the Authority is assessed and recognized for its specialized technical competence to assess conformity with a directive or regulation.

Market surveillance - post-market conformity assessment of the product on ESM. Its purpose is to determine whether the mandatory assessment has been carried out once the regulated product is already on the market, and whether it continues to comply with the requirements of EU legislation.

CONCEPTS OF CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT

Regulated products - products that are regulated by mandatory requirements and safety standards set out in regulatory acts of the ETL. They have the right to free movement within the ESM.

ESM Regulated Area – covers products that are regulated by technical regulations constituting the ETL.

Unregulated /Free/ zone of the ESM- includes products that are not regulated by ETL acts, but are subject to voluntary standards.

CONCEPTS OF CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT

Product standard – a regulatory document that defines product quality characteristics and their recommended standards for compliance.

Harmonized standard - is a normative document that is a European standard, developed and adopted based on a standardization request from the European Commission to one of the three European standardization organizations (CEN, CENELEC or ETSI) in support of European legislation and policies.

- **The application of harmonized standards is voluntary, but it is the easiest way for manufacturers, other economic operators or conformity assessment bodies to demonstrate that products, services or processes comply with the relevant EU legislation. The explanation of the relationship between the harmonized standard and the essential requirements of the directives/regulations to which it applies is provided in Annex Z of each standard developed at the standardization request of the EC.**

Normative characteristic of a product – it is defined in a standard.

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CONCEPTS OF CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT

Normative support - includes the Bodies and processes for determining, adopting, introducing and implementing regulatory documents that contain the requirements and standards for products and activities related to competitiveness.

Certificate of Conformity for Voluntary Conformity Assessment – issued by a Product Certification Body.

Test report for voluntary conformity assessment - issued by a Testing Laboratory and contains only the test results, but not the conclusion.

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CONCEPTS OF CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT

Certificate of conformity for mandatory conformity assessment - issued by a notified body.

The "CE" marking – is mandatory only for products for which EU harmonized standard exist and for which this marking is required.

Declaration of Conformity - issued by the manufacturer of a regulated product or by its authorized representative.

Technical documentation of a regulated product - prepared by the manufacturer.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Conformity assessment criteria are parameters used to determine whether a given object meets the requirements. They include:

Technical criteria – compliance with international, European and national standards (ISO, EN, BDS, SR, DIN, etc.).

Legal criteria – compliance with laws and regulations.

Functional criteria – the ability of the product or service to perform its intended functions.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Safety – ensuring that the product or process does not pose any threat to health or the environment.

Quality – the level of performance according to certain quality standards.

Reliability and sustainability – the ability of a product or service to function without failure for a certain period.

Compatibility – ability to integrate with other systems and products.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

Topic 2: Documentation of conformity assessment. Principles of CE marking

Module 2: Product responsibility and market surveillance

Course "General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry"

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

General provisions

Decision 768/2008/EC is the basic act of the ETC, which sequentially describes 16 modules for assessing product safety conformity.

- Each module is designated by a capital Latin letter, with a number added to the letter in some modules:

A, A1, A2, B, C, C1, C2, D, D1, E, E1, F, F1, G, H, H1.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module A:

Internal production control is the conformity assessment procedure through which the manufacturer ensures and declares that the relevant products meet the legislative requirements. The manufacturer: prepares technical documentation that allows the conformity of the product with the applicable requirements to be assessed and includes the relevant risk analysis and evaluation; takes all necessary measures to ensure that the manufacturing process and its monitoring confirm the compliance of the manufactured products with the technical documentation and the legislative requirements; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity for the product.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module A1:

Internal production control with product testing supervision is the conformity assessment procedure through which the manufacturer ensures and declares that the relevant products meet the legislative requirements. The manufacturer: prepares technical documentation that allows the conformity of the product with the applicable requirements to be assessed and includes the relevant risk analysis and evaluation; takes all necessary measures to ensure that the manufacturing process and its monitoring confirm the compliance of the manufactured products with the technical documentation and the legislative requirements; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity for the product.

The accredited internal body or notified body: conducts one or more tests on each individual product, focusing on one or more specific aspects of the product, to verify conformity with the relevant legislative requirements.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module A2:

Internal production control with product testing supervision at random intervals is the conformity assessment procedure through which the manufacturer ensures and declares that the relevant products meet the legislative requirements. The manufacturer: prepares technical documentation that allows the conformity of the product with the applicable requirements to be assessed and includes the relevant risk analysis and evaluation; takes all necessary measures to ensure that the manufacturing process and its monitoring confirm the compliance of the manufactured products with the technical documentation and the legislative requirements; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity for the product.

The accredited internal body or notified body: conducts inspections at random intervals to verify the quality of the internal product checks, taking into account the technological complexity of the products and the quantity of production.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module B:

EC type-examination is that part of the conformity assessment procedure in which a notified body examines the technical design of the product and verifies and certifies that the technical design meets the legislative requirements.

The manufacturer provides the notified body with technical documentation, supporting evidence for the suitability of the design decision, specimen(s) representative of the planned production, in accordance with the requirements. The EC type-examination may be carried out in one of the following ways:

- examination of a specimen of the final product, representative of the planned production (type examination of the manufactured product);
- assessment of the suitability of the technical design of the product by examination of the technical documentation and supporting evidence with examination of specimens, representative of the planned production of one or more essential parts of the product (combination of type examination of the manufactured product and type design);
- assessment of the suitability of the technical design of the product by examination of the technical documentation and supporting evidence, without examination of a specimen (type examination of the type design).

The notified body issues an EC type-examination certificate to the manufacturer when the type meets the applicable legislative requirements.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module C:

Conformity with the type based on internal production control is that part of the conformity assessment procedure through which the manufacturer ensures and declares that the products are in conformity with the type as described in the EC type examination certificate and meet the legislative requirements.

The manufacturer: takes all necessary measures to ensure that the production process and its monitoring confirm the compliance of the manufactured products with the approved type and with the legislative requirements; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity for the product.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module C1:

Conformity with the type based on internal production control with product testing supervision is that part of the conformity assessment procedure through which the manufacturer ensures and declares that the products are in conformity with the type as described in the EC-type examination certificate and meet the legislative requirements.

The manufacturer: takes all necessary measures to ensure that the manufacturing process and its monitoring confirm the compliance of the manufactured products with the approved type and the legislative requirements; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity for the product.

The accredited internal body or notified body: conducts one or more tests on each individual product, focusing on one or more specific aspects of the product, to verify conformity with the relevant legislative requirements.

CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module C2:

Conformity with the type based on internal production control with product testing supervision at random intervals is that part of the conformity assessment procedure through which the manufacturer ensures and declares that the products are in conformity with the type as described in the EC-type examination certificate and meet the legislative requirements.

The manufacturer: takes all necessary measures to ensure that the manufacturing process and its monitoring confirm the compliance of the manufactured products with the approved type and the legislative requirements; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity for the product.

The accredited internal body or notified body: conducts inspections at random intervals to verify the quality of the internal product checks, taking into account the technological complexity of the products and the quantity of production.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module D:

Conformity with the type based on production quality assurance is that part of the conformity assessment procedure whereby the manufacturer ensures and declares that the products are in conformity with the type described in the EC-type examination certificate and meet the legislative requirements.

The manufacturer: The manufacturer: develops and implements an approved quality system for the production, control, and testing of the final product; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity for the product.

The notified body: evaluates the quality system to determine whether it ensures the conformity of the products with the type described in the EC-type examination certificate and with the legislative requirements; conducts surveillance of the approved quality system.

CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module D1:

Production quality assurance is the conformity assessment procedure whereby the manufacturer ensures and declares that the relevant products meet the legislative requirements.

The manufacturer: prepares technical documentation that allows the conformity of the product with the applicable requirements to be assessed and includes the relevant risk analysis and evaluation; develops and implements an approved quality system for the production, control and testing of the final product; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity for the product.

The notified body: evaluates the quality system to determine whether it ensures the conformity of the products with the legislative requirements; conducts surveillance of the approved quality system.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module E:

Conformity with the type based on product quality assurance is that part of the conformity assessment procedure through which the manufacturer ensures and declares that the products are in conformity with the type described in the EC-type examination certificate and meet the legislative requirements.

The manufacturer: develops and implements an approved quality system for final product inspection and testing; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity for the product.

The notified body evaluates the quality system to determine whether it ensures conformity of the products with the type described in the EC-type examination certificate and with the legislative requirements; conducts surveillance of the approved quality system.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module E1:

Quality assurance of final product inspection and testing is the conformity assessment procedure through which the manufacturer ensures and declares that the relevant products meet the legislative requirements.

The manufacturer: prepares technical documentation that allows the conformity of the product with the applicable requirements to be assessed and includes the relevant risk analysis and evaluation; develops and implements an approved quality system for the production, control and testing of the final product; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity for the product.

The notified body: evaluates the quality system to determine whether it ensures the conformity of the products with the legislative requirements; conducts surveillance of the approved quality system.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module F:

Conformity with type based on product verification is that part of the conformity assessment procedure through which the manufacturer ensures and declares that the products are in conformity with the type described in the EC type-examination certificate and meet the legislative requirements. The manufacturer: takes all necessary measures to ensure that the manufacturing process and its monitoring confirm the compliance of the manufactured products with the approved type and the legislative requirements; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity for the product.

The notified body: conducts suitable examinations and tests to check the conformity of the products with the approved type and with the legislative requirements; issues a certificate of conformity in respect of the examinations and tests conducted on the product. The examinations and tests to check the conformity of the products with the requirements are carried out, at the choice of the manufacturer, either by examination and testing of every product or by examination and testing of the products on a statistical basis. In the latter case, the manufacturer takes all the necessary measures to ensure that the manufacturing process and its monitoring guarantee the uniformity of each manufactured batch and presents the products for inspection in the form of uniform batches.

CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module F1:

Conformity based on product verification is the conformity assessment procedure through which the manufacturer ensures and declares that the relevant products meet the legislative requirements.

The manufacturer: prepares technical documentation that allows the conformity of the product with the applicable requirements to be assessed and includes the relevant risk analysis and evaluation; takes all necessary measures to ensure that the manufacturing process and its monitoring confirm the compliance of the manufactured products with the legislative requirements; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity of the product.

The notified body: conducts appropriate examinations and tests to check the conformity of the products with the legislative requirements; issues a certificate of conformity in respect of the examinations and tests carried out on the product. The examinations and tests to check the conformity of the products with the requirements are carried out, at the choice of the manufacturer, either by examination and testing of each product or by examination and testing of the products on a statistical basis. In the latter case, the manufacturer takes all the necessary measures to ensure that the manufacturing process and its monitoring guarantee the uniformity of each manufactured batch and presents the products for verification in the form of uniform batches.

CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module G:

Conformity based on single product inspection is the conformity assessment procedure whereby the manufacturer ensures and declares that the relevant products meet the legislative requirements.

The manufacturer: prepares technical documentation that allows the conformity of the product with the applicable requirements to be assessed and includes the relevant risk analysis and evaluation and provides it to the notified body; takes all necessary measures to ensure that the manufacturing process and its monitoring guarantee the conformity of the manufactured products with the legislative requirements; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity of the product.

The notified body: conducts appropriate examinations and tests to check the conformity of the product with the legislative requirements; issues a certificate of conformity in respect of the examinations and tests carried out on the product.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module H:

Conformity based on full quality assurance is the conformity assessment procedure whereby the manufacturer ensures and declares that the relevant products meet the legislative requirements.

The manufacturer: develops and implements an approved quality system for the design, manufacture and control and testing of the final product; applies the required conformity marking and prepares a written declaration of conformity for the product.

The notified body: evaluates the quality system to determine whether it ensures the conformity of the products with the legislative requirements; conducts surveillance of the approved quality system.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Module H1:

Conformity based on full quality assurance with design examination is the conformity assessment procedure whereby the manufacturer ensures and declares that the relevant products meet the legislative requirements.

The manufacturer: develops and implements an approved quality system for design, manufacture and control and testing of the final product; applies the required conformity marking and draws up a written declaration of conformity of the product.

The notified body: evaluates the quality system to determine whether it ensures the conformity of the products with the legislative requirements; examines the design of the products and issues an EC design examination certificate; conducts surveillance of the approved quality system.

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CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT MODULES AND PROCEDURES

Conditions for the establishment of Modular procedures

“Modular procedure” refers to the set of modules and the specific ways of performing tasks within each module, which are used to evaluate the elements in the lifecycle of the regulated product.

A, A1, A2, G and H are independent complete Modular procedures;

For the 16 modules, the following specifications can be made:

D1, E1 and F1 are applied independently but are not complete Modular procedures;

Module B, combined with modules C, C1, C2, D, E, F and H1, form a complete Modular procedure.

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PRINCIPLES OF “CE” MARKING

CE marking, European regulations

The CE marking, indicating the conformity of the product with the legislative safety requirements, is the visible sign of the entire conformity assessment process in the broadest sense.

Regulation 765/2008/EC sets out the basic principles for the CE marking, which will be immediately applicable and thus simplify future legislation.

The CE marking should be the only marking indicating that the product complies with EU harmonization legislation.

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PRINCIPLES OF “CE” MARKING

“CE” marking, European regulations

- Other markings may be used if they enhance consumer protection and are not covered by EU harmonization legislation.
- Through the "CE" mark, the manufacturer indicates that the product complies with the requirements of EU harmonization legislation, which mandates its application.

PRINCIPLES OF "CE" MARKING

The principles are defined:

The "CE" marking is applied only by the manufacturer or their authorized representative.

The CE marking, whose shape is shown in the figure, may only be applied to products for which there is a provision in EU harmonization legislation. It cannot be applied to other products.

By applying the "CE" marking, the manufacturer demonstrates that they take responsibility for the compliance of their product with all the requirements specified in the relevant EU harmonization legislation.

The "CE" mark is the only confirmation of the product's compliance with the requirements of certain acts of EU harmonization legislation.

PRINCIPLES OF “CE” MARKING

The principles are defined:

The applying of markings, signs or inscriptions that could mislead third parties regarding the meaning or form of the „CE“ marking is prohibited. Other markings may be applied as long as they do not affect the visibility, legibility and meaning of the ‘CE’ marking.

Member states monitor the proper application of the "CE" mark and take appropriate actions in case of improper use.

Member States provide for sanctions for violations of the regime governing the CE marking, including criminal penalties for serious infringements. The sanctions must be proportionate to the severity of the violation and serve as an effective deterrent against improper use of the CE marking.

PRINCIPLES OF “CE” MARKING

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PRINCIPLES OF “CE” MARKING

Decision 768/2008/EC establishes the rules for the applying of the „CE“ marking, which must be applied in EU harmonization legislation providing for the use of this marking.

By applying the "CE" marking to the product, the manufacturer declares that the product complies with all requirements and that they take the responsibility for this.

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PRINCIPLES OF “CE” MARKING

Rules and conditions for applying the „CE“ marking:

The "CE" marking is applied directly on the product itself or its data plate in a way that ensures it is visible, legible and indelible. When this is not possible or cannot be guaranteed due to the nature of the product, it is applied to the packaging and accompanying documents, where legislation requires such documents.

The “CE” marking is applied before the product is placed on the market. It may be followed by a pictogram or other symbol indicating a special risk or use.

The identification number of the notified body shall be added to the „CE“ marking when it is involved in the internal /production/ control phase. The identification number must be applied by the body itself or, under its instructions, by the manufacturer or their authorized representative.

Member States should further develop existing mechanisms, to ensure the proper application of the regime governing the „CE“ marking, through appropriate actions and sanctions for violations in accordance with the provisions of *Regulation 765/2008/EC*.

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

Topic 3: Products for CE marking

Module 2 “Product responsibility and market surveillance”

Course “General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry”

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PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

Products for CE marking are all products intended for the ESM that fall within the scope of EU harmonization legislation providing for the applying of the CE marking.

These products can be manufactured both in member states and in third countries (outside the EU).

Therefore, the CE marking does not indicate that a product is manufactured in the EU.

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PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

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PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

Products for CE marking are intended for placing (or putting into operation) in the ESM.

Such products are typically ready for use or require only adjustment that can be done with regard to their intended use.

Products for CE marking intended for the ESM must comply with the applicable legislation in all forms of delivery, including remote sales and sales through electronic means.

PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

When a product is subject to several acts of EU harmonization legislation requiring the CE marking, its application by default indicates the product's conformity with the provisions of all acts.

During the transitional period of an EU harmonization act, the manufacturer may choose whether to comply with the requirements of the act or the relevant national provisions.

The choice made and the scope of conformity expressed by the CE marking must be clarified by the manufacturer in the EU Declaration of conformity and in documents, records or instructions accompanying the product.

PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

The CE marking is a key indicator (but not proof) of a product's compliance with EU harmonization legislation and enables the free movement of products within the ESM.

The CE marking indicates conformity with the requirements set out in the texts of directives or regulations of EU harmonization legislation.

The CE marking should be considered essential information for Member State authorities.

PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

The CE mark is a visible consequence of a comprehensive process, including conformity assessment, and indicates that the product has been declared by the manufacturer as compliant with EU harmonization legislation.

The CE mark should typically be applied at the end of the production phase, during the internal control stage.

This is not an issue when the CE mark is applied to the data plate, which is not affixed to the product until it passes the final assessment.

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PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

When the CE mark is an integral part of the product or its component, for example, through stamping or casting, it can be applied at any other stage of the production phase, provided that conformity is confirmed during the manufacturing process.

If the product was not manufactured for the EU (i.e., the manufacturer has not assessed conformity), the importer can carry out the conformity assessment and apply the CE mark.

If the importer places the product on the market under their own name, they assume the responsibilities of the manufacturer and must apply the CE marking themselves.

PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

To ensure legibility, the minimum height of the CE marking is required to be 5 mm. It must be indelible, i.e. it cannot be erased under normal circumstances without leaving visible traces.

It is important to note that some product standards require testing for cleaning (wiping) of finished product specimens with water and gasoline vapors.

In such cases, it must be ensured that the material used for the CE marking is resistant to the effects of cleaning agents and environmental influences.

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PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

The identification number of the notified body is added to the CE marking only if it assesses the production phase. Therefore, the identification number of the notified body that carried out the conformity assessment under Module B is not applied after the CE marking.

In these cases, several identification numbers are placed after the CE marking.

This is possible when several acts of EU harmonization legislation are applied simultaneously.

Sometimes several Notified Bodies assess the product in the production phase.

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PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

The size of each of the two symbols of the CE marking is determined by the diameter of the circle in which these symbols are inscribed.

Its diameter cannot be less than 5 mm.

There are no specific regulations regarding the values by which the sizes /diameters/ of the signs can increase.

Their size is assumed to correspond to the standardized series of font heights in the drawings:

diameter 5, 7, 10, 14, 20, 28 mm, etc.

Each subsequent value in this series is twice the previous number.

PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

To determine the dimensions of the elements of the CE marking, it is placed in a grid.

The diameter of each character in the grid is divided into 20 horizontal and vertical lines.

Accordingly, the specific dimensions of the elements of the symbol are a function of twentieths of the diameter.

The two circles of the signs intersect at a common part equal to $\frac{3}{20}$ of the diameter.

With these data, the total length of the CE marking is $\frac{37}{20}$ of the diameter.

PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

The line thickness of each symbol and its elements is $\frac{3}{20}$ of the diameter.

The length of each symbol is $\frac{11}{20}$ of the diameter, i.e. they are longer than half the circle.

A flat section is noticeable at the upper ends of the signs, which is $\frac{2}{20}$ of the diameter in length.

The middle protrusion of the second character in the CE marking is $\frac{9}{20}$ of the diameter long, i.e. $\frac{1}{20}$ smaller than its radius.

PRODUCTS FOR CE MARKING

The "CE" marking has no expiration date.

However, the EU declaration of conformity required for the CE marking must be updated regularly.

If any of the elements of the declaration of conformity is changed, its version must be updated.

The changes may be related, for example, to amendments in legislation, changes to the product or updates to the manufacturer's or authorized representative's contact details.

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

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Topic 4: Declaration of performance and Technical documentation

Module 2 “Product responsibility and market surveillance”

Course “General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry”

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EC DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY AND TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

„EC declaration of conformity” of products

- *Decision No 768/2008/EU specifies the requirements, nature and content of the 'EC declaration of conformity'.*
- European harmonisation legislation requires the manufacturer to declare that the requirements have been met and that the conformity of his product with those requirements has been demonstrated.
- The manufacturer prepares and issues an 'EC declaration of conformity'.
- It is the only declaration of conformity of the product with all relevant ETL acts.

CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT

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EC DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY AND TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

The EC declaration of conformity must contain all the information required by the European harmonisation legislation, including the relevant acts.

The suppliers of the product in the Single European Market keep a copy of it at the disposal of the market surveillance authorities. Shelf life takes into account the life cycle of the product and the degree of risk associated with its use. Suppliers make sure that the EC declaration of conformity is provided to the authorities upon request.

The EC declaration of conformity is made in accordance with the model set out in Decision 768/2008/EC. It contains the elements defined in the relevant modules and is updated regularly. It shall be translated into the language required by the Member State on whose market the product is launched.

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EC DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY AND TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

By preparing and issuing the EC declaration of conformity, the manufacturer takes responsibility for the conformity of the product and draws it up as follows:

1) № xxxxxx - the unique identification data of the product.

2) Name and address of the Manufacturer/or its Authorized Representative.

3) This declaration of conformity is issued under the responsibility of the Manufacturer (the person who installs).

4) Subject matter of the declaration - product identification, necessary for its tracking, may also include a photo.

EC DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY AND TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

5) The subject matter of the declaration described above corresponds to the relevant act of the European harmonisation legislation.

6) References are made to the harmonised standards or specifications used in respect of which conformity was declared.

7) When a notified body is involved – the data: ...(name, number)... performed ... (description of what was performed)... and issued the certificate:

8) Additional information: Signed for and on behalf of: ... (place and date of issue) (name, position, signature).

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EC DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY AND TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

Technical documentation of a regulated product

Decision 768/2008/EC requires the manufacturer, in addition to the EC declaration of conformity, to prepare the so-called technical documentation. It contains the documents that prove the accuracy of the issued declaration.

This summarises the content of the technical documentation required by the different conformity assessment modules.

The technical documentation refers to only one product of the company, which is regulated by an act of European harmonisation legislation.

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EC DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY AND TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

Only some of the modules require the implementation of Technical Documentation for a regulated product. The modules that are based on a quality management system (QMS), in addition to Technical Documentation for a specific product, also require the technical documentation of the QMS.

The QMS documentation refers to all products of the company, most of which may not be regulated by an act of the ETL. The QMS technical documentation is independent and does not act as Technical Documentation.

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EC DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY AND TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

The general requirements for the role and content of the technical documentation shall be formulated using the description of the modules in Decision 768/2008/EU.

Role of the Technical documentation:

- **the technical documentation of a regulated product is issued by the Manufacturer;**
- **its content must provide the conditions for assessing the conformity of the product with the applicable requirements;**
- **should include the relevant analysis and risk/s assessment;**
- **the technical documentation must clearly and accurately define the applicable requirements and describe them in as much detail as is necessary for the purposes of evaluating the design, manufacture and action of the product**

EC DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY AND TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

The technical documentation shall contain at least the following elements:

- a general description of the product;
- construction and manufacturing drawings and schemes of components, assembled units, electrical circuits, etc;
- the descriptions and explanations necessary for the understanding of these drawings and schemes and for the operation of the product;
- a list of harmonised standards and/or other technical specifications, the details of which are published in the Official Journal of the EU, which may be applied in full or in part;

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EC DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY AND TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

- descriptions of the decisions taken to meet the essential requirements of the ETL Act where harmonised standards have not been applied;
- in the case of partial application of harmonised standards, the parts of them which have been applied should be indicated;
- results of the project calculations that have been carried out;
- the tests carried out on specimens of the product;
- test reports, etc.

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

Topic 5: Product Liability and Consumer Protection

Module 2 “Product responsibility and market surveillance”

Course “General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry”

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PRODUCT LIABILITY

Product liability provisions

“The responsibility for the product” was established as a key factor shaping the manufacturer's "market" image in society.

There is evidence that the first product liability law was promulgated in Germany in 1872.

In 1985, the governing bodies of the European Community adopted the second horizontal Directive 85/374/EEC "On liability for damages caused by defective products...".

It was amended by the adoption of Directive 1999/34/EC.

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PRODUCT LIABILITY

Product liability provisions

The most essential principles and provisions are:

The Directive harmonizes the legislation of the Member States in the field of product liability, without undermining free competition, while ensuring an equal level of consumer protection against damages caused by defective goods.

All products manufactured or imported into the EEA, when they cause harm to a person or their property, fall within the scope of the Directive.
These are the products regulated by acts of the Sectoral Technical Legislation, although they are marked “CE” and are a subject to market surveillance.

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PRODUCT LIABILITY

**The Directive provides for a strict liability regime for manufacturers and importers in the ESM.
It requires a fair distribution of responsibility with the injured party if they were at fault he has made a mistake in using the product.**

**The directive only applies to products that are not safe for the intended purpose.
It allows for the avoidance of the so-called “development risk” - when new, more advanced models of the product are introduced, they cannot make outdated models into defective goods.**

PRODUCT LIABILITY

The responsibility to compensate for damages is taken on by the manufacturer or any supplier of the final product in the ESM if the manufacturer cannot be identified within a certain period.

If several entities in the production and supply chain are at fault for the product defect, they are jointly and individually liable.

PRODUCT LIABILITY

The directive provides that the manufacturer must compensate for the damage caused by the defective product up to a certain amount.

Does not compensate for a destroyed product.

It also does not cover moral damages, which should be subject to national legislation.

A limit should be set on the manufacturer's overall liability for death or bodily injury, ensuring it is sufficiently high to provide a comparable level of consumer protection in the ESM.

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PRODUCT LIABILITY

The manufacturer is not directly declared guilty and liable for the damages caused by their product.

The buyer or consumer of this product may obtain compensation through legal action.

The legal claim must be filed within three years after the damage, defect, and manufacturer of the product have become known.

PRODUCT LIABILITY

Compensation is granted only when it is proven in court that the damage was caused by a defective product.

In the case of proven liability, no waiver of responsibility towards the injured party can be agreed upon. If such clauses exist in contracts between the manufacturer and the consumer, they should be considered null and void in all Member States.

When the victim has contributed (due to negligence or other reasons) to the damage, the manufacturer's liability is reduced or even rejected.

Proving the manufacturer's negligence is irrelevant - the Directive is based on their liability for product manufacturing free from individual faults. This means that the manufacturer will not be excused for a defective product when he proves that he was not negligent, or that the omissions of another person were to blame, or that he correctly applied the necessary standards, carried out the required tests, etc.

PRODUCT LIABILITY

The manufacturer is not considered liable when they prove that:

the product was not placed on the market by them /e.g. it was stolen/;

the product was not defective when it was placed on the market (e.g. the defect appeared years later);

the defect is caused by the use of legislative acts that are not harmonized with the ETL;

when the product was placed on the market, the level of knowledge was not sufficient to detect its defect.

The manufacturer's liability lasts for ten years after a specific product has been placed on the market, unless there are pending cases. This period is consistent with the wear and tear of the product, as well as the idea that public perceptions and safety standards change over time.

PRODUCT LIABILITY

When placing a product on the market, every importer must indicate their name and the contact address on the product. Exceptions should be made in cases where the size or nature of the product does not allow this. In such cases, the importer must open the packaging to apply their name and address on the product.

Any supplier who places a product on the market under their name or trademark, or modifies the product in a way that may affect its compliance with applicable requirements, should be considered the manufacturer of the respective product and take on the manufacturer's responsibility for the product.

PRODUCT LIABILITY

Directive (EU) 2024/2853 on liability for damage caused by defective products and repealing Council Directive 85/374/EEC was adopted to improve the proper functioning of the internal market and to ensure that competition is not distorted and that the movement of goods is not hindered. It will lead to a higher level of protection of the health or property of consumers and other individuals.

Directive (EU) 2024/2853 applies to products placed on the market or put into service after 9 December 2026. For this reason, its provisions are not discussed here.

REGULATION (EU) 2023/988 - GENERAL PROVISIONS

Regulation (EU) 2023/988 on the general product safety establishes basic rules for the safety of consumer products placed on or made available on the market.

The aim of the regulation is to improve the functioning of the ESM while ensuring a high level of consumer protection.

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REGULATION (EU) 2023/988 - GENERAL PROVISIONS

It applies to products placed on or made available on the market, insofar as there are no specific provisions with the same objective under EU law that govern the safety of the respective products.

When products are subject to specific safety requirements imposed by EU law, this Regulation applies only to the aspects and risks or categories of risks not covered by those requirements.

REGULATION (EU) 2023/988 - GENERAL PROVISIONS

Regulation (EU) 2023/988 applies to products placed on or made available on the market, regardless of whether they are new, used, repaired or refurbished.

It does not apply to products that need to be repaired or refurbished before use, when these products are placed on or made available on the market and are clearly marked as such.

The Regulation does not affect consumer protection rules established by EU law.

It is applied taking into account the precautionary principle.

Products offered for sale online or through other means of distance selling are considered to be made available on the market if the offer is targeted at consumers in the EU.

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REGULATION (EU) 2023/988 - GENERAL PROVISIONS

Economic operators shall place or make available only safe products on the market.

For the purposes of the Regulation, a product is considered to comply with the general safety requirement in the following cases:

- if it meets the relevant European product safety standards or parts of them, insofar as they address the risks and categories of risks covered by these standards, the data for which has been published in the Official Journal of the EU in accordance with Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012;

- in the absence of relevant European standards, the product complies with national requirements concerning the risks and categories of risks covered by health and safety requirements established in the national law of the Member State where it is made available on the market, provided that this law is in accordance with EU law.

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REGULATION (EU) 2023/988 - GENERAL PROVISIONS

The Commission adopts implementing acts that set out the specific safety requirements to be covered by European standards in order to ensure that products complying with these European standards meet the general safety requirement.

When placing their products on the market, manufacturers guarantee that these products are designed and manufactured in accordance with the general safety requirement.

Before placing their products on the market, manufacturers conduct an internal risk assessment and prepare technical documentation containing at least a general description of the product and its essential characteristics relevant for assessing its safety.

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REGULATION (EU) 2023/988 - OBLIGATIONS OF ECONOMIC OPERATORS

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REGULATION (EU) 2023/988 - OBLIGATIONS OF ECONOMIC OPERATORS

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Before placing a product on the market, distributors make sure that the manufacturer and the importer have met the requirements.

Distributors ensure that, while they are responsible for a product, the storage or transportation conditions do not compromise its compliance with the general safety requirement and its conformity.

When a distributor believes that a product does not comply, the distributor does not make the product available on the market unless it is brought into compliance.

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REGULATION (EU) 2023/988 - OBLIGATIONS OF ECONOMIC OPERATORS

Economic operators cooperate with market surveillance authorities in actions that can eliminate or limit the risks posed by the products they have placed on the market.

At the request of a market surveillance authority, the economic operator shall provide all necessary information:

- a full description of the risk posed by the product, the complaints and known incidents related to it;
- a description of the corrective measures taken to eliminate the risk.

REGULATION (EU) 2023/988 - OBLIGATIONS OF ECONOMIC OPERATORS IN DISTANCE SELLING

When economic operators make products available on the market online or through other means of distance selling, the offer for those products contains:

- **the name, registered trade name or registered trademark of the manufacturer, as well as the postal and electronic address at which they can be contacted;**
- **when the manufacturer is not established in the EU - the name, postal and electronic address of the person responsible for the products placed on the EU market;**
- **information allowing identification of the product, including its image, its type and any other identifier of the product;**
- **any safety warnings or information that are placed on the product or its packaging, or included in an accompanying document.**

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Regulation (EU) 2023/988 - OBLIGATIONS OF ECONOMIC OPERATORS IN THE EVENT OF AN INCIDENT

The manufacturer ensures that, through the Safety Business Gateway, a notification of an incident caused by a product placed on or made available on the market is submitted without unnecessary delay to the competent authorities of the Member State where the incident occurred, from the moment they become aware of the incident.

Importers and distributors who have learned of an incident caused by a product they have placed or made available on the market inform the manufacturer about it without unnecessary delay.

When the manufacturer of the product is not identified in the EU, the responsible entity for the products placed on the market which is aware of the incident ensures that the notification is made.

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SAFETY GATE RAPID ALERT SYSTEM

SAFETY GATE RAPID ALERT SYSTEM

The Commission shall further develop, update and maintain the rapid alert system for exchanging information regarding corrective measures related to dangerous products (the Safety Gate rapid alert system) as well as improving its efficiency.

The Commission and the Member States have access to the Safety Gate rapid alert system. For this purpose, each Member State appoints a central contact authority.

Member States notify the corrective measures taken by their authorities or economic operators in the Safety Gate rapid alert system.

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SAFETY GATE RAPID ALERT SYSTEM

Member States may also notify the planned corrective actions related to products posing a serious risk through the Safety Gate rapid alert system if they consider it necessary due to the urgency concerning the risk to the health or safety of consumers.

Member States inform the Commission of the corrective measures taken by their authorities or economic operators on the basis of this Regulation and the Commission forwards this information to the other Member States.

SAFETY GATE RAPID ALERT SYSTEM

National authorities submit notifications through the Safety Gate rapid alert system without delay and in all cases within four working days after the corrective measures have been taken.

Within four working days of receiving the complete notification, the Commission checks whether it is compliant, and if it is in compliance, the Commission forwards it to the other Member States.

Member States notify without unnecessary delay through the Safety Gate rapid alert system for any updates, changes or withdrawals of corrective measures.

SAFETY GATE RAPID ALERT SYSTEM

When a Member State notifies corrective measures taken in relation to products posing a serious risk, the other Member States notify through the Safety Gate rapid alert system about any subsequent corrective measures or actions taken regarding the same products without unnecessary delay and no later than four working days after the adoption of the measures or actions.

If the Commission identifies, including based on information received from consumers or consumer organizations, products which are likely to present a serious risk and for which Member States have not submitted a notification through the Safety Gate, it informs the Member States about this. Member States carry out the appropriate checks and, if they adopt measures, they notify them through the Safety Gate.

The Commission establishes the interface between the information and communication system and Safety Gate to enable the initiation of a draft notification in Safety Gate from this information and communication system, in order to avoid duplicate data entry.

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SAFETY GATE RAPID ALERT SYSTEM

The Commission adopts delegated acts to supplement this Regulation by determining:

- access to the Safety Gate rapid alert system;
- the functioning of the Safety Gate rapid alert system;
- the information to be entered into the Safety Gate rapid alert system;
- the requirements to be met by notifications;
- the criteria for assessing the level of risk.

SAFETY GATE RAPID ALERT SYSTEM

SAFETY BUSINESS GATEWAY RAPID ALERT SYSTEM

- **The Commission maintains a web portal that allows economic operators and online marketplace providers to easily provide information to market surveillance authorities and consumers ("Safety Business Gateway").**
- **The Commission prepares guidelines for the practical use of Safety Business Gateway.**

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

Topic 6: European market surveillance legislation

Module 2 “Product responsibility and market surveillance”

Course “General information and process of standardization, standards as a tool for market placement of products and innovative solutions in the construction industry”

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MARKET SURVEILLANCE REGULATION

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - GENERAL PROVISIONS

The purpose of Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 is to improve the functioning of the EEA by strengthening market surveillance of products covered by EU harmonization legislation. It ensures that only compliant products, meeting requirements that provide a high level of protection for public interests, are made available in the EEA.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - GENERAL PROVISIONS

The Regulation applies to products insofar as there are no specific provisions with the same purpose in EU harmonization legislation that address specific aspects of market surveillance and enforcement in a more detailed manner.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - TASKS OF ECONOMIC OPERATORS

Products that are subject to certain acts of EU harmonization legislation (construction products, personal protective equipment, simple pressure vessels, measuring instruments, etc.) can only be placed on the market if there is an economic operator established in the EU. This can be:

manufacturer established in the EU;

**importer,
when the manufacturer is not established in the EU;**

an authorized representative who has received a written power of attorney from the manufacturer to act on their behalf;

a service provider for order processing established in the EU, with regard to the products for which it processes orders, when no other economic operator from the aforementioned categories is established in the EU.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - TASKS OF ECONOMIC OPERATORS

Tasks that this economic operator performs in relation to these products:

- **verifies that the EU declaration of conformity or the declaration of performance and the technical documentation have been drawn up, keeps the declaration of conformity or the declaration of performance and ensures that the technical documentation can be made available upon request;**
- **provides the market surveillance authority with all the information and documentation necessary to demonstrate the product's compliance, upon justified request.**
- **informs the market surveillance authorities when a product presents a risk;**
- **cooperates with the market surveillance authorities.**

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - ORGANISATION, ACTIVITIES AND DUTIES OF THE MARKET SURVEILLANCE AUTHORITIES AND OF THE SINGLE LIAISON OFFICE

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - ORGANISATION, ACTIVITIES AND DUTIES OF THE MARKET SURVEILLANCE AUTHORITIES AND OF THE SINGLE LIAISON OFFICE

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - ORGANISATION, ACTIVITIES AND DUTIES OF THE MARKET SURVEILLANCE AUTHORITIES AND OF THE SINGLE LIAISON OFFICE

Market surveillance authorities conduct
guarantee their activities to guarantee:

effective market surveillance within their
territory;

the taking of appropriate and proportionate
corrective actions by economic operators;

taking appropriate and proportionate
measures when the economic operator fails
to take corrective action.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - ORGANISATION, ACTIVITIES AND DUTIES OF THE MARKET SURVEILLANCE AUTHORITIES AND OF THE SINGLE LIAISON OFFICE

Market surveillance authorities exercise their powers and perform their functions independently, impartially and without bias.

Market surveillance authorities conduct appropriate checks on the characteristics of products on a suitable scale through document inspections and, where appropriate, physical and laboratory tests based on suitable samples, organizing their resources and activities according to priorities to ensure effective market surveillance.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - ORGANISATION, ACTIVITIES AND DUTIES OF THE MARKET SURVEILLANCE AUTHORITIES AND OF THE SINGLE LIAISON OFFICE

When deciding what checks to carry out, on what type of products and on what scale, market surveillance authorities follow a risk-based approach.

When economic operators present test reports or certificates attesting the conformity of their products issued by a conformity assessment body accredited in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 765/2008, market surveillance authorities appropriately take these reports or certificates into account.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - ORGANISATION, ACTIVITIES AND DUTIES OF THE MARKET SURVEILLANCE AUTHORITIES AND OF THE SINGLE LIAISON OFFICE

Evidence used by a market surveillance authority in one Member State may be used as part of investigations to verify the compliance of products with the requirements carried out by market surveillance authorities in another Member State.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - ORGANISATION, ACTIVITIES AND DUTIES OF THE MARKET SURVEILLANCE AUTHORITIES AND OF THE SINGLE LIAISON OFFICE

Market surveillance authorities establish the following procedures in relation to products that are subject to EU harmonization legislation:

- Procedures to ensure the consideration of complaints or reports on issues related to risks or non-compliance

- procedures for verifying whether the corrective actions that should have been taken by economic operators have actually been taken.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - ORGANISATION, ACTIVITIES AND DUTIES OF THE MARKET SURVEILLANCE AUTHORITIES AND OF THE SINGLE LIAISON OFFICE

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 – POWERS AND MEASURES RELATING TO MARKET SURVEILLANCE

Member States provide their market surveillance authorities with the powers of market surveillance, investigation and enforcement.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 – POWERS AND MEASURES RELATING TO MARKET SURVEILLANCE

Market surveillance authorities ensure that when no other effective means are available to eliminate a serious risk, products are withdrawn or recalled from the market, or their placing on the market is prohibited. The market surveillance authorities immediately notify the Commission about this.

A decision on whether a product poses a serious risk is based on an appropriate risk assessment, which takes into account the nature of the hazard and the likelihood of its occurrence.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 – POWERS AND MEASURES RELATING TO MARKET SURVEILLANCE

If a product presenting a serious risk has been placed on the market, the market surveillance authorities immediately notify the Commission of all voluntary measures taken and reported by the economic operator to the market surveillance authority

The Rapid Information Exchange System is used.

The Commission provides and maintains a data interface between the Rapid Information Exchange System and the information and communication system, with the aim of avoiding the need for double data entry.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 – CROSS-BORDER MUTUAL ASSISTANCE

Effective cooperation and information exchange take place between the market surveillance authorities of the Member States, as well as between the market surveillance authorities, the Commission, and the relevant EU agencies.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 – COORDINATED ENFORCEMENT AND INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

An EU Product Compliance Network (the "Network") is hereby established.

The purpose of the Network is to serve as a platform for structured coordination and cooperation between the enforcement authorities of the Member States and the Commission, and to streamline market surveillance practices within the EU, thereby helping to make market surveillance more effective.

The network consists of representatives from each Member State, including one representative from each of the single liaison offices and a national expert of choice, the chairpersons of the ADCO groups, and representatives of the Commission.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - COORDINATED LAW ENFORCEMENT AND INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

The meetings of the ADCO groups are intended only for representatives of market surveillance authorities and the Commission.

The Commission supports and encourages cooperation between market surveillance authorities through the Network and participates in the meetings of the Network, its subgroups and the ADCO groups.

The network may create permanent or temporary subgroups dealing with specific issues and tasks.

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REGULATION (EU) 2019/1020 - COORDINATED LAW ENFORCEMENT AND INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

The Commission further develops and maintains an information and communication system for collecting, processing, and storing information in a structured manner on issues related to the implementation of EU harmonization legislation, with the aim of improving data exchange between Member States.

The Commission further develops and maintains an electronic interface between this system and the national market surveillance systems.

The Commission develops an electronic interface to allow the transmission of data between national customs systems and the information and communication system.

In order to improve the efficiency of market surveillance in the EU, the Commission may cooperate and exchange market surveillance-related information with regulatory authorities of third countries or international organizations.

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

AFCOS

Topic 1: CARBON FOOTPRINT & LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

Module 3 “Green & Digital Transition”

Course “Specific rules for standardization of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope”

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AGENDA

Introduction to Carbon Footprint (CF) and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

Why CF and LCA matters?

CF vs LCA

How to calculate CF and conduct LCA

Sources of emissions

Case studies. Strategies for reducing

Conclusions

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Introduction to Carbon Footprint (CF)

CF - quantification of greenhouse gases (GHG) issued directly or indirectly by products, services, companies

Expressed in terms of equivalent tons of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions

The concept of CF - born as part of the ecological footprint, as one indicator of our impact on the Earth.

The concept gained popularity in the early 2000s with increasing awareness of climate change (BP's public awareness campaign – asking people about their CF, 1st online CF calculator)

In 2015, with the signing of the Paris Agreement, governments were able to analyze precise data about their countries' CF, and the focus shifted to companies

As a pioneer in environmental impact assessment, having conducted its first footprint survey in 1991, Patagonia aims to achieve carbon neutrality by 2025—a significantly more ambitious target than most companies.

Since the 2010s, calculating and disclosing carbon footprints has gone from a rarity to a common regulatory and investor expectation globally.

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Introduction to Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

LCA - a comprehensive method for assessing a wide range of environmental impacts of a product, process, or service throughout its entire life cycle

Environmental impacts: climate change, human and eco-toxicity, ionizing radiation, and resource base deterioration

<https://oneclicklca.com/>

A 1969 Coca-Cola bottle study was its starting point, but it wasn't widely used until the late 1980s

Today, LCA is a globally recognized and essential tool for environmental management, sustainable development, and ecological design, widely applied across diverse fields like manufacturing, transportation, and energy.

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Why CF and LCA matters?

CF

- quantifies total GHG emissions - the main cause of climate change - to pinpoint key sources and guide reduction strategies
- easy to understand and communicate, making it a powerful tool for raising awareness and engaging individuals, businesses, and governments in climate action
- helps in identifying major sources of pollution, enabling stakeholders to develop effective strategies to reduce ecological impact. This awareness drives policy changes, influences consumer behavior, and shapes corporate strategies towards sustainability

- takes a broader view by assessing the environmental impact of a product or service throughout its entire life cycle
- crucial for identifying opportunities to improve the environmental performance of products at various points in their lifecycle and aids businesses and consumers in making more informed decisions
- enables key sustainability initiatives, such as eco-labeling, green procurement, and environmental regulations

LCA

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Why CF and LCA matters?

- ✓ With GHG reporting becoming mandatory in many regions, proactive CF and LCA assessments allow businesses to anticipate **regulatory changes** and avoid costly future adjustments
- ✓ With increasing regulations on **product environmental impact** (energy efficiency and material restrictions), LCA helps companies prove compliance
- ✓ **Transparency in environmental performance**, through LCA and CF data, builds customer trust and enhances brand reputation
- ✓ By pinpointing resource inefficiencies (e.g., energy, water, and materials), LCA enables businesses to **optimize processes, reduce waste**, and achieve significant **cost savings**
- ✓ By highlighting opportunities to reduce waste and boost recycling, LCA can drive cost savings in disposal and generate revenue from **recovered materials**

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CF and LCA

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CF vs LCA

Scope of Assessment

CF - focuses specifically on greenhouse gas emissions

LCA - provides broader range of environmental impact categories beyond GHGs, including water use, eutrophication, acidification, smog, resource depletion, and toxicity impacts on humans and ecosystems

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CF vs LCA

Purpose and Application

CF - used for understanding and communicating climate impacts and promoting carbon management and reduction strategies, with applications in carbon labeling, regulatory compliance, setting and tracking emissions reduction targets

LCA - used for evaluating and improving the overall environmental footprint of a product or service, but also for product design, eco-labeling, policymaking, and strategic planning

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CF vs LCA

Outcome and Reporting

CF - a single metric (e.g., tonnes of CO₂-equivalent), which simplifies communication but may overlook other environmental dimensions

LCA - a multi-dimensional view of environmental impacts, leading to a comprehensive report that helps identify trade-offs and synergistic opportunities for environmental performance improvements

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CF vs LCA

Role

CF - a crucial metric for addressing climate change

- it's pivotal in tracking progress towards climate goals, such as those outlined in the Paris Agreement.
- integral in carbon trading schemes and in corporate social responsibility (CSR) strategies focused on climate impact

LCA - a comprehensive tool that informs broader environmental strategies, helping organizations minimize their ecological footprint across various impact categories

- essential in developing more sustainable products, enhancing resource efficiency, and supporting circular economy initiatives

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How to calculate CF and conduct LCA

<https://www.iso.org/home.html>

<https://ghgprotocol.org/>

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the world's most widely used GHG accounting standards and guidance

provides a comprehensive framework for measuring and managing GHG emissions for both organizations (corporations, NGOs, government agencies) and projects

helps companies to understand their CF, set reductions, track progress over time, compare performance across different organizations

The **Corporate Standard** – first launched in 2001 and revised in 2004 – has been widely adopted by businesses, NGOs, and governments around the world as the international standard for developing and reporting a company-wide GHG inventory.

The *Corporate Standard* classifies a company’s direct and indirect GHG emissions into 3 “scopes”:

scope 1 emissions (i.e., direct emissions from owned or controlled sources)

scope 2 emissions (i.e., indirect emissions from the generation of purchased energy consumed by the reporting company)

optional scope 3 emissions (i.e., all other indirect emissions that occur in a company’s value chain).

<https://www.epa.gov/climateleadership/scope-3-inventory-guidance>

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ISO standards for *CF of a product*

EN ISO 14044:2007 Environmental management - Life cycle assessment – Requirements and guidelines

EN ISO 14026:2019 Environmental labels and declarations - Principles, requirements and guidelines for communication of footprint information

EN ISO 14027:2017 Environmental labels and declarations - Development of product category rules

ISO 14067: 2018 Greenhouse gases - Carbon footprint of products - Requirements and guidelines for quantification

ISO/TS 14071: 2014 Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Critical review processes and reviewer competencies: Additional requirements and guidelines to ISO 14044:2006

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ISO 14060 series of standards offers **organizations** practical guidance for managing **GHG emissions**

ISO 14064-1: 2018 Greenhouse gases – Part 1: Specification with guidance at the organization level for quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions and removals

ISO 14064-2: 2019 Greenhouse gases - Part 2: Specification with guidance at the project level for quantification, monitoring and reporting of greenhouse gas emission reductions or removal

ISO 14064-3: 2019 Greenhouse gases - Part 3: Specification with guidance for the verification and validation of greenhouse gas statements

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ISO 14065: 2020 General principles and requirements for bodies validating and verifying environmental information

ISO 14066: 2011 Greenhouse gases - Competence requirements for greenhouse gas validation teams and verification teams

ISO 14067: 2018 Greenhouse gases - Carbon footprint of products - Requirements and guidelines for quantification

ISO/TR 14069:2013 Greenhouse gases - Quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions for organizations - Guidance for the application of ISO 14064-1

Life cycle assessment (LCA) ISO standards

ISO 14040:2006 - Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework

EN ISO 14044:2007 Environmental management - Life cycle assessment – Requirements and guidelines

ISO 14046:2014 Environmental management — Water footprint — Principles, requirements and guidelines

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Life cycle assessment (LCA) ISO standards

ISO/TS 14048:2002 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Data documentation format

ISO 14067: 2018 Greenhouse gases - Carbon footprint of products - Requirements and guidelines for quantification

ISO/TS 14072:2014 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines for organizational life cycle assessment

ISO/TS 14071:2014 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Critical review processes and reviewer competencies: Additional requirements and guidelines to ISO 14044:2006

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LCA phases

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Embodied impact

Product stage (A1 - A3)			Construction stage (A4 - A5)		Use stage (B1 - B7)					End of life stage (C1 - C4)			
Raw material extraction	Transport	Manufacturing	Transport	Construction and installation processes	Use	Maintenance	Repair	Replacement	Refurbishment	Deconstruction/ Demolition	Transport	Waste processing	Disposal
A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	C1	C2	C3	C4

Circular economy

Beyond the building life cycle stage (D)		
Benefits		
Reuse	Recovery	Recycling
D	D	D

Operational impact

B6	Operational energy
B7	Operational water

Cradle to Gate

Cradle to Grave (Building life cycle information)

Cradle to Cradel (Building Assessment information)

LCA phases and modules included in the assessment

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<https://hieducarbon.tuke.sk/>

Tools for CF and LCA

CF

Individuals

- Carbon Footprint Calculator
- Ecological Footprint Calculator
- Myclimate

Businesses

- GHG Protocol Tools
- Carbon Trust
- Sphera

LCA

- SimaPro
- GaBi (by Sphera)
- Umberto
- One Click LCA

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Sources of emissions

Scope 1 – direct emissions from a company’s owned or controlled sources.

On-site energy (natural gas and fuel),

Refrigerants

Emissions from combustion in owned or controlled boilers and furnaces

Emissions from fleet vehicles (e.g. cars, vans, trucks, helicopters for hospitals)

Process emissions that are released during industrial processes and on-site manufacturing (e.g. factory fumes, chemicals).

Scope 2 – indirect emissions from purchased or acquired energy

Electricity,

Steam,

Heat or cooling

Scope 3 – indirect emissions from sources that are not owned and not directly controlled by the reporting company

Purchased goods and services

Capital goods

Fuel & energy-related activities

Upstream Transportation and Distribution

Waste generated in operations

Business travel

Employee commuting

Upstream leased assets

Downstream transportation and distribution

Processing of sold products

Use of sold products

End-of-life treatment of sold Products

Downstream leased assets

Franchises

Investments

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Case studies. Strategies for reducing

Corporate Responsibility

- ❑ a company's commitment to minimizing its environmental impact through
- ❑ **sustainable practices**, ethical operations, and **responsible resource management**
- ❑ businesses that take proactive steps can **enhance their reputation**, **improve efficiency**, and contribute to **global climate goals**.

Strategies for reducing

- ❑ Energy efficiency measures
- ❑ Transitioning to renewable energy
- ❑ Low-carbon transportation
- ❑ Sustainable supply chain management
- ❑ Waste reduction and recycling
- ❑ Eco-friendly materials
- ❑ Water conservation
- ❑ Carbon offsetting programs
- ❑ Green bonds and climate finance

Case studies – Coca-Cola the 1st LCA

Coca-Cola conducted its first Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) in 1969

The goal was to evaluate the environmental impact of their beverage containers and compare different packaging options

The methodology was known as Resource and Environmental Profile Analysis (REPA), which involved quantifying the raw materials and fuels used, as well as the environmental impact of the manufacturing processes for each container type.

The European equivalent was called an Ecobalance (The German name of Life Cycle Assessment, Ökobilanz, is directly derived from this term).

© Coca-Cola

<https://ecochain.com/>

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Case studies – Coca-Cola the 1st LCA

The first LCA helped Coca-Cola understand that the type of packaging used (glass bottles, plastic bottles and aluminum cans) had different environmental footprints

Plastic bottles were the most environmentally friendly packaging, followed by aluminum cans and then glass bottles (assessed in terms of fossil fuel use, GHG emissions and water usage)

- primarily due to their lighter weight and lower energy requirements during production and transportation

Coca Cola 1st LCA paved the way for the development of standardized LCA methodologies, which are now widely used by companies across various industries.

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Case studies – AI Lab Technical University of Cluj-Napoca. Building Life-Cycle Impact Reduction

<https://dicositiganas.ro/>

Scope

Compare the **different impact categories** based on the **LCA** requirements of the **whole building**

Include

Materials of the **building structure**
Materials of the **building envelope**
Over a 60-year period

Exclude

Operational energy
Water use
Construction site impacts

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Case studies – AI Lab Technical University of Cluj-Napoca. Building Life-Cycle Impact Reduction

Software used

One Click LCA

Life cycle stages

A1-A3 (Construction Materials)

A4 (Transportation to site)

B1-B5 (Maintenance and material replacements)

C1-C4 (Deconstruction)

Two scenarios

Initial scenario: baseline material – rebar 60%

Optimised scenario: proposed material – rebar 90%

All the building data, the other material types and quantities remained the same for the two design simulations

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Case studies – AI Lab Technical University of Cluj-Napoca. Building Life-Cycle Impact Reduction

- ✓ The materials used in the **initial design** generate **10,510,815 kg CO2e** versus **8,887,911 kg CO2e** in the case of the materials used in the **optimized design**
- ✓ The difference of **1,622,904 kg CO2e** is related to the **30% increase in the recycled content in the rebar** total quantities in the optimized design.

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Case studies – AI Lab Technical University of Cluj-Napoca. Building Life-Cycle Impact Reduction

Impact category	Unit	Reduction %
Global warming potential (GWP)	kgCO ₂ e	-15%
Ozone depletion potential (ODP)	kgCFC-11e	-0.1%
Acidification potential (AP)	kgSO ₂ e	-20%
Eutrophication potential (EP)	Kg PO ₄ e	+2.2%
Formation of ozone of lower atmosphere (POCP)	C ₂ H ₄ e	-29%
Depletion of non-renewable energy resources	MJ	-19%

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Case studies – CF for Technical University of Cluj-Napoca

Scope

CF analysis based
on GHG Protocol
methodology
Scope 1, 2 and 3
2 years period

Include

- Scope 1 direct emissions:
- ✓ Natural gas from thermal plant
 - ✓ Mobile fuel from vehicle fleet
- Scope 2 indirect emission
- ✓ Electricity consumption and self-generated
- Scope 3 indirect emissions
- ✓ Purchased good and services
 - ✓ Capital goods
 - ✓ Fuel and energy related activities
 - ✓ Waste from operation
 - ✓ Business travel
 - ✓ Investments

Exclude

- Scope 3 indirect emissions
- Upstream/downstream transportation and distribution
 - Employee commuting
 - Upstream/downstream leased assets
 - Processing/use/end-of-life of sold products
 - Franchises

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Case studies – CF for Technical University of Cluj-Napoca

2022

2023

The largest portion of emissions continued to come from stationary fuel usage, especially natural gas

The rise in scope 1 GHG emissions resulted from the completion and operational use of two newly refurbished university buildings

Less renovation-related waste explains the operational waste reduction in 2023

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Case studies – CF for Technical University of Cluj-Napoca

Area: 238,678 m²

2022: 19722 persons 2023: 19985 persons

Completed building renovations, which had temporarily raised emissions, led to the 2023 scope 3 emissions decrease

Scope 3's considerable contribution makes its inclusion essential for a comprehensive carbon footprint analysis

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Challenges and Limitations

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Who benefits from a Life Cycle Assessment?

- Companies often must meet environmental regulations to bid on public projects, like providing a product's life cycle assessment. This compliance is crucial for continued business.
- Lower-emission products are desirable for various reasons, including efficiency. Life Cycle Assessments can help R&D compare material options for minimal environmental impact.

Product Management
/ Research &
Development (R&D)

- Supply chains often dominate a product's environmental impact.
- LCAs help Supply Chain Managers and Procurement choose suppliers based on environmental performance, not just price.

Supply Chain
Management /
Procurement

- Consumers increasingly expect companies to be environmentally responsible.
- LCAs help marketing and sales understand and communicate product sustainability, revealing competitive advantages and areas for improvement.

Marketing & Sales

- Sustainability is now a key strategic concern, not just greenwashing.
- LCAs provide crucial insights for top management to make informed decisions about environmental impact, offering a broader perspective than other analyses.

Executive Level &
Strategic
Management

<https://ecochain.com/>

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Conclusions

While both the CF and LCA aim to *reduce environmental impacts*, their roles and applications cater to different but complementary aspects of sustainability

The *CF* is crucial for addressing specific concerns about *climate change*, whereas *LCA* provides a more holistic approach to understanding and mitigating *broader environmental effects*

Employing both tools provide a comprehensive understanding of the *environmental impact* of products, services, and activities, enabling *informed decisions* for a more *sustainable future*

CF and LCA are not just about "*doing the right thing*" for the environment; they are also about *good business strategy*.

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For more information:

info@afcoss-project.eu

<https://afcoss-project.eu/>

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

AFCOS

Topic 2: CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Module 3 “Green & Digital Transition”

Course “Specific rules for standardization of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope”

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AGENDA

Introduction to circular economy

Principles of circular economy

Benefits of circular economy

Case studies. Future trends in circular economy

Conclusions

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Introduction to circular economy

LINEAR ECONOMY

CIRCULAR ECONOMY

ENERGY FROM FINITE SOURCES

With smart design we can reduce waste, save costs and regenerate the natural landscapes

ENERGY FROM RENEWABLE SOURCES

<https://www.dreamstime.com/illustration/circular-economy-linear.html>

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While the term "Circular Economy" (CE) is relatively recent, the underlying concepts have deep roots in history and have evolved over time

The economist **Kenneth Boulding** proposed the idea of a "**closed-loop system**," where resources are reused indefinitely (1960s)

The architect and economist **Walter Stahel** introduced the idea of a "**closed-loop economy**" in his paper "**The Product-Life Factor**" (1980s). He focused on extending the life of products through reuse, repair, and remanufacturing, which later became key pillars of the circular economy

Developed by **Michael Braungart and William McDonough**, the concept **Cradle to Cradle** proposed designing products for perpetual cycles, either as **biological nutrients** or **technical materials** (1990s)

Founded by Ellen MacArthur, the **Ellen MacArthur Foundation** has been a driving force in advancing CE globally. Their 2012 report, "**Towards the Circular Economy**," played a pivotal role in spreading CE principles across businesses and governments.

The EU launched its **Circular Economy Action Plan**, setting ambitious goals for recycling, resource efficiency, and reducing waste (2015)

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Definition of circular economy

„Moving away from our current linear economy (make-use-dispose) towards one where our products, and the materials they contain, are valued differently; creating a more robust economy in the process”.

Environmental Audit Committee
(2014)

„Re-using, repairing, refurbishing and recycling existing materials and products. What used to be regarded as „waste” can turn into a resource. All resources need to be managed more efficiently throughout their life cycle.”

European Commission (2014)

„Seeks to ultimately decouple global economic development from finite resource consumption. It enables key policy objectives such as generating economic growth, creating jobs, and reducing environmental impacts, including carbon emissions”.

Ellen MacArthur Foundation
(2015)

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Origins of circular economy

The **IDEAS** of a **CIRCULAR ECONOMY** are founded on several different **SCHOOLS OF THOUGHT**

It takes inspiration from biological cycles where nothing is wasted and waste is food

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1. Cradle to Cradle concept - instead of being „less bad” to the environment, the aim should be to be „100% good”

All material involved in industrial and commercial processes to be nutrients, of which there are two main categories:

technical and biologic

3 principles

takes inspiration from natural systems, where there is no concept of waste: everything is a resource for something else

use clean and renewable energy

celebrate diversity: diversity builds resilience in natural systems, and can do so in human systems

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Selecting materials and products that are compatible with the principles of a circular economy ***is complex***.

The shortcut is to ***use certification schemes*** that analyse and assess products against these criteria and label products according to their relative environmental performance.

Cradle to Cradle Certified

Cradle to Cradle Certified® is the leading multi-attribute standard used globally across industries by designers, brands and manufacturers for designing and making products that enable a healthy, equitable and sustainable future. For more than a decade, Cradle to Cradle Certified has been helping companies to innovate and optimize materials and products according to the world's most advanced science-based measures.

To date, more than **34,000 products** have been **Cradle to Cradle Certified®** across a variety of categories including building materials, interior finishes, furniture and household products, automotive, consumer electronics, textiles and apparel, cosmetics and personal care, cleaning products, paper, packaging and polymers.

<https://c2ccertified.org/>

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The Cradle to Cradle Certified® Product Standard provides the *framework to assess* the safety, circularity and responsibility of materials and products across five categories of *sustainability performance*

product manufacturing results in a positive impact on air quality, the renewable energy supply, and the balance of climate changing greenhouse gasses

chemicals and materials used in the product are selected to prioritize the protection of human health and the environment

clean air & climate protection

water and soil are treated as precious and shared resources. Watersheds and soil ecosystems are protected, and clean water and healthy soils are available to people and all other organisms

water & soil stewardship

material health

product circularity

products are intentionally designed for their next use and are actively cycled in their intended cycling pathways

companies are committed to upholding human rights and applying fair and equitable business practices

social fairness

<https://c2ccertified.org/>

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C2C Certified® Circularity

C2C Certified Circularity® focuses on **product circularity** and offers measurable goals to guide all aspects of circular product development – from product design and sourcing of materials, to circular systems, packaging, and material health.

Backed by rigorous **third-party verification**, **C2C Certified®**

Circularity enables **companies** to confidently communicate their tangible steps **toward circular economy leadership**.

As a supportive tool for compliance, the certification helps companies meet and go beyond evolving regulatory standards while **fostering innovation in circular design**.

<https://c2ccertified.org/>

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Different types of materials and products with C2C Certification

<https://c2ccertified.org/>

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2. Biomimicry concept “Innovation inspired by nature” - Janine Benyus

Biomimicry is about mimicking (imitating) the way that living organisms solve design challenges to produce sustainable solutions.

Nature uses structure and form to create stiffness and flexibility. Structural elements such as bones and tree trunks use complex forms to create light and efficient structures from microstructures.

Products can be made with the exact amount of material required to perform the function needed, so structures could have material added at points of increased stress and even designed with the complex internal geometries demonstrated in nature.

Example: birds can fly with no need for fossil fuels, barnacles can adhere to underwater surfaces and have a tremendous ability to stay attached, insects outweigh humans yet cause no pollution or waste, leaves soak up sunlight and manage to efficiently and effectively transport water and nutrients through a dense network

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<http://www.exploration-architecture.com/>

The Biomimetic Office Building

- ✓ uses **biomimicry** to create a self-heated, self-cooled, self-ventilated, and day-lit structure that is also a net producer of energy
- ✓ is inspired by the **spookfish's** way of focusing low light levels
- ✓ a mirror is used for **focusing low-intensity light** in building that **reduces energy use and raise occupants' wellbeing.**

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3. Industrial Symbiosis

Industrial Symbiosis is the study of how materials flow between industries and finding opportunities to use „waste“ from one industry as a raw material for another.

It identifies business opportunities that optimize industrial processes and use underutilized resources such as materials, energy, water, capacity, expertise, assets, or other by-products, etc.

Industrial Symbiosis is a business collaboration where residuals from one enterprise serve as input for another enterprise – thereby reducing the total impact of the industry on the environment.

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Kalundborg Symbiosis

- ✓ is a partnership between 9 public and private companies in Kalundborg, Denmark.
- ✓ since 1972, they develop the world's first industrial symbiosis with a circular approach to production.
- ✓ by working together and exchanging material, water, and energy streams between the partners, Kalundborg Symbiosis increases resilience and economic gains, while reducing the environmental impact and expenses.

<https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/>

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Key benefits of industrial symbiosis

Impact reduction

Reduction of environmental impact of waste through recovery, reuse and recycling

Biostabilisation reduces the environmental impacts and risks associated with waste that are sent to landfill

Economic value

Creation of economic value from waste material

Climate and air

Reduction of GHG emissions from waste transport and raw material extraction

Reduction of reliance on fossil fuels and decrease of emissions of Nox, SO₂, CO₂

Knowledge and skills

Extension of knowledge and practical know-how of how waste management can be transformed into a sustainable and growth-oriented business

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Principles of circular economy

Eliminate waste and pollution

Circulate products and materials

Regenerate nature

designing products, materials, and infrastructure to re-enter the economy after use

maintaining, reusing, and refurbishing materials and products

improving natural environments and building biodiversity
In nature, there is no waste. Waste is a human invention.

The *linear economy* is a choice we made; let's choose a *circular economy* and redesign our economy for a *positive future.*

<https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/>

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A restorative *circular economy* prioritizes *shifting materials* in consumables from *technical to biological nutrients*, cascading them through various uses, extracting valuable components, and ultimately returning nutrients to nature.

1 Hunting and fishing
2 Can take both post-harvest and post-consumer waste as an input

SOURCE
Ellen MacArthur Foundation
Circular economy systems diagram (February 2019)
www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org
Drawing based on Braungart & McDonough,
Cradle to Cradle (C2C)

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In the *technical cycle*, products and materials are *kept in circulation* through processes such as *reuse, repair, remanufacture and recycling*.

Relevant for products that are *used rather than consumed*.

The *inner loops* are where *most value* can be captured because they *retain more of the embedded value* of a product by keeping it whole.

Inner loops like *sharing, maintaining, and reusing* should be prioritised above the outer loops that see the product broken down and remade.

The outermost loop, *recycling*, is therefore the *stage of last resort* in a circular economy, because it means *losing the embedded value of a product* by reducing it to its basic materials

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In the *biological cycle*, the nutrients from *biodegradable materials* are returned to the Earth to *regenerate nature*.

This process primarily applies to *consumable goods* like food.

Some biodegradable materials, such as cotton or wood, may eventually make their way from the technical cycle into the biological cycle once they have degraded to a point where they can no longer be used to make new products.

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Smarter product use and manufacture	R0	Refuse	Avoid using unnecessary resources by designing waste out of the system (e.g., refusing single-use plastics)
	R1	Rethink	Rethink – Redesign products and business models for sustainability (e.g., product-as-a-service models instead of ownership)
	R2	Reduce	Minimize resource and energy consumption in production and usage
Extend lifespan of product and its parts	R3	Reuse	Extend product life by using items multiple times before disposal
	R4	Repair	Fix and maintain products to extend their lifespan
	R5	Refurbish	Restore products to good working condition for continued use
	R6	Remanufacture	Rebuild products using parts from used goods to maintain functionality
	R7	Repurpose	Adapt discarded products or materials for a different use
Useful application of materials	R8	Recycle	Process materials to create new raw materials for manufacturing
	R9	Recovery	Extract useful energy or materials from waste when other options are exhausted

10R of CE

Strategies that guide how we can *keep resources* in use for as long as possible, extract the *maximum value* from them whilst in use, then *recover* and *regenerate* products and materials at the end of each service life.

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Benefits of circular economy

The circular economy (CE) offers significant *benefits* across *environmental*, *economic*, and *social dimensions* by shifting from the linear "*take-make-waste*" model to a regenerative "*reduce-reuse-recycle*" system

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The ***circular economy*** represents a win-win solution, addressing environmental challenges while creating economic and social value. By transitioning to this model, we can build a ***sustainable, resilient future*** for both ***businesses and society***.

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Case studies. Future trends in circular economy

1. ARUP Group Limited

A leader in the transition to a circular built environment: Arup Group Limited

<https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/>

Multi-disciplinary design firm known for innovative projects (Sydney Opera House)

Knowledge partner of the Ellen MacArthur Foundation since 2016

Adopt circular economy principles to achieve the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Projects like the Forth Road Bridge in Scotland demonstrate significant resource savings and reduced environmental impact

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Case studies. Future trends in circular economy

ARUP's initiatives

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Case studies. Future trends in circular economy

Quay Quarter Tower (projects by Arup) Sydney, Australia

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Case studies. Future trends in circular economy

The Living Lab (projects by Arup)
Hong Kong, China

<https://ce-toolkit.dhub.arup.com/>

The Living Lab encourages behavioral change through small, consistent actions

Boasting a renewable energy system, the building upcycles the algae in the façade together with food waste and black water in a tri-digestion process to generate a renewable supply of electricity and hot water for daily operations.

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Case studies. Future trends in circular economy

2. Brummen Town Hall Brummen, Netherlands

A building that can be reused: Brummen Town Hall

Was designed by architect Thomas Rau to be dismantled and reused after 20 years. The building uses a modular, Lego-like structure with 90% of materials being reusable.

The construction avoided difficult-to-recycle concrete, opting instead for high-quality prefabricated timber elements to maximize future reuse

The building was designed with a circular economy approach, ensuring that materials can be economically recovered and reused in future buildings.

Brummen Town Hall received the world's first materials passport, recording information about the building's materials, components, and products, turning it into a "material depot" for future use.

The design reduces carbon emissions and ensures that building materials will have a 20% residual value at the end of the building's life. The modular construction method also reduced the construction period and costs.

<https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/>

Case studies. Future trends in circular economy

3. HAUT

Amsterdam, Netherlands

HAUT is a 21-floor timber hybrid building in Amsterdam, completed in 2022, featuring 55 apartments, parking, and a city garden. It is the first residential building in the Netherlands to achieve BREEAM Outstanding certification.

Timber construction reduces carbon emissions by 50% compared to conventional buildings and stores approximately 1,800 tonnes of CO₂.

Experts suggest timber is best used for extensions and mid-rise constructions. The Cirerers project in Barcelona demonstrates timber's application in affordable housing.

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Case studies. Future trends in circular economy

4. Universal bottle

Coca-Cola

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Case studies. Future trends in circular economy

5. Superuse Studios

Netherlands

Finding and utilising 'waste' materials for construction purposes: Superuse Studios

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Case studies. Future trends in circular economy

6. Văcărești Nature Park

Bucharest, Romania

Located in Bucharest, Romania, it evolved into an urban wetland after the government abandoned plans to build a reservoir in 1989

Provides critical ecosystem services, such as water management and temperature regulation. It acts as a natural water filtration system and helps cool the air during hot summer months.

According to a 2022 report, nature-based solutions like wetlands are 50% more cost-effective than grey infrastructure, yet they received only 0.3% of overall spending on urban infrastructure in 2021.

Is a powerful example of the potential of maximizing nature-based solutions for urban resilience and sustainability.

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Future trends in circular economy

The future of the circular economy will be shaped by

- technological advancements,
- policy changes,
- innovative business models,
- shifting consumer behaviors.

Companies that embrace circular principles will benefit from:

- cost savings,
- regulatory compliance,
- stronger customer loyalty - making sustainability a competitive advantage rather than just an environmental obligation.

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Conclusions

While not explicitly mandatory, the adoption of these principles is strongly encouraged through various EU directives and national policies aimed at **enhancing resource efficiency, reducing waste, and promoting the use of renewable materials**

The circular economy approach in construction not only addresses environmental concerns but also offers significant **economic benefits**, including cost savings, job creation, and **increased competitiveness through innovative practices**

As awareness and regulatory frameworks continue to evolve, circular economy practices are set to become more prevalent, driving the construction industry towards a more **sustainable and resilient future**

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For more information:

info@afcoss-project.eu

<https://afcoss-project.eu/>

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

AFCOS

Topic 3: GREEN BUILDING CERTIFICATIONS

Module 3 “Green & Digital Transition”

Course “Specific rules for standardization of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope”

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AGENDA

Introduction to green building certifications

Benefits of green building certifications

Types of green building certifications

Certification process

Case study

Conclusions

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Introduction to Green Building Certifications

Green Building Certifications

- a set of ***standards*** and ***rating systems*** that recognize and promote ***environmentally responsible construction*** and ***operation*** of buildings
- a ***framework for assessing a building's performance*** in various areas of sustainability, such as ***energy efficiency, water conservation, material selection, indoor environmental quality***

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Buildings have extensive direct and indirect ***impacts on the environment***

Buildings ***consume*** energy, water, and materials, while generating ***waste and emissions*** throughout their lifecycle—from construction and occupancy to renovation, repurposing, and demolition

Green building standards, certifications, and rating systems emerged as a direct response to the ***environmental impact of buildings***, promoting ***sustainable design*** as a key solution

Globally, countries have established **green building certifications** to promote sustainable construction and contribute to the UN's Sustainable Development Goals.

While green building certifications have existed since the 1980s, their adoption has accelerated alongside the rise of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) policies

<https://sdgs.un.org/>

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Benefits of green building certifications

Structured Approach

- Certifications provide a clear roadmap for achieving sustainability goals, with established best practices. This allows developers to make informed decisions throughout the construction process.

Reduction in environmental impact

- Sustainable building practices reduce environmental impact, helping companies meet ESG goals and improve brand image.

Innovation

- Certifications encourage the development and implementation of innovative solutions for reducing a building's carbon footprint

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Benefits of green building certifications

Third-Party Verification

- The independent verification process ensures the building meets the stated sustainability criteria. This builds trust and transparency for tenants, buyers, and investors.

Visibility for brands engaging in sustainability

- Sustainability is both eco-conscious and commercially savvy. Consumers and employees demand it, making inaction a business risk. Green building certification effectively showcases a company's sustainability commitment.

Increase in property value, rent prices and lease rates

- Green-certified buildings command higher prices and rents. Based on research, BREEAM-certified properties achieve a 20.6% higher capital value. Sustainable features, like biophilic design, also boost value by improving tenant well-being.

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Benefits of green building certifications

Occupant Health & Wellness

- COVID-19 highlighted the importance of healthy buildings. Green building certifications improve occupant health and well-being through better air quality, daylighting, and biophilic design, while also reducing building operating costs.

Operation and maintenance cost savings

- Green building certifications assess both operational and embodied carbon, leading to long-term cost savings through increased efficiency. While initial investment may be higher, reduced running and maintenance costs offer a strong return.

Tax incentives

- Green building incentives, like tax breaks in the US and potential EU subsidies, can offset higher initial costs, driving their adoption.

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Benefits of green building certifications

Green Financing opportunities

Property tax reduction for green building owners in Cluj-Napoca, Romania

Cluj-Napoca is one of the first cities in Europe to offer a tax deduction for green buildings and the first municipality in Romania to adopt specific measures to promote the development of green buildings

The City Council voted on 24 May 2012 to offer a 50% reduction in property tax for buildings that receive a green certificate and achieve the highest energy efficiency rating

Building owners must provide the following documents to qualify for the property tax reduction:

- ✓ a final reception certificate,
- ✓ an energy performance certificate,
- ✓ a green building certificate (LEED, BREEAM, or DGNB),
- ✓ a declaration of conformity from the Romania Green Building Council.

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Benefits of green building certifications

Green Financing opportunities

Property tax reduction for green building owners in Cluj-Napoca, Romania

For businesses (legal entities): If a building has an "A" energy performance rating and a recognized green building certification, the annual property tax is halved, effectively reducing it from 0.50% to 0.25%.

For homeowners (individuals): A 50% reduction in annual property taxes is granted for residential buildings that achieve an "A" energy performance rating and hold an official green building certification.

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Benefits of green building certifications

Green Financing opportunities

Property tax reduction for the development of green buildings in other EU countries

Spain

offers property tax reductions for green buildings, particularly those with solar installations, but adoption varies widely among municipalities due to a lack of central government guidance.

Bulgaria

offers full real estate tax exemptions for green buildings using renewable energy: 10 years for category A certificates, 5 years for category B. Exemptions apply to energy-reducing renewables and require official energy performance certificates.

Italy

Italy's property tax (ICI) is generally 0.4-0.7% of market value, but can be lower for homes with renewable energy (up to 5 years, 3 for solar thermal).

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Types of green building certifications

BREEAM (Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method)

LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design)

WELL Building Standard

Green Globes

Energy Star

Living Building Challenge

National Green Building Standard

Green Star

EDGE (Excellence in Design for Greater Efficiencies)

CASBEE (Comprehensive Assessment System for Built Environment Efficiency)

DGNB (German Sustainable Building Council)

GREEN Homes (certified by RoGBC)

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1. LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design)

the world's most widely used green building rating system

evaluates buildings based on their design and construction, operation and maintenance, and overall environmental impact

recognized globally and widely used for new and existing buildings

provides a comprehensive framework for sustainable building practices and offers different levels of certification, including LEED Silver, Gold, and Platinum, depending on the building's performance.

Platinum

80+ points earned

Gold

60-79 points earned

Silver

50-59 points earned

Certified

40-49 points earned

<https://www.usgbc.org/>

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1. LEED Certification

BUILDING RATING OR CERTIFICATION SYSTEM	MANAGING ORGANIZATION	TYPE OF STANDARD OR CERTIFICATION	ISSUES / AREAS OF FOCUS
LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design)	U.S. Green Building Council	Green building rating and certification system through independent third-party verification for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New Construction (NC) • Existing Buildings, Operations & Maintenance (EB O&M) • Commercial Interiors (CI) • Core & Shell (CS) • Schools (SCH) • Retail • Healthcare (HC) • Residential • Cities and Communities 	Performance in <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable Sites • Water Efficiency • Integrative Process • Location & Transportation • Energy & Atmosphere • Materials & Resources • Indoor Environmental Quality • Innovation • Regional Priority

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2. BREEM (Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method)

Originating in the UK, it's now used internationally to evaluate and certify the environmental performance of buildings throughout their lifecycle.

is a leading sustainability assessment method for masterplanning projects, infrastructure and buildings.

The certification comes with a star rating from one to six and a designation of "pass," "good," "very good," "excellent," or "outstanding."

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2. BREEAM Certification

BUILDING RATING OR CERTIFICATION SYSTEM	MANAGING ORGANIZATION	TYPE OF STANDARD OR CERTIFICATION	ISSUES / AREAS OF FOCUS
BREEAM (Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method)	BRE Global	Green building rating and certification system through on-site independent third-party verification for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New Construction • In-Use • Refurbishment & Fit Out • Communities • Infrastructure 	Performance in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy • Health & Well-being • Transport • Water • Materials • Waste • Land Use & Ecology • Management • Pollution No prerequisites for In-Use

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LEED vs BREEAM

Feature	LEED	BREEAM
Origin	United States	United Kingdom
Focus	Energy efficiency, design innovation	Project management, climate change adaptation
Scoring System	Point-based, even weighting	Weighted scoring
Certification Process	Self-reporting, USGBC review	Licensed assessors, BRE review
Geographic Popularity	United States, growing globally	United Kingdom, Europe

Both the LEED and BREEAM certifications offer robust frameworks for achieving sustainable building practices. A thorough understanding of their respective criteria is essential for determining the most suitable certification for a given project.

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LEED vs BREEAM

Cost and Resources: The cost implications for LEED and BREEAM depend on several factors, including project size, certified level, location, and consulting fees:

- **LEED Costs:** LEED often has higher registration and certification fees, with additional costs for hiring a LEED Accredited Professional. These fees may range between \$6,000 and \$50,000 depending on project size and certification level.
- **BREEAM Costs:** BREEAM costs are generally lower, particularly for smaller projects, as the certification process can be adapted to specific regional requirements. The average certification fee can range from €3,500 to €20,000.
- **Operational Costs:** While upfront costs are higher, operational savings from energy, water, and maintenance efficiencies contribute to long-term financial benefits.

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3. Green Gloves

BUILDING RATING OR CERTIFICATION SYSTEM	MANAGING ORGANIZATION	TYPE OF STANDARD OR CERTIFICATION	ISSUES / AREAS OF FOCUS
Green Gloves	Green Building Initiative in the U.S. BOMA Canada	Green building guidance and assessment program for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing buildings • New construction 	Environmental assessment areas to earn credits in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy • Indoor Environment • Site • Water Efficiency • Materials • Project Management • No prerequisites

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4. Living Building Challenge

BUILDING RATING OR CERTIFICATION SYSTEM	MANAGING ORGANIZATION	TYPE OF STANDARD OR CERTIFICATION	ISSUES / AREAS OF FOCUS
Living Building Challenge	International Living Future Institute	Performance-based standard, and certification program for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Landscape and infrastructure projects • Partial renovations and complete building renewals • New building construction • Neighborhood, campus and community design 	Performance areas include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Place • Water • Energy • Materials • Health & Happiness • Equity • Beauty • All areas are requirements.

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5. WELL Building Standard

BUILDING RATING OR CERTIFICATION SYSTEM	MANAGING ORGANIZATION	TYPE OF STANDARD OR CERTIFICATION	ISSUES / AREAS OF FOCUS
Living Building Standard	Administered by the International WELL Building Institute™ (IWBI)	Performance based standard and certification program for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New and Existing Buildings • New and Existing Interiors • Core and Shell Retail • Retail • Education Facilities • Restaurant • Commercial Kitchen • Multifamily Residential 	Measures attributes of buildings that impact occupant health by looking at ten factors: Air, Water, Nourishment, Light, Movement, Thermal Comfort, Sound, Materials, Mind, Community, and Innovation.

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5. CASBEE

BUILDING RATING OR CERTIFICATION SYSTEM	MANAGING ORGANIZATION	TYPE OF STANDARD OR CERTIFICATION	ISSUES / AREAS OF FOCUS
CASBEE (Comprehensive Assessment System for Built Environment Efficiency)	JSBC (Japan Sustainable Building Consortium) and its affiliated sub-committees	Building assessment tools for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-design • New Construction • Existing Building and • Renovation 	Assessment areas include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy efficiency • Resource efficiency • Local environment, and • Indoor environment

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6. EDGE

BUILDING RATING OR CERTIFICATION SYSTEM	MANAGING ORGANIZATION	TYPE OF STANDARD OR CERTIFICATION	ISSUES / AREAS OF FOCUS
EDGE (Excellence in Design for Greater Efficiencies)	International Finance Corporation (IFC), a member of the World Bank Group	A universal standard and a certification system for residential and commercial structures.	Assessment areas include: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Energy• Water• Materials

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7. DGNB

BUILDING RATING OR CERTIFICATION SYSTEM	MANAGING ORGANIZATION	TYPE OF STANDARD OR CERTIFICATION	ISSUES / AREAS OF FOCUS
<p>DGNB (German Sustainable Building Council)</p>	<p>Non-profit, participatory association and Europe's largest network for sustainable building. It's the market leader among certification system providers in Germany</p>	<p>An internationally recognized certification with a focus on sustainability in construction. Depending on the project status, the DGNB System can be used as a planning, optimisation or management tool.</p>	<p>©DGNB</p>

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8. GREEN Homes certified by RoGBC

BUILDING RATING OR CERTIFICATION SYSTEM	MANAGING ORGANIZATION	TYPE OF STANDARD OR CERTIFICATION	ISSUES / AREAS OF FOCUS
GREEN Homes	Romania Green Building Council (RoGBC)	Green Homes is a certification system for the residential sector. Is internationally recognised and encourages the construction of better quality, healthier housing with financial benefits for occupants	Romania Green Building Council (RoGBC) has created a certification for Green Housing at an affordable cost, which includes all the essential aspects in evaluating and identifying the best performing residential projects that use sustainable construction principles

CERTIFIED BY

<https://www.rogbc.org/>

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What is a “Green home”?

All **Green Home** strategies aim to reduce or eliminate **environmental impact** through careful design, construction, and operation

There are two processes for assessing project eligibility for Green Finance products:

<https://green-homes.org/>

Holistic Green Assessment

- This applies to full-scale projects like new home construction, multi-family developments, or deep renovations exceeding €10,000.
- A Green Homes assessor and Energy Auditor are required to certify compliance with sustainability criteria.
- This approach is ideal for large projects where multiple green factors can be integrated, such as site selection, energy efficiency, and sustainable design.

Smaller Renovation Projects

- These involve limited upgrades where a full assessment is impractical. Instead, lenders support the financing of eco-friendly materials, technologies, and services.
- A set of "pre-approved" green solutions ensures eligibility for Green Finance products without requiring a dedicated assessor.

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8 GREEN Homes certified by RoGBC. How does the program work?

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A practical financial comparison from Romania shows how investing in green building (low A energy rating and green mortgage qualification) reduces the total monthly cost of homeownership compared to a standard new build (B rating).

While construction costs and energy prices vary globally, this methodology can be replicated in other countries to demonstrate the long-term cost savings associated with green building.

	EPC "B" rated apartment	EPC "A" rated apartment	Green Homes certified apartment
NET SAVINGS WITH GREEN MORTGAGES (in Euros)			
Sales price of 70 sqm apartment with Value Added Tax	98,000	100,100	104,300
Loan amount with 15% down payment	83,300	85,085	88,655
Monthly mortgage payment	499	510	505
Cost of energy/apartment/month (€)	101	65	33
TOTAL COST OF MONTHLY OWNERSHIP: MORTGAGE + ENERGY	600	575	538
Net monthly savings for certified Green Homes versus "B" apartment	0	25	62
Net annual savings for certified Green Homes versus "B" apartment	0	300	744

* Assumptions: Market price: €1,400/sqm; Payment period: 25 years;
The developers will pass on the cost of the energy efficiency improvements directly to the consumers but will not add a profit on it.

COSTS AND SAVINGS OF ENERGY EFFICIENT MEASURES

Construction parameters

Increase in construction cost from green measures (%)	0%	5%	15%
Construction cost (€/sqm)	600	630	690
Additional construction cost from green measures (€/sqm)	0	30	90
Total additional construction cost from green measures for home (€)	0	2,100	6,300

Energy consumption

Energy consumption for heating (kWh/sqm/year)	117	70	50
Energy consumption for domestic hot water (kWh/sqm/year)	35	15	15
Energy consumption for air conditioning (Cooling) (kWh/sqm/year)	35	20	10
Energy consumption for ventilation (kWh/sqm/year)	10	5	5
Energy consumption for lighting (kWh/sqm/year)	49	40	10
Total energy consumption for apartment (kWh/sqm/year)	246	150	90

Cost of energy

Average price of electricity (€/kWh incl. VAT)	0.12	0.12	0.12
Average price of gas (€/kWh incl. VAT)	0.04	0.04	0.04
Annual cost for heating energy (€/sqm/year)	4.89	2.93	2.09
Annual cost for domestic hot water (€/sqm/year)	1.46	0.63	0.63
Annual cost with airconditioning (cooling) (€/sqm/year)	4.11	2.35	1.17
Annual cost for ventilation (€/sqm/year)	1.17	0.59	0.59
Annual cost for lighting (€/sqm/year)	5.75	4.70	1.17
Total annual cost of energy (€/sqm/year)	17.40	11.19	5.65
Total annual cost of energy for 70 sqm apartment (€)	1,217.72	783.18	395.79
Average monthly cost of energy for 70 sqm apartment (€)	101.48	65.27	32.98

Energy cost reductions

Average monthly energy savings relative to "B" apartment	0.00	36.21	68.49
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MORTGAGE RATE CALCULATION

Size of apartment (sqm)	70	70	70
Price of apartment	98,000	100,100	104,300
Percent of down payment	15%	15%	15%
Down payment	14,700	15,015	15,645
Interest rate (7 year fixed; local currency)	5.25%	5.25%	4.75%
Repayment period (years)	25	25	25
Loan amount	83,300	85,085	88,655
Yearly mortgage payment	5,988	6,120	6,060
Monthly mortgage payment	499	510	505

<https://green-homes.org/>

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Certifications process

1

- Decide which rating tool to use to certify your project with

2

- Appoint an Accredited Professional (AP) who is qualified in your rating tool.

3

- Register your project with GBCSA through the online platform

4

- Submit your documentation: Your AP will do this. Depending on the tool, submission stages and information requirements will vary.

5

- Get your project certified: The independent panel of sustainability experts will assess your submission and/or confirm certification.

6

- Promote your achievement: Once certified you will receive your certificate and building plaque, and be ready to celebrate your achievement!

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Case study

What is the difference between an Energy Efficient Building and a GREEN one?

Energy-Efficient Buildings

- Focus: reducing energy consumption
- Key features: high-performance insulation, energy-efficient HVAC systems., efficient lighting, energy-efficient appliances, proper building orientation to maximize natural light and minimize solar heat gain
- Goal: reduce energy bills and decrease the building's carbon footprint by lowering energy consumption

GREEN Buildings

- Focus: Overall environmental impact throughout the building's lifecycle, considers factors beyond just energy consumption
- Key features: all features of energy-efficient buildings, sustainable materials, water conservation measures, improved indoor air quality, waste reduction and recycling
- Goal: Minimize the building's overall environmental footprint, promoting sustainability across energy, materials, water, and occupant well-being

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“Green building” is a more comprehensive term that includes
energy efficiency as a vital component, along with
other **sustainable practices**

All **green buildings** are **energy-efficient**, but
not all energy-efficient buildings are **fully green**

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<https://dicositiganas.ro/>

IQuest, a prominent IT company, was repurposing the former “**Flacăra**” garment factory site to create its new office campus.

The project centers on renovating the factory's main building and adding two modern wings, all connected by a central, publicly accessible indoor space and a shared garden

Integrated certification covers all stages from design, construction and operation:

- ✓ BREEAM OUTSTANDING
- ✓ ZERO WASTE FACILITY
- ✓ GREEN OFFICE: RESTORE OUTSTANDING

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<https://dicositiganas.ro/>

Categories assessed under green building certifications:

- ✓ ENERGY
- ✓ TRANSPORT
- ✓ MATERIALS
- ✓ LAND USE & ECOLOGY
- ✓ INNOVATION
- ✓ HEALTH & WELLBEING
- ✓ MANAGEMENT
- ✓ POLLUTION
- ✓ WATER
- ✓ WASTE

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✓ MANAGEMENT

- Integrated design: Multidisciplinary collaboration and involvement to optimise the design and construction process
- Full reuse of the old Flacăra factory structure: revitalisation of a closed industrial area, a model of urban regeneration

✓ MATERIALS

- Certified wood FSC (Forest Stewardship Council)

✓ MATERIALS, HEALTH & WELLBEING

- Rockwool Frontrock
- Finishes with low volatile organic compound (VOC) content

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✓ HEALTH & WELLBEING

- Individual control of systems for increased occupant comfort:
 - DALI controlled lighting systems - separate dimming of luminaires
 - Luminaires dimmable according to natural light
 - Heating and ventilation systems - realised in the technical floor, zoning to approx. 200 m²
- Integration of natural elements in the interior design of the building: vegetal wall, wooden ceiling, ceramic finishes and flooring

✓ MATERIALS, HEALTH & WELLBEING, INNOVATION

- Knauf Cleaneo Acoustic – gypsum board for sound absorption with air cleaning effect

✓ TRANSPORT

- Easy access to public transport
- Carsharing services, preferential parking for electric cars

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✓ ENERGY

- Higher energy efficiency – certificate class A
- Active solar design - dynamic simulation for the installation of photovoltaic panels
- LED efficient lighting
- Integrated Building Management – BMS
 - All interior lights automatically switch off after 19:00
 - Exterior lights are set at 90° down, reducing light pollution
 - Motion and light sensors
 - Fire prevention and extinguishing systems
- Energy-efficient panoramic elevator with energy recovery on descent

Analysis:
 BREEAM®-Office design (v3)
 Software: IES Virtual Environment FlucsDL v2015

No light penetration through internal windows

Building floor area 14253.7m²
 Selected room area 3021 m²
 No. of spaces in building 157
 Selected number of occupied rooms 39
 External windows area % of ext wall 52%

Result:
#1... BREEAM® HEA 1 2 Credit
 Credit 1 Pass
 Credit 2 (exemplary level) Pass

Analysis #	Date/Time	% area meeting DF target	Daylight factor % (area weighted)	BREEAM @ Credits
1	18 November 2015 at 16:13	99.1	30.1	2

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✓ ENERGY, HEALTH & WELLBEING

- Day lighting
- Solutions to reduce the heat island effect such as roof terraces, light colors of roof membranes

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✓ WATER

- Efficient sanitary equipment for low water consumption

✓ WASTE

- Zero waste solutions: on-site bio-waste prevention, sorting and treatment: building will be the first office building in Romania to implement a complex waste prevention and sorting system for six waste fractions, including on-site treatment of bio-waste.
- Building occupants will benefit from: education, infrastructure, and organization

✓ POLLUTION

- HVAC systems
 - Minimum degree of pollution
 - Air conditioning and ventilation UFAD (Underfloor Air Distribution) - does not use refrigerants
 - Air conditioning of rooms with special purpose - refrigerants: R134a, R410a

✓ LAND USE & ECOLOGY

- Sustainable landscaping

✓ MANAGEMENT

- On-site pollution prevention and reduction plan
- Communication with citizens:
 - introductory letters presenting the project and contact details - sent to all neighbours
 - provide a register of complaints, easily accessible and visible to the public, with contact details and addresses for notifying the public after remedial action has been taken.
- Commissioning:
 - verification and testing of all installed mechanical and safety systems by a third party not involved in the execution process, to optimise post-occupancy performance by eliminating potential errors in the installation of building systems.

✓ MANAGEMENT, INNOVATION

- Education for occupants:
 - educational programme organised over a 12-month period during the building's operational phase, including: building user guides, seminars, competitions, documentary projections

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Conclusions

Green building certifications represent a transformative shift in construction and real estate

They provide immense value by aligning environmental responsibility with economic gains

Certified buildings:

- ✓ Enhance corporate reputation, ensuring alignment with ESG priorities and regulatory compliance.
- ✓ Deliver long-term cost savings through efficient resource use and operational excellence.
- ✓ Attract tenants and investors, offering competitive advantages in the marketplace.

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For more information:

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<https://afcoss-project.eu/>

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

AFCOS

Topic 4: ESG

Module 3 “Green & Digital Transition”

Course “Specific rules for standardization of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope”

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AGENDA

Introduction to ESG

ESG implementation and reporting

Challenges in ESG implementation

Benefits of ESG

Case studies

Future of ESG

Conclusions

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Introduction to ESG

Sustainability is a broad and complex concept, but at its core, it's about meeting *the needs of the present* **without compromising the ability of future** generations to meet their own needs.

Decisions, whether entrepreneurial or political, should consider economic efficiency, social justice, and ecological sustainability. This integrated approach aligns with the principles of **ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance)**.

ESG stands for **environmental, social, and governance**, and is a holistic framework that measures the sustainable and ethical behaviour of a business.

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"Green finance," "sustainable finance," "climate finance," and "low-carbon finance" are related concepts that overlap in their application to financial decisions and investment flows.

The UNFCCC defines "climate finance" as funding from public, private, and other sources, used to mitigate climate change by reducing emissions and to help countries adapt to its effects

"Green finance" expands beyond climate-focused initiatives to address diverse environmental concerns, and it prioritizes channeling private investment, rather than primarily relying on public financial flows

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Environmental issues:

- ❑ nature's health, climate change, waste and depletion

Social issues:

- ❑ people's rights, well-being, and community impact, including labor, health, safety, and ethical conduct

Economic issues:

- ❑ performance, risk, and broader economic impact

Governance issues:

- ❑ how well a company is run, ethically and accountably, for all stakeholders.

Sustainable finance is the broadest term, covering environmental, social, economic and governance factors.

Main goal of sustainable finance - to channel **financial resources** towards **sustainable and inclusive growth** while maintaining **financial stability** in the face of climate-related and other ESG risks

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ESG

<https://sigmaearth.com/>

Environmental

examines how a company manages its impact on the environment:

- Carbon footprint and GHG emissions
- Energy usage and waste management
- Resource conservation (water, materials, etc.)
- Pollution and its prevention
- Commitment to renewable energy and sustainable practices

Climate-related risks refer to financial risks of financial institutions through physical or transition risks caused by extreme weather events or a decline in asset value in carbon-intensive sectors.

Environmental risks refer to financial risks arose due to environmental degradation and the loss of ecosystem services.

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ESG

<https://sigmaearth.com/>

Social

focuses on a company's relationships with employees, customers, suppliers and the communities in which it operates:

- Labor practices and employee rights (e.g., fair wages, working conditions)
- Diversity, equity, and inclusion (e.g., gender and racial diversity in leadership)
- Community engagement and impact
- Customer satisfaction and product safety
- Human rights policies and actions

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Governance

evaluates how a company is run, ensuring that it operates transparently and ethically.
Key areas include:

- Board diversity and structure
- Executive compensation and alignment with company performance
- Shareholder rights and transparency in financial reporting
- Anti-corruption policies and business ethics
- Risk management and compliance with regulations

ESG

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ESG criteria (Environmental, Social and Governance)

ESG factors are becoming increasingly important in how companies and investments are judged.

Evaluations now look beyond just financial results to consider a company's environmental impact, social responsibility, and governance practices.

ESG criteria have evolved beyond their initial environmental focus to now include a broader range of social and governance factors, such as social justice, labor practices, human rights, and ethical conduct.

Companies that consistently prioritize and expand their use of ESG criteria demonstrate a strong commitment to responsible business practices and help build a better future.

ESG implementation

1. Define ESG Strategy & Goals

Identify key ESG factors relevant to the industry and stakeholders.

Align ESG goals with corporate values and long-term business objectives.

Establish ESG policies addressing environmental impact, social responsibility, and governance practices.

2. Assess Current ESG Performance

Conduct ESG materiality assessments to identify risks and opportunities.

Benchmark against industry standards and competitors.

Collect baseline data on carbon footprint, diversity & inclusion, corporate ethics, etc.

3. Integrate ESG into Business Operations

Implement sustainable supply chain practices.

Adopt energy-efficient technologies and carbon reduction initiatives.

Enhance workplace diversity, employee well-being, and community engagement programs.

Strengthen corporate governance, ethics, and transparency measures.

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4. Set KPIs and Track ESG Metrics

Define key performance indicators (KPIs) aligned with ESG goals.

Use ESG reporting frameworks like GRI (Global Reporting Initiative), SASB (Sustainability Accounting Standards Board), TCFD (Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures), etc.

Implement data collection and monitoring tools for accurate reporting.

5. Engage Stakeholders & Ensure Compliance

Communicate ESG initiatives to investors, employees, customers, and regulators.

Ensure compliance with local and international ESG regulations and standards.

Collaborate with ESG rating agencies to enhance transparency.

6. Report & Continuously Improve

Publish annual ESG reports outlining progress, challenges, and future goals.

Seek third-party audits and certifications for credibility.

Regularly update ESG strategies based on emerging trends and stakeholder feedback.

ESG reporting

Enables companies to transparently showcase their commitment to sustainable practices.

It's about more than just profits; it also considers environmental impact, social responsibility, and good governance.

Allows companies to demonstrate their dedication to tackling global issues like climate change, diversity and inclusion, and ethical governance.

Committing to ESG reporting demonstrates a company's commitment to positive environmental and social impact, as well as long-term business success. This builds stakeholder trust and positions the company as a leader in creating a more sustainable world.

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ESG reporting framework

Framework	Overview	Focus area	Who use it	Key strength
Global Reporting Initiative (GRI)	The most widely used global standard for sustainability reporting	Covers a broad range of ESG topics, including climate change, labor practices, human rights, and governance	Companies of all sizes, governments, and NGOs	Provides a modular structure, allowing organizations to report only on material ESG issues
Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB)	Focuses on financially material ESG issues relevant to investors	Industry-specific ESG metrics	Public companies, investors, and asset managers	Helps companies integrate ESG into financial reports for capital markets
Task Force on Climate-Related Financial Disclosures (TCFD)	Focuses on climate-related risks and opportunities in financial reporting	Governance, strategy, risk management, and climate-related financial disclosures	Banks, insurers, investors, and large corporations	Helps organizations assess climate risks under different climate scenarios
European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS)	Developed under the EU Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)	Mandatory ESG reporting for large and listed companies in the EU	Companies operating in or with business in the European Union	Aligns with EU Taxonomy and double materiality (impact on business & society)

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ESG reporting framework

With **numerous ESG frameworks**, each with unique requirements, and the evolving landscape of standards and regulations, selecting the **optimal approach is challenging**.

Companies should select an ESG framework based on **industry, regulatory requirements, and stakeholder needs**.

Many businesses **combine multiple frameworks** (e.g., GRI for sustainability, TCFD for climate risks, and SASB for financial disclosures) **to provide a comprehensive ESG report**.

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Who is required to report in EU?

European Union (EU) – CSRD & ESRS Compliance EU

Under the [Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive \(CSRD\)](#), ESG reporting is mandatory for:

- ✓ Large EU Companies (meeting at least 2 of the following criteria):
 - More than 250 employees
 - Over €40 million in revenue
 - Over €20 million in total assets
- ✓ Listed Companies on EU-regulated markets (except micro-enterprises).
- ✓ Non-EU Companies with:
 - Over €150 million revenue in the EU
 - At least one EU branch/subsidiary meeting local reporting thresholds

[Reporting Framework](#): European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) is [mandatory from](#):

- ✓ 2024 (for large public-interest entities already reporting under NFRD)
- ✓ 2025 (for large companies not previously covered)
- ✓ 2026 (for listed SMEs, except micro-enterprises)
- ✓ 2028 (for non-EU companies meeting revenue criteria)

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Challenges in ESG implementation

Lack of Standardized ESG Frameworks

Multiple ESG reporting standards create confusion.
No universal methodology for measuring ESG performance.
Difficulty in comparing ESG performance across industries and companies.

Data Collection & Reporting Issues

Inconsistent or incomplete ESG data across different departments and supply chains.
Challenges in tracking indirect environmental and social impacts.
Risk of "greenwashing" due to inaccurate or misleading ESG reporting.

Regulatory and Compliance Complexities

ESG regulations vary by country and industry, making compliance difficult.
Frequent updates to ESG laws require continuous adaptation.
Risk of legal liabilities for failing to meet ESG disclosure requirements.

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High Implementation Costs

Initial investments in sustainable infrastructure, renewable energy, or ethical sourcing can be costly.

ESG compliance often requires hiring experts, consultants, and third-party auditors.

Smaller companies may struggle with the financial burden of ESG initiatives.

Greenwashing & Credibility Risks

Companies may exaggerate ESG efforts to appeal to stakeholders.

Increased scrutiny from regulators, investors, and consumers can lead to reputational damage.

Lack of third-party verification may reduce trust in ESG claims.

Balancing ESG with Profitability

Striking a balance between sustainability and financial performance can be challenging.

Short-term financial pressures may discourage long-term ESG investments.

Investors may be skeptical about the financial returns of ESG initiatives.

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EU's role in ESG leads global efforts in **integrating ESG principles into financing**. Through initiatives like the European Green Deal, the EU aims to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050.

To increase transparency, EU law compels large and listed companies (excluding micro-enterprises) to publicly disclose their social and environmental risks, opportunities, and effects.

ESG Regulations & Directives

Regulatory measures ensure consistent ESG compliance:
Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) (2023)
Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR) (2021)
EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities (2020)

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EU's role in ESG leads global efforts in **integrating ESG principles into financing**. Through initiatives like the European Green Deal, the EU aims to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050.

EU Green Deal & Climate Goals

The EU's Green Deal is its blueprint for making Europe climate-neutral by 2050. Targets 55% emissions reduction by 2030 (Fit for 55 package). Introduces Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) to tax high-carbon imports. Invests in renewable energy, circular economy, and biodiversity initiatives.

Sustainable Finance & Investment

The EU is driving sustainable finance to support ESG-aligned investments. EU Green Bonds Standard (EUGBS): A framework for credible green investments. European Investment Bank (EIB): Funds green projects under the EU Green Deal. Social Impact Investing: Focuses on ESG-conscious businesses and funds.

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ESG in Romania: Trends, Regulations, and Challenges

Romanian businesses are undergoing a significant change with the introduction of the [Order of the Ministry of Finance \(OMF\) 85/2024](#), which aligns with the [EU's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive \(CSRD\)](#) and [demands comprehensive ESG reporting](#), impacting investment and reputation

The phased obligations are linked to company size, public interest status and employee thresholds.

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ESG in Romania: Trends, Regulations, and Challenges

Beginning 1 January 2024 (financial year 2024, reporting in 2025):

- Public Interest Entities with over 500 employees and meeting the large/medium entity criteria
- Public-Interest Entities that are parent companies of a large group, with an average of over 500 employees on a consolidated basis during the financial year.

Beginning 1 January 2025 (financial year 2025, reporting in 2026):

- Medium and large-sized entities that are not Public Interest Entities.
- Parent companies of large groups that are not Public Interest Entities.

Beginning 1 January 2026 (financial year 2026, reporting in 2027):

- Entities listed on regulated markets that do not meet the size criteria for sustainability reporting for 2024 and 2025

Beginning 1 January 2028 (financial year 2028, reporting in 2029):

- Romanian branches or subsidiaries whose ultimate parent companies are governed by the laws of a third country, subject to specific size criteria

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ESG in Romania: Trends, Regulations, and Challenges

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ESG in Romania: Trends, Regulations, and Challenges

Challenges

- Many companies struggle with ESG reporting and compliance due to a lack of knowledge and resources
- Transitioning to sustainable business models requires significant financial investments
- Companies must navigate rapidly evolving EU ESG regulations and adapt to new disclosure standards

Future opportunities

- Romania can leverage EU sustainability funds to accelerate its green transition
- Businesses adopting AI-driven ESG analytics and blockchain for supply chain transparency will gain a competitive edge
- The banking sector is expanding green loans and ESG-linked bonds, creating opportunities for sustainable investments

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Benefits of ESG

For investors

- **Better Risk-Adjusted Returns:** ESG factors can provide valuable insights into a company's long-term sustainability and risk profile, helping investors make more informed decisions and potentially achieve better risk-adjusted returns.
- **Positive Impact:** ESG investing allows investors to align their financial goals with their values, supporting companies that are making a positive impact on the environment and society.
- **Growing Market:** The market for ESG investments is rapidly growing, providing investors with a wider range of opportunities to invest in sustainable and responsible companies.

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For businesses

- **Improved Financial Performance:** Studies suggest that companies with strong ESG performance often have better financial results, including higher profitability and lower cost of capital.
- **Enhanced Reputation and Brand Value:** A commitment to ESG can enhance a company's reputation and brand image, attracting customers, employees, and investors who value sustainability and ethical practices.
- **Reduced Risk:** ESG factors can help identify and mitigate potential risks, such as environmental liabilities, social conflicts, and governance issues, leading to greater resilience and long-term stability.
- **Increased Innovation:** Focusing on ESG can drive innovation in products, services, and processes, leading to new market opportunities and competitive advantages.
- **Stronger Stakeholder Relationships:** Engaging with stakeholders on ESG issues can build trust and strengthen relationships with employees, customers, suppliers, and communities.
- **Attracting and Retaining Talent:** Many employees, especially younger generations, are increasingly interested in working for companies with strong ESG performance. A commitment to ESG can help attract and retain top talent.

For the world

- **Sustainable Development:** ESG promotes sustainable development by encouraging businesses to consider their impact on the environment and society.
- **Addressing Global Challenges:** ESG can help address pressing global challenges, such as climate change, social inequality, and environmental degradation.
- **Increased Transparency:** ESG reporting and disclosure can increase transparency and accountability, helping to ensure that companies are operating in a responsible and ethical manner.

Case studies

1. Embracing a greener footprint **Company: Unilever**

Task: Unilever, with its broad global presence, had to confront the significant environmental impact of its operations, seeking ways to innovate and reduce that impact while continuing to grow

Solution: Unilever introduced the "Unilever Sustainable Living Plan" in 2010 - a holistic strategy, designed to unite profitability and sustainability through initiatives focused on waste, sourcing, and carbon emissions

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Case studies

1. Embracing a greener footprint **Company: Unilever**

Overall Impact:

- Reduced carbon footprint by 64% in operations.
- 50% of raw materials sustainably sourced, including 100% sustainable tea & palm oil.
- Over 1.3 billion people benefited from health and hygiene programs.

Key takeaways:

- Set clear, measurable ESG goals aligned with business objectives
- Engage stakeholders (employees, suppliers, and customers) in sustainability efforts
- Use technology (AI, blockchain) for ESG data tracking and transparency
- Adopt a circular economy approach, prioritizing sustainable sourcing & waste reduction

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Case studies

2. Reducing Plastic in the Beverage Industry **Company: Coca-Cola**

Task: Coca-Cola aimed to balance environmental responsibility with product quality and consumer satisfaction by innovating its packaging to minimize plastic waste.

Solution: Coca-Cola launched the “World Without Waste” initiative, which aims to collect and recycle the equivalent of every bottle or can it sell by 2030.

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Case studies

2. Reducing Plastic in the Beverage Industry [Company: Coca-Cola](#)

Overall Impact:

- 60% of packaging is recyclable globally, with 100% collection goals by 2030.
- Replenished 100% of the water used in its beverages since 2015.
- Reduced carbon emissions by more than 30% in bottling operations.

Key takeaways:

- Set measurable sustainability goals with clear timelines
- Use innovative packaging solutions to reduce waste
- Prioritize water stewardship and conservation efforts
- Invest in social impact programs that empower communities

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Case studies

3. Setting the Gold Standard in Green Tech **Company: Google**

Task: Google, a tech giant, faced the challenge of reducing the massive energy consumption and environmental impact of its global data centers.

Solution: To address its energy impact, Google invested in renewable energy and partnered with green power producers.

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Case studies

3. Setting the Gold Standard in Green Tech [Company: Google](#)

Overall Impact:

- 100% renewable energy match since 2017, making Google the largest corporate buyer of renewable energy.
- 50% improvement in AI-driven energy efficiency in data centers.
- Google Maps AI has helped reduce 1 million metric tons of CO₂ emissions from vehicle routes

Key takeaways:

- Set ambitious, science-based sustainability goals
- Use AI and technology to enhance ESG performance and efficiency
- Prioritize responsible AI governance and data privacy
- Invest in community impact, digital inclusion, and workplace equity

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Case studies

4. Banking on a Greener Tomorrow **Company: HSBC**

Task: HSBC, understanding its massive financial impact, aimed to balance profit with environmental responsibility.

Solution: HSBC's Green Bond Program aimed to drive real environmental change by investing \$100 billion in projects with measurable positive impacts by 2025.

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Case studies

4. Banking on a Greener Tomorrow [Company: HSBC](#)

Overall Impact:

- Reduced operational carbon footprint by 41% since 2019.
- Issued over \$12 billion in green bonds to support eco-friendly projects.

Key takeaways:

- Integrate ESG into core business strategy & financial products
- Align investments with sustainability goals and climate action
- Promote financial inclusion through targeted social programs
- Ensure ESG transparency with robust reporting frameworks

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Future of ESG

Stricter ESG Regulations & Compliance

- **Mandatory ESG disclosures** are replacing voluntary ones, driven by global regulators
 - EU: EU's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) mandates comprehensive ESG reporting for companies, including environmental and social factors
 - USA: the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) is pushing for greater ESG transparency in the U.S., with new rules targeting climate and board diversity reporting
 - Asia: Driven by the global push for ESG transparency, countries from the Asia-Pacific are implementing their own reporting standards
- **Companies will require substantial ESG service investments** to meet regulations and remain ahead of their competition

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Future of ESG

Integration of ESG into Business Strategy

- **Sustainable Innovation:** businesses are embedding sustainability throughout their operations, from product design to supply chain
- **ESG Metrics in Executive Compensation:** by linking executive compensation to ESG, businesses are making leadership responsible for their sustainability impact
- **ESG in Mergers and Acquisitions (M&A):** ESG performance is a significant driver in M&A transactions, affecting both company valuation and due diligence processes

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Future of ESG

The Growing Importance of Social and Governance Factors

- **Diversity and Inclusion:** companies must prioritize diversity and inclusion at all levels, from hiring to leadership.
- **Human Rights and Labor Practices:** companies face rising pressure for clear and responsible labor and human rights practices, especially in their supply chains.
- **Corporate Governance:** to effectively address ESG, companies must have solid governance, including independent boards and fair compensation

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Future of ESG

The Role of Technology in ESG

- **Data Analytics and AI:** AI and advanced analytics are powering smarter ESG decisions by revealing trends and risks
- **Blockchain for Supply Chain Transparency:** blockchain helps verify ethical and sustainable product sourcing
- **Digital Platforms for Stakeholder Engagement:** digital platforms facilitate two-way communication between companies and stakeholders on ESG matters.

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Future of ESG

The Increasing Influence of ESG Investors

- **ESG Funds and Indexes:** investors have a widening array of ESG funds and indexes to choose from, reflecting the rising popularity of sustainable investments
- **Shareholder Activism:** investors are actively pressuring companies for better ESG performance through voting, resolutions, and direct engagement
- **Impact Investing:** there is a growing trend of investors seeking companies that produce both financial returns and measurable positive social or environmental impact.

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Future of ESG

The future of environmental, social and governance (ESG) is evolving rapidly, driven by [stricter regulation](#), [technological advances](#) and changing investor and consumer [expectations](#).

Companies that adapt will gain [competitive advantage](#), while those that ignore ESG risks may face [financial and reputational consequences](#).

ESG is evolving from a trend to a [foundational business principle](#), reshaping how companies operate and build value.

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Conclusions

ESG is no longer just a trend — it is a fundamental **component of sustainable economic growth and responsible investment**

By integrating **environmental, social, and governance** criteria into financing decisions, businesses and investors align with global sustainability goals while fostering economic and social progress

Although challenges like data availability and greenwashing persist, advancements in **technology, regulation, and transparency** are paving the way for more effective ESG adoption

ESG is not only about addressing **global challenges** but also about creating **opportunities for innovation, profitability, and long-term resilience**. It stands as a cornerstone for building a better, **more sustainable future**.

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

AFCOS

Topic 5: GREEN FINANCING

Module 3 “Green & Digital Transition”

Course “Specific rules for standardization of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope”

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AGENDA

Introduction to green financing

Principles of green financing

Types of green financing

Benefits of green financing

Case studies

Conclusions

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Introduction to Green Financing

Green financing encompasses any **financial activity** that supports **environmental sustainability**.

This includes **investments, loans, and bonds** that contribute to a healthier planet, a more stable climate, and reduced environmental risks, all while providing financial gains for those who invest.

<https://www.unep.org/>

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Green finance addresses the challenges of climate change by building a **sustainable and resilient economy** and facilitating the transition to low-carbon activities.

Green finance initiatives include:

- Renewable energy and energy efficiency
- Pollution prevention and control
- Biodiversity conservation
- Circular economy initiatives
- Sustainable use of natural resources and land

Two main goals of green finance:

- **to internalize environmental externalities**
- **reduce risk perceptions**

Expanding green finance in a way that's both profitable and widespread is essential to breaking away from unsustainable growth patterns.

Green finance **promotes transparent and long-term investment strategies** that support **environmental goals** and align with the **UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**.

ESG and Green financing

Green finance is among several terms describing the interplay between **environmental** concerns and **financial** activities

Green finance is closely linked to related concepts like **climate finance** and **sustainable finance**.

Sustainable finance

- includes environmental, social, governance and economic aspects (**ESG**)

Green finance

- includes climate finance but excludes social and economic aspects

Climate finance

- is a subset of environmental (green) finance

Aspect	ESG	Green Financing
Focus	Environmental, Social, and Governance criteria used to assess sustainability.	Investment in projects that have a positive environmental impact
Key Areas	Environmental: Climate change, resource use, pollution control.	Green bonds, green loans, and other financial products for eco-friendly projects.
	Social: Labor rights, community impact.	
	Governance: Ethical management, transparency.	
Purpose	To evaluate the sustainability of a company or investment based on all ESG factors.	To provide funds for projects with clear environmental benefits.
Environmental Criteria	Assess a company's environmental impact (carbon footprint, waste management, etc.).	Focuses on funding environmentally sustainable projects like clean energy, pollution reduction, etc.
Governance Impact	Strong governance ensures accountability in ESG practices.	Green projects are often more effective when backed by strong governance structures.
Investor Demand	Investors are increasingly prioritizing companies with strong ESG performance.	Green financing products meet the growing demand for sustainable, environmentally conscious investments.
Regulatory Context	Growing regulations around ESG disclosures, e.g., EU Taxonomy.	Regulations often mandate that green financing projects meet environmental standards.

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EU Taxonomy

The EU's 2019 **Green Deal** aims for a **climate-neutral economy by 2050** (55% reduction by 2030) via sustainable investments (e.g., renewables, biodiversity, circular economy).

A €1 trillion, 10-year investment plan is in place, but private sector support is also essential for achieving Paris Agreement goals.

The **EU Taxonomy** and the **Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR)** create a level playing field and provide legal clarity for businesses operating in the EU.

These regulations, aligned with the Green Deal, aim to:

- Shift capital towards sustainable investments.
- Integrate sustainability into risk management.
- Foster long-term sustainable investment and economic activity.

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Taxonomy Regulation sets out 6 climate and environmental objectives

The EU taxonomy regulation describes a framework to classify “green” or “sustainable” economic activities executed in the EU

The EU taxonomy regulation creates a clear framework for the concept of sustainability, exactly defining when a company or enterprise is operating sustainably or environmentally friendly.

The legislation aims to reward and promote environmentally friendly business practices and technologies

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An economic activity's sustainability classification depends on these 4 criteria, which are based on the environmental objectives mentioned earlier:

The economic activity contributes to one of the six environmental objectives
The economic activity does ' no significant harm ' (DNSH) to any of the six environmental objectives
The economic activity meets ' minimum safeguards ' such as the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights to not have a negative social impact
The economic activity complies with the technical screening criteria developed by the EU Technical Expert Group

The economic activity **contributes** to one of the six environmental objectives

The economic activity does '**no significant harm**' (DNSH) to any of the six environmental objectives

The economic activity meets '**minimum safeguards**' such as the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights to not have a negative social impact

The economic activity **complies** with the technical screening criteria developed by the EU Technical Expert Group

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Impact of EU Taxonomy on different stakeholders

Businesses

- Provides clear criteria for sustainable activities, helping businesses meet the increasing demand for eco-friendly practices.
- By using the taxonomy, companies can showcase their environmental commitment, potentially unlocking green financing and boosting investor confidence.

Investors

- Helps investors assess the environmental impact of their investments, guiding capital towards environmentally beneficial projects and companies.
- This is crucial as institutional investors are increasingly expected to make their portfolios more sustainable.

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Impact of EU Taxonomy on different stakeholders

Regulators and policymakers

- Helps regulators shape policies and align incentives with sustainability goals. It also boosts transparency, enabling policymakers to monitor the EU's progress toward its sustainability targets.

Consumers

- Empowers consumers to make eco-conscious choices by clarifying the environmental impact of products and services.
- By increasing market transparency, it enables consumers to more easily support sustainable businesses.

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Principles of green financing

Environmental Sustainability

Investments should contribute to environmental objectives, such as reducing carbon emissions, promoting renewable energy, or enhancing biodiversity.

Impact Measurement

Projects financed through green finance should have measurable environmental benefits, such as reduced greenhouse gas emissions or improved energy efficiency.

Alignment with Sustainability Goals

Green investments should align with broader sustainability goals, such as the UN (SDGs) and national or regional environmental strategies.

Innovation and Green Technology Promotion

Encouraging investment in green innovations, such as clean energy, sustainable agriculture, and eco-friendly infrastructure.

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Principles of green financing

Risk Management

Identifying and mitigating environmental and climate risks in financial decisions to promote long-term sustainability.

Inclusivity and Social Responsibility

Green finance should consider the social impact of investments, ensuring benefits reach all stakeholders, including marginalized communities.

Regulatory Compliance

Adherence to international and national environmental policies, standards, and frameworks such as the Paris Agreement or the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities.

Transparency and Disclosure

Clear reporting and disclosure of how funds are used ensure accountability and prevent greenwashing.

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Principles of green financing

These principles provide a framework for ensuring that **green finance** genuinely supports the **transition to a sustainable and low-carbon economy**.

They help to **guide investors, businesses, and policymakers** in making informed decisions that **benefit both the environment and the economy**.

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The UN Environment is guiding financial markets to fund projects that build a sustainable future, as today's investments determine tomorrow's world

The main areas for the current work on green financing are:

- Supporting public sector on creating enabling environment
- Promoting public-private partnerships on financing mechanisms such as green bonds
- Capacity building of community enterprises on micro-credit

<https://www.unep.org/>

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Process of *green financing*

Project Identification

A project must meet specific environmental and sustainability criteria, such as reducing carbon emissions or promoting clean energy.

Common sectors include renewable energy, energy-efficient buildings, climate adaptation projects, and sustainable agriculture.

Funding Selection

Based on project size, risk level, and expected impact, the project owner chooses an appropriate funding source.

Assessment

Investors and financial institutions evaluate the project's environmental impact, financial feasibility, and alignment with green finance principles.

Certifications such as LEED, BREEAM, or the Green Loan Principles may be required.

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Fund Allocation and Monitoring

Once financing is secured, funds must be used strictly for green projects.

Regular reporting and impact measurement ensure transparency and accountability.

Impact Measurement and Reporting

Investors and regulators require reports on environmental benefits, such as CO₂ reduction, energy savings, or waste reduction.

This prevents "greenwashing" (false claims of sustainability).

Types of green financing

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Green Bonds

- Debt instruments issued to finance projects with environmental benefits, such as renewable energy, clean transportation, and climate adaptation.
- Examples: Green bonds issued by governments, corporations, and international organizations like the World Bank.

Green Loans

- Loans provided specifically for projects that promote sustainability, such as energy-efficient buildings or waste management initiatives.
- Can be structured similarly to traditional loans but with environmental criteria.

Green Insurance

- Encourages sustainable practices by offering lower premiums to environmentally friendly businesses and consumers.
- Global financial institutions are increasingly prioritizing sustainability-linked insurance

Green Grants

- Provided by governments, philanthropic organizations, private foundations, and environmental NGOs, also support research on climate change and sustainable development at universities and research facilities.
- At a larger scale, the UN's Green Climate Fund, established in 2010, prioritizing grants for the most vulnerable nations, including least developed countries, small island developing states, and African nations.

Crowdfunding

- Allows businesses or individuals to raise funds directly from a large number of people, each contributing a small amount, bypassing traditional financial institutions.
- Is unstable and vulnerable to economic shock

Green Venture Capital

- Finance projects and companies that are developing sustainable technologies to ensure environmental conservation and combating climate change
- It provides vital capital to sectors like energy, waste management, and mobility, enabling the development of cleaner technologies

Carbon Credits and Carbon Offset

- One carbon credit permits a company to emit one ton of carbon dioxide. Polluting companies receive a limited number of these credits, and this cap decreases annually, pushing them toward greener practices.
- This market incentivizes companies to sell surplus credits for revenue, which can then be reinvested in developing sustainable technologies.
- While often used interchangeably, carbon offsets and carbon credits have distinct roles.
 - ***Carbon credit*** represents the right to emit one tonne of CO₂ and is a tradeable permit. These credits are issued when an activity removes, avoids, or reduces one tonne of CO₂ emissions.
 - ***Carbon offsets***, on the other hand, are a mechanism by which companies or individuals compensate for their emissions by supporting projects that reduce emissions elsewhere. Both credits and offsets are traded on the carbon market. Credits can be created by governments or awarded for verified emission reductions.

Benefits of green financing

Environmental

- ***Reduces Carbon Emissions*** – Investments in renewable energy and energy efficiency help lower GHG emissions.
- ***Encourages Sustainable Resource Use*** – Supports projects that promote water conservation, waste management, and biodiversity protection.
- ***Mitigates Climate Change Risks*** – Helps finance climate adaptation measures, such as flood control and resilient infrastructure.

Economic

- ***Promotes Green Innovation*** – Encourages research and development of clean technologies and sustainable business models.
- ***Creates Green Jobs*** – Expands employment opportunities in renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, and eco-friendly industries.
- ***Enhances Long-term Economic Stability*** – Reduces dependence on fossil fuels and exposure to environmental risks.

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Benefits of green financing

Financial

- **Attracts Responsible Investors** – Increases access to capital from investors prioritizing sustainability and ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) factors.
- **Improves Financial Performance** – Many green investments, such as energy efficiency projects, result in cost savings and higher long-term returns.
- **Access to Incentives** – Governments often provide a benefits, subsidies, and grants for green projects.

Social

- **Enhances Public Health** – Reduces pollution and promotes cleaner energy sources, improving air and water quality.
- **Supports Sustainable Development** – Helps developing nations finance essential infrastructure while protecting the environment.
- **Increases Community Resilience** – Funds adaptation strategies that protect vulnerable communities from climate-related disasters.

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Benefits of green financing

Regulatory and Corporate Benefits

- ***Ensures Compliance with Regulations*** – Helps businesses and financial institutions align with environmental laws and international agreements (e.g., the Paris Agreement).
- ***Reduces Climate-Related Financial Risks*** – Protects companies and investors from losses due to environmental regulations, resource depletion, and climate impacts.
- ***Enhances Brand Reputation*** – Companies that adopt green financing practices are viewed as socially responsible, attracting environmentally conscious consumers and stakeholders.

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Advantages for the Bank

Enhanced Reputation

Supporting green projects boosts the bank's image as a socially responsible institution.

It demonstrates the bank's commitment to environmental sustainability and aligns with societal expectations for corporate responsibility.

Customer Base Expansion

Attracts environmentally conscious clients and businesses, fostering long-term relationships.

These customers are more likely to seek additional green financial products and services.

Regulatory Compliance

Aligns with global and local sustainability regulations, avoiding penalties.

Green financing initiatives help meet obligations under frameworks like the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities.

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Advantages for the Bank

Financial Returns

Green loans and bonds often attract lower risk due to the stability of sustainable projects, ensuring steady returns over time.

They also offer opportunities for premium pricing due to growing demand.

Innovation Opportunities

Green financing enables the bank to diversify its product offerings and innovate in the financial sector.

This fosters a competitive edge and positions the bank as a leader in sustainable finance.

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Advantages for the Investor

Higher Returns

Green investments often lead to long-term financial benefits through stable and growing returns driven by demand for sustainable products and services.

Portfolio Diversification

Adds sustainable assets to the investment portfolio, reducing portfolio risk and enhancing resilience to market volatility.

Tax Incentives

Many governments offer tax breaks for green investments, increasing the overall profitability of such ventures.

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Advantages for the Investor

Increased Demand

The growing market for green assets increases their value over time, offering opportunities for capital appreciation.

Access to New Markets

Green investments open doors to emerging sectors like renewable energy and sustainable infrastructure, providing first-mover advantages.

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Advantages for the Beneficiary

Lower Costs

Access to reduced interest rates and better loan terms lowers financial barriers to adopting green technologies or sustainable practices.

Improved Efficiency

Green projects often lead to lower operational costs due to energy efficiency and reduced waste, enhancing profitability.

Enhanced Value

Sustainable buildings or businesses often have higher resale values and greater attractiveness to eco-conscious buyers.

Market Competitiveness

Green certification improves reputation and attracts customers who prioritize environmental sustainability, boosting brand loyalty.

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Case studies

1. European Investment Bank (EIB) – Green Bonds Initiative

EU, launched in 2007

Description:

EIB was the first institution to issue **Green Bonds**, also known as Climate Awareness Bonds (CABs)

The funds are used to finance projects related to **renewable energy**, **energy efficiency**, and **climate adaptation**

As of 2023, EIB has issued over €50 billion in green bonds

Impact:

Financed **solar and wind energy projects** across EU countries

Supported **energy efficiency** improvements in buildings

Encouraged private and public institutions to **invest in green bonds**

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Case studies

2. EU's Green Deal Investment Plan & Just Transition Mechanism

EU, 2020-present

Description:

The European Green Deal Investment Plan (EGDIP) aims to mobilize €1 trillion for **sustainable investments** by 2030

The Just Transition Mechanism (JTM) supports regions most affected by the transition to a **green economy** (e.g., coal-dependent regions)

Funding comes from the EU budget, private sector, and European Investment Bank (EIB)

Impact:

Supports industries in **shifting to low-carbon models**

Helps regions **transition away from fossil fuel dependence**

Funds research and innovation in **sustainable technologies**

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Case studies

3. European Investment Bank (EIB) - Green Financing for Romania

Romania, since 2018

Description:

EIB has provided over €1 billion in green financing for Romanian projects

Key sectors include **renewable energy, climate resilience, water infrastructure, and eco-friendly transportation**

Notable projects funded include:

Expansion of **wind and solar farms in Romania**

Investments in **modernizing public transport, including electric buses**

Upgrading **water treatment and waste management facilities**

Impact:

Increased Romania's **renewable energy capacity**, reducing reliance on coal and natural gas.

Improved **urban air quality** by financing **electric and hybrid public transport**.

Enhanced climate resilience in flood-prone areas through **better water management**.

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Case studies

4. Green Mortgage Program - the Romanian Green Building Council (RoGBC)

Romania, since 2012

Description:

RoGBC launched a **Green Mortgage Program** in partnership with **banks** to offer **lower interest rates** for homebuyers purchasing **certified green buildings**

This program offers **preferential terms** and **interest rates** for green homes and apartments, encouraging developers to **invest in green solutions**, while homeowners **benefit from healthier, higher quality homes and lower monthly costs**

The following **mortgage products** dedicated to **Green Homes certified by RoGBC projects** are available in Romania: Casa Ta Verde (Raiffeisen Bank), Alpha Green (Alpha Bank), Casa Mea NaturA, (Banca Comercială Română), Verde Credit (Libra Bank), Vista Green Home (Vista Bank), Casa Eco (Garanti BBVA), RoGBC certified Green Loan (Banca Transilvania), Habitat Green (BRD Groupe Societe Generale)

Impact:

Increased demand for **sustainable housing**, pushing developers to adopt **green construction standards**

Encouraged **banks** to **integrate green finance products** into their portfolios.

Homebuyers benefited from **lower energy costs** due to **energy-efficient designs**

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Challenges in Green Financing

High Initial Costs – Green projects often require significant upfront investment.

Regulatory Barriers – Lack of standardized definitions and policies can create confusion.

Greenwashing Risks – Some companies falsely claim sustainability benefits to attract funding.

Limited Awareness and Accessibility – Many businesses and individuals are unaware of available green financing options.

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Conclusions

Green financing faces challenges such as ensuring projects meet genuine **sustainability** standards and overcoming high initial costs for green technologies.

However, it also creates **opportunities** for **economic growth**, stimulates **innovation** in **sustainable** industries, and generates jobs in **renewable energy** and construction sectors

As a cornerstone of the EU's sustainability strategy, green financing plays a vital role in **transitioning to a greener**, more **resilient economy** while addressing **climate change**.

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For more information:

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

AFCOS

Topic 1: Technological features of innovative building products

Module 4 “How to standardize innovative products “low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products” and “bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope””

Course “Specific rules for standardization of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope”

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CONTENTS

Low carbon cement and low carbon cement based products

Low carbon cement AFCOS study

Bio-based products for insulation of the buildings' envelope

Bio-based products for insulation of the buildings' envelope-AFCOS study

AFCOS interest in two types of products:

Low carbon cement and low carbon cement based products

Bio-based products for insulation of the buildings' envelope

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Cement problems

No alternative for cement in many areas

3% global growth in 2023

in 1990 emissions of 783 kg CO₂/ t of cement which need to be reduced to 0 in 2050 (the situation was in 2017 was 667 kg CO₂/ t of cement). The reduction is based on clinker (decarbonated raw materials, alternative fuels, thermal efficiency, low-carbon clinker, and hydrogen and electrification), cement (clinker substitution, electrical efficiency and renewable electricity, carbon neutral transport), concrete (concrete mix, carbon neutral transport) and construction carbonation (concrete in use and CO₂ capture in build environment).

Carbon dioxide emissions from the manufacture of cement worldwide from 1960 to 2022 (in million metric tons)

Sources

Global Carbon Project; Expert(s) (Friedlingstein et al. (2023), Andrew and Peters (2023).) © Statista 2024

Additional Information:

Worldwide; Global Carbon Project; Expert(s) (Friedlingstein et al. (2023), Andrew and Peters (2023).)

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Cement decarbonisation in Europe

Since 2021, the European Union invested more than € 1.1 billion into 7 large-scale innovative projects under the Innovation Fund. The seven projects were selected for funding under the first Innovation Fund call for large-scale projects from 311 applications. Four large-scale projects were selected from the cement industry, that include the Go4EcoPlanet project of Lafarge Cement (Holcim Group) in Kujawy/Poland, the ANRAV project of Devnya Cement (Heidelberg Materials Group) in Devnya/Bulgaria, the Carbon2Business projects of Holcim in Lägerdorf/Germany and the K6 project by Eqiom (CRH Group) in Lumbres/France.

In 2022, the EU Innovation Fund granted more than € 3.6 billion to 41 large-scale clean-tech projects out of a pool of 239 applications, with 5 projects focused on decarbonizing cement. A number of other full-scale carbon capture, utilisation and storage (CCUS) projects have been announced by the cement industry in Europe. In total there are 15 full-scale projects (incl. full-scale demonstration projects) in the EU, comprising a carbon reduction potential of about 10.8 Mt CO₂ per year by the cement producers Cemex, Eqiom (CRH), Heidelberg Materials, Holcim, Rohrdorfer Cement, Titan and Vicat. The 15 plants comprise a clinker production capacity of 15.1 Mt/a, which corresponds to about 10.3% of the EU capacity.

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CEMBUREAU

The European Cement Association is based in Brussels and is the representative organisation of the cement industry in Europe. Currently, its Full Members are 23 national cement industry associations and cement companies of the European Union (except for Malta) plus Norway, Switzerland and the United Kingdom. Croatia, Serbia and Slovakia are Associate Members of CEMBUREAU. Cooperation agreements have been concluded with Vassiliko Cement in Cyprus and UKRCEMENT in Ukraine.

The Association acts as spokesperson for the cement industry before the EU institutions and other public authorities, and communicates the industry's views on all issues and policy developments regarding technical, environmental, energy, employee health and safety and sustainability issues. In addition to the EU, permanent dialogue is maintained with other international organisations (e.g. OECD, IEA), the Global Cement and Concrete Association (GCCA) and sister associations in other parts of the world.

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CEMBUREAU – updated Net Zero Roadmap

the roadmap projects a 37% reduction in CO₂ emissions related to cement production, and 50% down the value chain.

the roadmap projects carbon neutral cement production in Europe, and looks at the potential to become carbon negative over the value chain.

a 78% reduction on cement, and 93% down the value chain.

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Cement industry in Romania

Cement industry in Bulgaria

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Low carbon cement and low carbon cement based products – AFCOS study

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In which areas do you feel there will be more technological improvements in the near future?

In which areas do you feel there are more needs to improve the existing standards or add new ones?

● Cement
 ● Concrete
 ● Prefabricate concrete products
 ● Mortar
 ● Grout
 ● All other products and applications related to built environment (including mining)

● Cement
 ● Concrete
 ● Prefabricate concrete products
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In which sectors did you face barriers preventing the growth of innovations?

Which was the main limitation factor?

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Action	Nr. Answers
Increase using different energy sources (non-fossil fuels) for cement production	17
Using alternative binders whenever possible (alternative to clinker / Portland cement)	17
Carbon capture and utilization (CCU, that is capturing CO ₂ emissions and converting them into useful products)	17
Using renewable energy in cement (and concrete) production	16
Improving energy efficiency in cement plants (or excess heat second use)	16
Increase use of supplementary cementitious materials	15
CO ₂ sequestration at the cement plant chimneys and subsequent carbon storage (CCS, including using excess heat to CO ₂ treatment)	12
Re-carbonization of cement components or concrete components (not releasing CO ₂)	9
Lowering the temperature for cement production for newly designed cements	9

What are the main barriers presented by today's European cement (EN197 series) and concrete standards (EN206) to successfully tackle the embodied carbon of concrete? (If you think that the best strategy is a combination of the following, please indicate all of them)

- Prescriptive approach of concrete standards, referring to issues with use of novel constituents, minimum cement content, water/cement ratios...
- Prescriptive approach of cement standards, limiting the use of supplementary cementitious materials and novel cements.
- Perceived lack of harmonisation of concrete standards on national level.
- Lack of attention for potential of CO2 storage in concrete products.
- Other entries

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Main problems - AFCOS study

Demand side/market problems: unfavorable price to value and need for a life cycle and embodied carbon approach

Limitations with allowed components in cement and concrete (admixtures, alternative binders, ...)

Limitations related to a still partly prescriptive rather than fully performance-based approach in standards

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Bio-based products for insulation of the buildings' envelope – types of material

Thermal insulation materials

Inorganic mineral derived

- Stone wool*
- Glass wool* (fibreglass)
- Slag wool
- Cellular glass
- Aerated glass
- Vermiculite
- Expanded clay pellets

Organic fossil fuel derived

- Polyurethane (PU)*
- Expanded polystyrene (EPS)*
- Extruded polystyrene (XPS)*
- Polyisocyanurate (PIR)*
- Phenolic foam

Organic plant / animal derived

- Woodfibre
- Cork
- Sheep's wool
- Cotton
- Hemp
- Flax
- Compressed straw

Innovative materials

- Biopolymers
- Nanocoatings
- Aerogels
- Vacuum insulation panels
- Nanocellular foam
- Phase change materials
- Advanced insulation foams

* The most common types

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Thermal insulation market

The thermal insulation market in Europe is 11.21 billion Euro with a cumulative average growth of 8.1%

- 1 By Applications:**
- Roof insulation
 - Wall Insulation
 - Floor Insulation

- 2 By Material:**
- Plastic Foam
 - Polystyrene Foam
 - Polyurethane (PUR) & Polyisocyanurate (PIR) Foam
 - Wool Insulation
 - Glass Wool
 - Stone Wool
 - Others

- 3 By Building Types:**
- Residential
 - Commercial
 - Industrial

- 4 By Countries:**
- Germany
 - Italy
 - France
 - United Kingdom
 - Rest of Europe

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Thermal insulation market in Romania

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Case study: Wool

Considered waste

Raw wool classified as waste by the EU since 2019
Legislation imposes costly disposal requirements

Lacking recycling infrastructure

Currently wool is incinerated, dumped or sent to landfills

Impact on farmers

Subsidies elimination exacerbates operational difficulties
Decline in wool demand for the textile industry

Green aspects

High energy-price sensitivity in current alternatives

Upcycling

Turning sheep wool from waste into zero-carbon wool insulation, lanolin, and organic fertilizers

Change the industry

Redesigning wool washing and carding technologies to produce financially optimized wool products at scale.

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How much do you expect that BUSINESS will increase in next 10 years?

How much do you expect that TECHNOLOGICAL IMPROVEMENTS will affect the market in next 10 years?

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In which area do you feel there will be more technological improvements in the near future?

In which area do you feel there are more needs to improve the existing standards or add new ones?

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In which sectors did you face barriers preventing the growth of innovations?

Which was the main limitation factor?

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Topic 2: Barriers for innovative construction products

Module 4 “How to standardize innovative products “low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products” and “bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope””

Course “Specific rules for standardization of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope”

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CONTENTS

Cement

Concrete

Bio-based insulation products

Bulgarian stakeholders identified the following challenges in relation to the standardization of low-carbon cement

- Lack of sufficient awareness and preparation on behalf of the participants in the construction process.
- Lack of a technical basis to produce concrete in accordance with the new requirements (lack of a sufficient number of silos at the concrete producers).
- The higher price of low-carbon concrete compared to the concrete produced with ordinary Portland cement and fly ash.
- The lack of synchronization in the legislative framework (Public Procurement Law, etc.).
- The lack of state incentives at the national level that encourage the application of ecological construction products.
- The lack of constant control throughout the construction process for the implementation of the new requirements.
- To research what additives are used in innovative concretes.
- Need to test new construction products, to assess their quality and inform the stakeholders that new construction products have the required quality.

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Bulgarian stakeholders identified the following challenges in relation to the standardization of low-carbon cement

- Need to include ecological requirements for the new construction products in the Public Procurement Act.
- Necessity of including low-carbon cements in standard EN 206 in Bulgarian National Annex.
- Trainings under the project should be aimed at all participants in the construction process, as well as at conformity assessors, assessors of construction products, bodies developing BTO, as well as at manufacturers of dry mixes
- Proposal to the EC - clarification of the term "Environmental construction product", which are the main indicators defining the product as ecological
- Proposal as an additional project activity to make a CWA simulation in the form of a working group including experts also from the EC.

However, related to this topic, the Bulgarian Association of the Cement Industry (BACI) identifies the problem of a lacking awareness among the stakeholders about the quality and price of new construction products. According to BACI low-carbon cements will not be more expensive than Portland cement, because the additives are not more expensive than the clinker that is used now. On this topic, BACI underlines the need to inform the participants in the construction process about these aspects.

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CEMENT

BARRIER		OBJECTIVE	
B-CE-1	Cement regulations are still too prescription-based, preventing the development of new cements	O-CE-1	Move towards a more performance-based approach in cement regulations
B-CE-2	Often modern cements cannot be CE marked because of harmonized standards are lacking	O-CE-2	CE mark modern cements (e.g. with reduced amount of clinker, with recycled material, ...)
B-CE-3	Currents standards limit the use of SCMs (supplementary cementitious materials)	O-CE-3	Increase use of SCMs (supplementary cementitious materials)
B-CE-4	Currents standards limit the use alternative hydraulic binders	O-CE-4	Using alternative hydraulic binders when possible (alternative to clinker / Portland cement)
B-CE-5	Current legislation does not encourage re-carbonization of cement components or concrete components	O-CE-5	Re-carbonization of cement components or concrete components (not releasing CO2)
B-CE-6	Current legislation does not encourage carbon captured + sequestered // captured + used	O-CE-6	Ensure appropriate recognition of carbon captured + sequestered // captured + used
B-CE-7	Current legislation does not encourage the use of more sustainable cements	O-CE-7	Inclusion of LCA impact categories in cement DOP as required, no NPD
B-CE-8	Current legislation does not encourage digitalization of product characteristics	O-CE-8	Alignment to Ecodesign regulation, which includes new Digital Product Passport

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CONCRETE

BARRIER		OBJECTIVE	
B-CO-1	Concrete regulations are still too prescription-based, preventing the development of new cements	O-CO-1	Move towards a more performance-based approach in concrete regulations
B-CO-2	Since concrete standards are not harmonized, national application standards exist, causing different rules in different EU countries	O-CO-2	Need to “harmonize” national application standards through EN 206
B-CO-3	Large variability of nationally applicable technical specifications complementary to EN 206, annex M	O-CO-3	Reduce variability by providing guidance and ranges to a limited number of indexes
B-CO-4	Promotion of low-impact concrete suffers the difficult interpretation of all LCA impact categories	O-CO-4	Summarize the evaluation of the environmental impact of concrete Promote and spread knowledge to increase market demand for concrete with declared environmental characteristics
B-CO-5	Current legislation does not encourage carbon capturing solutions	O-CO-5	Ensure proper use and transparency on carbon capturing solutions (CCS, CCU, re-carbonation of components at a production stage)
B-CO-6	General lack of availability of LCA-relevant information	O-CO-6	Ensure the availability of LCA information
B-CO-7	Current legislation does not encourage digitalization of product characteristics	O-CO-7	Alignment to Ecodesign regulation, which includes new Digital Product Passport

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Bio-based products for insulation - barriers

Among bio-based insulations products, only 3 hENs have been identified, referring to cork products, wood wool, and wood fibers.

All the other products categories lack of hENs. This complicates the procedures for manufacturers to prove their product conformity in order to apply CE marking. In this framework, the only possible way to CE mark is to use the EOTA path. However, at least from the point of view of Romanian stakeholders, this path is very difficult to follow for a small manufacturer due to the lack of proper budget and insufficient information. This is mainly due to the nature of the manufacturers of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings` envelope. In fact, at least at the Romanian level, manufacturers are small local entrepreneurs with limited resources and limited knowledge on standardization processes and policies.

Some ISO standards related to these products have been developed. However, these have been not transposed at the European level as EN, due to the lack of interest and consensus at the European level.

Another critical situation about this is related to the actual situation concerning major blocking of EN standards for OJEU citation. The ongoing revision of CPR 305/2011 will help solving this situation.

One more regulatory barrier related to these products concerns the permits needed to collect raw materials. For example, concerning the Posidonia-based products and for the specific case of Italy, collecting material on beaches requires a very complicated permitting process. Simplifying this could significantly help the growth of this market.

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Bio-based products for insulation – proposed actions

Related to the introduction of a CE marking process for bio-based products, another proposed action is related to the need to consider mandatory the introduction of sustainability parameters in the product DOPs. These should include for example:

- a parameter to measure the carbon footprint of the specific product;
- the recyclability of the product; this could help distinguishing between 100% bio-based products (which are fully recyclable) and products based on mixtures between bio-based materials and synthetic materials (which are not recyclable).

No specific preference has been given among the two approaches. However, considering the large variety of products belonging to the bio-based category, introducing a general hENs could significantly help the market entrance of new products not belonging to the listed ones.

Another need expressed by stakeholders is related to the need for a standard to define what is to be considered “bio-based”. At present there are no clear rules to define it. There is often confusion between what is truly “bio-based” and what is simply of “natural origin”.

The mostly shared action which could significantly improve the marketing of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope is to the introduction of hENs for the CE marking of the different products.

In this field, two different approaches have been identified:

- introduce hENs for each of the products mentioned above;
- introduce a general hENs valid for all the mentioned products.

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Topic 3: Understanding new standards: preparing construction stakeholders for evolving building product requirements. Role of national standardization bodies.

Module 4 “How to standardize innovative products “low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products” and “bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope””

Course “Specific rules for standardization of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope”

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EU Standardization process

European Standard EN

Process of standardization for EN standards

EU Standardization process

The standardization process within the European Union (EU) is a systematic approach aimed at developing, implementing, and maintaining standards across various sectors and industries. European standards (ENs) and standardization deliverables are developed by the three recognized standardization organizations: CEN (European Committee for Standardization), CENELEC (European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization) and ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute). In many cases, when possible and relevant, European standards are aligned with the international standards of ISO (International Organization for Standardization) and IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission).

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Process of standardization for EN standards

Identifying the need for a standard and submitting a proposal

Any interested party

Gathering opinions of stakeholders, evaluation and decision

Technical Committee

Developing a draft of the standard

Working group at the Technical Committee

Public enquiry - submitting opinions

Any interested party

Development of final draft and voting

Technical Committee

Adoption and publication

Standardization organization

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Needs and planning

Identification of needs

The process begins with identifying the areas where standardization is necessary and submitting a proposal for standard development. This could be driven by technological advancements, regulatory requirements, safety concerns, market demands, or other factors. The main drivers of a new standardization topic are the members of the National Standardization Bodies – NSBs). Relevant stakeholders, including industry representatives, regulatory bodies, academics, business and professional associations, consumer groups, environmental and labour organizations, may be involved in this phase. At this step, the new work item proposal shall be subject to public commenting to define whether there is an agreement on the need to develop a new standard or to revise an existing one. The need, scope and objectives of the standardization effort should be defined.

Preparation and planning

Once the needs are identified, the standardization process is planned and prepared. This involves assigning or establishing the appropriate technical working bodies (technical committees/subcommittees, working groups or workshops); determining the participating national standards organizations and the experts that will be involved in the development of the draft deliverable; establishing timelines and milestones; allocating resources; establishing organizational arrangements. An important issue to be addressed is the involvement of different stakeholders of the process.

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Development of a draft standard

Standards are developed based on technical expertise, scientific research, industry best practices, and input from stakeholders. This phase typically involves drafting the standard, conducting technical reviews, assessments and discussions, resolving conflicting viewpoints, and achieving consensus among participants of the working group or the technical body.

Consultation and consensus building

Draft standards are subject to consultation with stakeholders to gather feedback and address any concerns or suggestions for improvement. During the Enquiry stage the ESOs Members (NSBs) have the obligation to make available the draft standard for public comments. This consultation process aims to ensure that the standards reflect the needs and interests of all relevant parties and facilitate consensus building among diverse stakeholders.

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Approval and publication

Approval and adoption

Once consensus is reached and a positive voting outcome is registered, the draft standards are formally approved by the relevant standardization organizations. In the EU context, standards may be adopted as European Standards (ENs) by the European Committee for Standardization (CEN), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC), or the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), depending on the sector. Unlike international standards, which don't necessarily require national adoptions in order to be used by the end-users, a European Standard shall be implemented by the CEN and CENELEC members – the national standards organizations - as national standards.

Publication and distribution

Approved standards are published and made available to stakeholders, industry players, regulators, and the public in compliance with the copyright rules applicable to the respective deliverable. CEN and CENELEC standards and deliverables, their national adoptions and other technical related deliverables and publications are covered and protected by copyright. The standard body issuing the standard has the property and exploitation rights on it. Standards are typically listed in online catalogues (online databases) of the respective standardization organization, and offered to the standards users for purchase through online or physical webstores to ensure easy and fast access and distribution.

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Implementation and Compliance

Standards users are encouraged to implement the standards within their organizations or industries. Compliance with standards may be voluntary or mandatory (by exception), depending on regulatory requirements, market expectations or contractual agreements. Implementation may require training, auditing, conformity assessment (inspection, testing, certification), and other measures to ensure adherence to the standards.

Monitoring and Review

The implementation of standards is monitored to assess their effectiveness, technology and market relevance and impact. Typically, every 5 years a published standard is subject to a systematic review process. Feedback from stakeholders, performance data, market trends, and technological advancements are considered during the systematic review stage to ensure the standards remain relevant, up-to-date, and aligned with state-of-the-art technology, as well as with the evolving needs and practices. The outcome of the systematic review stage might lead to confirmation of the relevance of the standard or deliverable, withdrawal, decision for revision.

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Alignment between European and International standardization through cooperation

The European standardization organizations CEN and CENELEC actively cooperate with international standardization organizations ISO and IEC to align European standards with global best practices. This alignment enhances interoperability, facilitates trade, and promotes the acceptance of European standards worldwide.

Correspondence between European and International Standardization

	General	Electrotechnical	Telecommunication
International			
European (regional)			

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Topic 4: European market access: EAD, ETA and hEN. CWA simulation.

Module 4 “How to standardize innovative products “low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products” and “bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope””

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Technical Specification (TS)

Technical Report (TR)

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CEN and/or CENELEC Guides

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Harmonized European Standard
(hEN)

Technical Report (TR)

CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop
Agreement (CWA)

Technical Specification
(TS)

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CEN and/or CENELEC Guides

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Harmonized European Standard (hEN)

A standard developed by one of the European standardization organizations (CEN, CENELEC, or ETSI) following a request from the European Commission to one of these organisations for the implementation of the application of European Union harmonization legislation. The references of harmonized standards must be published in the Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU). These standards are developed to ensure products meet essential requirements set by EU legislation, facilitating the free movement of goods within the European Single Market. Compliance with hENs allows manufacturers to affix the CE marking to their products, indicating conformity with relevant EU directives and regulations.

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Harmonization Document (HD)

A HD is a normative document of CENELEC only.

CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA)

A CWA is an agreement developed and approved in a CEN or CENELEC Workshop. The workshop is open to the direct participation of anyone with an interest in the development of the agreement. There is no geographical limit on participation; hence, participants may be from outside Europe. The development of a CWA is fast and flexible, on average between 10-12 months. A CWA does not have the status of a European Standard.

CEN and/or CENELEC Guides

a Guide is a document that gives rules, orientation, advice or recommendations relating to European standardization.

CE marking

While TSs, TRs and CWAs are considered standardization documents, ENs and hENs are standards. The only deliverables in the above list which are used for CE marking are the hENs, this is especially relevant for construction products under the CPR (Regulation (EU) 305/2011, to date). Of course, hENs can be seen as a medium-term reference for today's innovative construction products, but hENs' development process is significantly longer and complicated, and hardly matches the market fast pace of innovative solutions.

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Technical Report (TR)

A TR is an informative standardization document (a document that describes useful or valuable information or offers help to understand concepts; may include recommendations, suggested good practice; no requirements for conformity included) that provides information on the technical content of standardization work. It may be prepared when it is considered urgent or advisable to provide additional information to the CEN and CENELEC national members, the European Commission, the EFTA Secretariat, other governmental agencies or outside bodies.

Technical Specification (TS)

A TS is a normative standardization document (a document that provides rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results), the development of which can be envisaged when various alternatives that would not gather enough as to allow agreement on a European Standard (EN), need to coexist in anticipation of future harmonization, or for providing specifications in experimental circumstances and/or evolving technologies.

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EN timeline

It's important to note that the standardization process usually takes a significant amount of time, spanning several months or several years, depending on the complexity, type and scope of the deliverable and the principles that need to be followed. For example, for a regular standard it takes about three years from first proposal to final publication. The reason is the involvement of multiple stakeholders, and the rigorous consultation process are crucial in producing effective and relevant standards that benefit society, industries, and consumers.

Innovation requires quick actions, outcomes and agile procedures to go to the market

Markets and industries, for which innovations are important, usually are dissatisfied with the long procedures of standards development. They require more flexible and rapid procedures for development of a reference document, which could timely enable the market uptake of innovative solutions and facilitate further innovations in the market. On the other hand, innovative solutions might have not reached a sufficient degree of reliability and maturity, which is needed for a European Standard to be developed.

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CE label

Placing construction products on the market requires CE marking, with some exceptions based on national qualifications and certifications (such as concrete and steel reinforcement bars, for example). CE marking is key to companies willing to place innovative construction products on the market. In lack of an applicable hEN, the potential development time of a new standard often becomes an obstacle moving the innovators towards alternative options.

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Differences between CWA and European standards

While standards are developed in Technical Committees with members from national delegations, CWAs are elaborated by temporary working groups according to CEN-CENELEC Guide 29 at workshops where individual interested parties could participate

CWA's development rules provide for direct and voluntary participation of stakeholders regardless of their participation in national TCs and they are an excellent forum for experts from R&I organizations, academia and industry to offer their innovative solutions for standardization

The approval of the document is subject to a decision of the registered participants in the workshop, and it is not subject to vote by CEN and CENELEC national members.

CWAs are developed under lighter and more rapid procedures, compared to regular standards

The working tools of the workshop are more agile, and flexible timeline and electronic communication and working tools could be preferred

Public consultation is not a mandatory stage of the CWA's development. It is optional but highly recommended in order to ensure as transparent process as possible

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Advantages of CWA

Open to all interested

Can become future European Standard

Specific document for R&I results

Flexible procedures

National implementation not mandatory

Fast elaboration

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DEVELOPMENT OF CEN AND/OR CENELEC WORKSHOP AGREEMENT - CWA

The development of CWAs is described in details in CEN-CENELEC Guide 29 “CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop Agreements – A rapid way to standardization”. The process that is going to be explained below is based on its third edition of March 2024. The Guide emphasizes that CWAs could be the preferred way of standardization particularly in cases of innovative solutions, which need faster market uptake, or assurance of interoperability and compatibility, or in cases where the Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) is not sufficient enough to start developing a European Standard (EN).

CWA could be addressed to a specific technology, a process or a specific methodology, or any other kind of innovative solution, and it is not necessary to address an innovation product in its completeness.

Definition of CWA: Guide 29 defines this type of standardization document as “CEN and/or CENELEC deliverable, developed by a CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop, which reflects an agreement between identified individuals and organizations responsible for its contents, and which is made available by CEN and/or CENELEC in at least one of the official languages”.

When it comes to innovative project outcomes or solutions, CWA offers additional advantages, compared to ENs: possibility to name the persons and organizations who participated in the CWA’s development in the Foreword of the document; the CWA’s development time span could fit into the timeframe of EU funded research and innovation projects in order to deliver verified and validated results.

It is important to emphasize that during the CWA creation all participants should be aware that a CWA shall not be in conflict with any EN (of Harmonization Document for CENELEC) and it is advisable to seek collaboration from a CEN or CENELEC technical body which is dealing with the related subjects. A support by a technical committee, for example, might ensure future sustainability of the CWA, if the topic is included in the committee’s future work programme.

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Technology Readiness Levels

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THE EUROPEAN TECHNICAL ASSESSMENT (ETA) AND THE EUROPEAN ASSESSMENT DOCUMENT (EAD)

- Another option for fast-track standardization and innovation uptake of research outcomes in the new building materials field, which needs to be considered, is given by the deliverables of the European Organisation for Technical Assessment (EOTA).
- The European Organisation for Technical Assessment (EOTA) is a Europe-wide association of Technical Assessment Bodies for construction products established under the Construction Products Regulation (CPR).

EUROPEAN ORGANISATION FOR TECHNICAL ASSESSMENT (EOTA)

EOTA is a non-profit organization, which provides the framework for the European Technical Assessment (ETA) of construction products to ensure consistent product performance information throughout Europe. The EOTA network is the only platform which allows European manufacturers of innovative or non-standard construction products to bring their products to the European market with CE marking. As stated in the previous chapter for standards, CE marking is crucial for construction products, with minor exceptions. In other words, in lack of a hENs ETAs are well known and largely used tools towards CE marking and product market placement on EU scale.

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European Technical Assessment (ETA)

- Provides an independent Europe-wide procedure for assessing the essential performance characteristics of non-standard construction products.
- The ETA offers manufacturers a voluntary route to CE marking, when the product is not or not fully covered by a harmonized standard (hEN) under the Construction Products Regulation (EU) 305/2011. CE marking based on the ETA allows manufacturers to freely market their product on the entire European internal market and introduce innovative products and new product features within short timeframes

Advantages

★ The ETA route is an efficient procedure ensuring the shortest possible processing time.

★ ETAs are recognized throughout Europe in all countries participating in the ETA procedure. The ETA also has a high international standing.

★ Only independent Technical Assessment Bodies (TABs) may issue ETAs. TABs are designated for the relevant product area by the EU Member and Partner States in accordance with the Construction Products Regulation (EU) No 305/2011. The independent assessment strengthens the credibility of the product performance information, enhances market transparency and builds customer trust.

★ ETAs provide reliable product performance information that is comparable across Europe based on European Assessment Documents (EADs).

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European Assessment Document (EAD)

Info

It is a harmonized technical specification developed by EOTA as the basis for ETAs.

In combination with the ETA, the EAD provides manufacturers with a way to CE marking for construction products that are not or not fully covered by a harmonized European standard under the Construction Products Regulation (EU) 305/2011.

Benefits

EADs can be tailored to a construction product;

The EAD development procedure could be kept confidential upon request to protect the manufacturer's competitive advantage;

After citation in the EU Official Journal, EADs can be downloaded for free from the EOTA website.

Development procedure

is initiated by a manufacturer's request for ETA, when harmonised criteria for the assessment of the product's performance are missing. The procedure is handled by a Technical Assessment Body - TAB, which the manufacturer has chosen. The TAB is supported by the EOTA network of highly qualified Technical Assessment experts.

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Development stages

1. ETA request of a manufacturer
2. Consultation of work and assessment programme; contract between the TAB and the manufacturer
3. Agreement on the final work programme and information to the EC
4. Drafting of the EAD
5. Adoption of draft EAD by the manufacturer, the responsible TAB and EOTA
6. Finalization of the EU legislative procedures (extensions and delays, where relevant)
7. EAD adoption by EOTA and the EC
8. Issuing of ETA and publication of reference of final EAD in Official Journal

Comparison between EN, CWA and ETA/EAD

Elements of the development process	EN	CWA	ETA/EAD
Procedures	Rigorous procedure with strict timing for public consultations and enquiry	More flexible and light procedures	Strictly defined procedures
Timing	Usually takes 3 years	Fast track – 10-12 months on average; time could be reduced even to 6 months, depending on the readiness	Fast track – The usual timeline for the development of an EAD set out in the Construction Products Regulation is 9 months.
Participation in development	National delegations of CEN and CENELEC members	Direct participation of experts and stakeholders Open to any company or organization	EOTA experts Member states representatives Manufacturers European Commission

Elements of the development process	EN	CWA	ETA/EAD
Approval	CEN and CENELEC members	Participating experts	EOTA European Commission
National adoption and publication	Mandatory	Optional	Not relevant
Allows for CE marking	Yes	No	Yes
Stakeholders involvement	Full open and transparent public consultation (manufacturer, end users, academia, researchers, consumer protection etc.)	From case to case, depends on the working group members	Only the manufacturer (group of) who asked for, EOTA and the EC

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	Advantages	Disadvantages
CWA	<p>Fast development</p> <p>Need to reach agreement among participants</p> <p>Possibility to conversion into another deliverable, as a TS or a TR or a European standard</p> <p>Does not entail significant costs</p>	<p>CWA is not equal to a standard. It is a standardization document.</p> <p>No right to affix CE marking</p> <p>No possible candidate for citation in OJEU</p>
ETA/EAD	<p>Fast development</p> <p>Harmonized technical specification</p> <p>No need to reach agreement of external stakeholders</p> <p>Right to affix CE marking (together with all applicable further obligations to the manufacturer, including the ones involving notified body)</p>	<p>Higher costs for obtaining ETA</p> <p>EAD needs to be published in Official Journal of the EU</p>

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Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

AFCOS

Topic 5: Eco-design regulation and Digital product passport

Module 4 “How to standardize innovative products “low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products” and “bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope””

Course “Specific rules for standardization of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products and bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings’ envelope”

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Eco-design regulation

On 28 June 2024, the EU published Regulation (EU) 2024/1781 establishing a framework for the setting of ecodesign requirements for sustainable products ("Ecodesign Regulation"). The Ecodesign Regulation has been in force since 18 July 2024 and is part of the European Green Deal. With the Green Deal, the European Commission aims to transform the European Union ("EU") into a competitive and climate-neutral circular economy.

To achieve this, the Ecodesign Regulation provides for minimum criteria to be applied to products to improve their recyclability and energy efficiency. In this way, the Ecodesign Regulation aims to permanently reduce the Union's carbon and environmental footprint. The Ecodesign Regulation thus joins a whole series of other sustainability-motivated legislation, such as the Battery Regulation ("EU-Batt-R") and the so-called Right to Repair Directive.

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Scope of Ecodesign

The Ecodesign Regulation applies to all physical goods that are placed on the market or put into service within the Union, including components and intermediate products ("Product"). Food, feed, medicinal products for human and veterinary use, living organisms and vehicles are excluded from the scope. It applies personally to economic operators who place such Products on the market or put them into service, i.e. authorised representatives, importers, distributors, dealers and fulfilment service providers in addition to manufacturers. In some cases, the Ecodesign Regulation also applies to operators of online marketplaces and online search engines.

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Ecodesign - application to basically all goods

In order to contribute to the functioning of the internal market and at the same time ensure a high level of environmental protection, the European Commission has extended the scope of the Ecodesign Directive to as many Products as possible. The Ecodesign requirements apply primarily to Products (or their raw materials) with a high environmental impact, such as Products containing cement, iron, steel or aluminium, but also Products such as textiles (especially garments and footwear), furniture (including mattresses), tyres, detergents and paints, lubricants, chemicals, energy related products and information and communication technology Products and other electronics. There is therefore no longer a restriction to energy related products such as washing machines, refrigerators or motors.

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Ecodesign - sustainable product design

The ecodesign requirements cover the entire life cycle of the respective Product, from manufacture, transport and operation to disposal or recycling. The Ecodesign Regulation itself provides the framework for the specific ecodesign requirements (see Article 5 Ecodesign Regulation).

Within this framework, certain minimum requirements are imposed on the Products concerned to ensure the sustainability of Products. Consequently, the Ecodesign Regulation itself does not set any specific requirements for Products. Instead, the European Commission fills these with life by adopting (subordinate) delegated acts (Article 4 para. 1 Ecodesign Regulation). The delegated acts set requirements for the reliability, reusability, reparability, energy use and energy efficiency of the specific product group they address. In addition, the delegated acts define the digital product passport (e.g. regarding commodity codes, unique product identifiers, instructions) and stipulate requirements for the label to be affixed to the Products (particularly with regard to the content, layout and manner in which the label is to be displayed to customers).

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Digital Product Passport - DPP

In order not to lose track of the numerous information obligations, the Ecodesign Regulation introduces the digital product passport. This should enable stakeholders along the value chain and consumers to quickly and easily access relevant information regarding the Products. Accordingly, in addition to the above-mentioned criteria, this product passport will contain information on the environmental sustainability of Products, whereby the exact requirements will also be specified by the European Commission in a delegated act. The first delegated act may enter into force not earlier than 19 July 2025. A comparison with the battery passport provisions of the EU-Batt-R shows that both passports contain a wide range of information and standardise safety requirements and compliance with technical standards. Both regulations also stipulate that the passports must be interoperable with other product passports in order to ensure consistent communication and data transfer.

The information obligations regarding unsold consumer products are worded more specifically. Economic operators who destroy unsold consumer products or have them destroyed are obliged, among other things, to report on the number and weight of Products discarded per year and the reasons for discarding. The European Commission will specify the details for the disclosure of the aforementioned information in an implementing act which shall be in force the latest on 19 June 2025.

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Obligation

For manufacturer

Most obligations apply to the manufacturer. A manufacturer is any natural or legal person that manufactures a Product or that has a Product designed or manufactured and markets that Product under their name or trademark. Manufacturers have to ensure that their Products fulfil the ecodesign requirements.

For authorised representative

Authorised representative means any natural or legal person established in the Union that has received a written mandate from the manufacturer to act on the manufacturer's behalf in relation to specified tasks with regard to the manufacturer's obligations under this regulation. The appointment of an authorised representative is not mandatory but is voluntary. In principle, the authorised representative does not have the same obligations as the manufacturer.

For distributor

Distributor is any natural or legal person in the supply chain, other than the manufacturer or the importer, that makes a Product available on the market. Distributors must ensure that the necessary information is available.

For importer

An importer within the meaning of the Ecodesign Regulation is any natural or legal person established in the Union that places a Product from a third country on the Union market.

Among other things, he must ensure that the manufacturer has fulfilled his obligations. In particular, this includes to check that the manufacturer has carried out a conformity assessment procedure, that the CE marking has been affixed, that all necessary information is available and that a product passport is available. Like the manufacturer the authorised representative is also subject to cooperation obligations.

For fulfilment service provider

Fulfilment service providers have significantly fewer obligations compared to other economic operators. They must ensure that the conditions during storage through to dispatch of the Products are not compromised.

For dealer

A dealer is a distributor or any other natural or legal person that offers Products for sale, hire or hire purchase, or that displays Products, to end users in the course of a commercial activity, including through distance selling; and includes any natural or legal person that puts a Product into service in the course of a commercial activity.

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Ecodesign penalties

In principle, Member States are obliged to adopt provisions on penalties for infringements of the Ecodesign Regulation (see Article 74 Ecodesign Regulation). The Member States must at least impose fines or time-limited exclusion from public procurement procedures.

Additionally, the Ecodesign Regulation provides for consumer claims for damages in the event of non-compliance of Products (see Article 76 Ecodesign Regulation). In this case, the manufacturer is primarily liable. If the manufacturer is not based in the EU, the importer or an authorised representative of the manufacturer is liable. If neither an importer nor an authorised representative is based in the EU, the fulfilment service provider is liable.

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Ecodesign conclusions

The Ecodesign Regulation marks a significant step towards a more sustainable product policy in the EU that contributes to achieving climate targets and promoting environmental protection. Even though no new obligations will apply directly to economic operators from 18 July 2024, they must nevertheless prepare for extensive changes and take early action to fulfil the new requirements. It is therefore advisable for affected companies to observe the transitional periods and monitor developments regarding the delegated acts in order to make the necessary adjustments in good time and avoid penalties.

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Construction Products Regulation (CPR)

The Construction Products Regulation (CPR) is a pivotal EU legislation that sets standardized safety, performance, and environmental impact requirements for construction products across the EU. Originally established in 2011 to streamline the circulation of construction products within the Single Market through standardized guidelines, the CPR was updated in 2024 to address modern environmental challenges, advancing sustainability and transparency in the construction sector. The CPR was published in the EU Official Journal in December 2024 and entered into force on January 7, 2025. The updated legislation defines key performance areas, includes harmonized CE marking rules, and mandates that Member States enforce safety and environmental requirements.

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What changed with the CPR update?

Digital Product Passports (DPP): The DPP is a digital repository of a product's technical specifications and environmental data, facilitating compliance and traceability across the EU market.

Enhanced CE marking: CE marking now reflects both technical performance and environmental impact, ensuring products meet comprehensive safety and sustainability requirements.

Environmental reporting standards: CPR requires manufacturers to report on climate-related indicators, particularly CO₂ emissions and energy usage, for priority construction products, with more indicators added gradually over the next few years.

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CPR - Standardized product performance and priority categories

Under the Construction Products Regulation (CPR), products must meet specific technical performance standards to ensure durability, safety, and overall reliability. The regulation prioritizes categories with high environmental impacts, particularly concrete, steel, and insulation materials, due to their significant embodied carbon and role in energy efficiency. Additional categories, including adhesives and paints, are also prioritized as critical construction materials. Standards for these priority categories are expected to roll out by 2026. The individual standards for these product categories will need to also be officially adopted for each priority category, before applying these standards.

Why is the CPR important for manufacturers outside of the EU?

For manufacturers outside the EU, aligning with CPR standards is critical to accessing and maintaining a position in the EU market. Compliance with CPR not only enables seamless market entry but also reduces the need for redundant testing and certifications across different EU member states. This unified compliance approach reduces administrative and financial burdens, enhancing market transparency and simplifying cross-border sales.

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CPR - Environmental reporting and Digital Product Passports (DPP)

The updated CPR requirements align with EN 15804, a European standard that establishes rules about creating Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) for construction products and materials. EPDs provide transparent and comparable information about the life-cycle environmental impact of products within specific product categories. They enable manufacturers to transparently communicate the environmental performance of their products and it allows AEC professionals to make sustainable choices by comparing similar products based on their EPDs.

The Digital Product Passport (DPP) is the primary means of reporting environmental data according to the CPR. The DPP will be mandatory for priority categories and will store standardized data that can be easily accessed by regulatory bodies and stakeholders, such as architects and building owners. This digitalization supports transparency and compliance checks, integrates with Building Information Modeling (BIM) systems, and ultimately improves data consistency across the entire EU market.

One of the most substantial updates in the 2024 CPR is the introduction of mandatory environmental reporting. Initially, manufacturers are required to report on climate impact indicators, specifically CO₂ emissions and energy consumption related to product manufacturing. As environmental standards evolve, additional metrics such as recyclability, resource efficiency, and toxicity will be phased in to provide a full lifecycle profile for each product.

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CPR - Expanded Declaration of Performance (DoP)

CPR compliance requires an expanded Declaration of Performance (DoP), which now includes environmental data in addition to traditional technical claims. The DoP acts as a comprehensive product dossier, detailing both performance and environmental standards that the product meets. This declaration is essential for regulatory authorities, as it ensures that all technical and environmental claims are verified and transparent.

Under the revised CPR, the DoP must report essential characteristics, including GWP, using defined performance levels, classes, or descriptions. These characteristics are specified in harmonised technical specifications, such as Harmonised European Standards (hENs) and European Assessment Documents (EADs). Until these specifications are updated to reflect the new CPR requirements, manufacturers should use the methodologies outlined in the current standards.

CPR - CE marking and its implications

The revised CPR integrates environmental criteria into the CE marking, which is now a mandatory indicator of both safety and environmental compliance. The enhanced CE marking requires manufacturers to verify that their products not only meet technical standards but also align with EU environmental goals, promoting responsible, transparent market practices. The updated CE marking system is intended to prevent "greenwashing" by holding manufacturers accountable for environmental claims through verified data.

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CPR - Harmonized standards and simplified compliance across the EU

The CPR's harmonized zone provides a cohesive regulatory framework for the EU, ensuring that CPR-compliant products are marketable across all member states without needing additional certifications. This harmonization is key to simplifying market entry, reducing the complexity of compliance, and eliminating redundant testing. Additionally, each EU country will have to establish Product Contact Points for Construction (PCPCs) to assist manufacturers in understanding specific regulatory requirements. These contact points are critical for manufacturers navigating regional variations and provide targeted support for new or complex compliance issues.

CPR - Tailored support for Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

To support smaller enterprises, CPR provides tailored options that reduce the costs and administrative burdens associated with full-scale testing. Micro-enterprises may submit simplified documentation verified by a third-party notified body, allowing them to bypass more extensive requirements. Additionally, manufacturers can rely on shared testing data for similar products, meaning products that have similar technical and environmental characteristics. For shared testing data to be accepted, it must be verified by a Notified Body, an independent organization authorized to assess conformity with EU standards.

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Overview of the new CPR timeframe

CPR – Implementation dates

Target dates: The regulation enters into force in January 7, 2025, and its application is set for January 8, 2026. However, compliance timelines will vary based on when standards for each product category are adopted.

Standards-dependent compliance: Full compliance for priority materials like concrete, steel, and insulation is expected around the end of 2025, starting with mandatory declaration of GWP. Requirements will become enforceable once individual standards are finalized.

Long-term alignment: By 2030, more comprehensive reporting, including full lifecycle environmental data, is expected. Early preparation will help manufacturers align with EU climate goals and maintain market access as these regulations phase in.

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